

DRIVe

Demand Response Integration tEchnologies:

Unlocking the demand response potential in the distribution grid

Project H2020 n° 774431

D7.1 Validation Plan

Project Coordinator: Meritxell Vinyals (CEA)

Work Package Leader: Aleksandar Kavgic (TH)

Deliverable Leader: Aleksandar Kavgic (TH)

With contributions from: Jan Bastiaensens & Eric Smets (ENER), Sergio Valentino Costa (COMSA), Murilo Alemeida, Victor Maryama, Jovana Markovic, Nikola Lepojevic & Aleksandar Kavgic (TH), Frits Maas (SCHOLT), Fanlin Meng and Monjur Mourshed (CU), Matthieu Gay (AIRBUS), Amy Taylor (BGCBC), Raymond Sterling (R2M)

1st Quality reviewer: Meritxell Vinyals (CEA)

2nd Quality reviewer: Raymond Sterling (R2M)

3rd Quality reviewer: Juan Espeche (R2M)

4th Quality reviewer: Massimiliano Raciti (R2M)

Deliverable nature:	Report (R)
Dissemination level: (Confidentiality)	Public (P)
Contractual delivery date:	30 November 2018 (M12)
Actual delivery date:	30 November 2018 (M12)
Version:	1.00
Total number of pages:	131
Keywords:	validation, validation plan, key performance indicator, KPI, scenario descriptions, use cases, step-by-step scenario

Abstract

This document provides a high-level description of validation activities envisaged for DRiVE as the next-generation, multi-agent demand response (DR) solution, as well as a general timeline of validation activities in the project. Although the validation scenarios are devised for the DRiVE platform and test sites, the scenarios should be universally applicable to other sites and other remote-controlled devices. The document first provides the description of the three different modes of validation activities – offline simulation, real-time cyber and cyber-physical emulation, and physical testing – which allow for a safe optimization and testing of DR services before deployment to the test site. The biggest innovation in this respect is the introduction of the cyber-physical emulation as a testing mode, which means that multi-agent system and DR logic can be fully tested in complete safety, because this kind of testing implies that local energy gateways are connected to high-fidelity models of controlled devices, providing direct insight into behaviour of the DRiVE logic and algorithm, but in the safety of virtualized power (devices are real-time models). After the modes of validation, the document provides the overview of the key performance indicators (KPIs) which are traditionally used to assess the DR system, where the main inference is that the KPIs which can be found in relevant references do not focus on individual services provided in DR programs, but at the general performance of the system from the point of view of large utilities. This conclusion represents the foundation for devising specialized, individual KPIs for various DR services which are to be provided via the DRiVE system. The main chapter of the document, entitled “Validation Scenarios”, therefore contains step-by-step descriptions of use cases and specialized KPIs for validating and assessing the DRiVE performance in each use case. Validation scenarios are organized into six main sections per type of the use case and service, where the first five sections contain use case descriptions of 1) in-building services for the prosumers, 2) community services, 3) flexibility services for the balance responsible parties (BRP), 4) flexibility services for the distribution system operators (DSO) and 5) flexibility services for the transmission system operators (TSO), while the final section contains an overview of cyber security validation and relevant KPIs. The penultimate chapter of the document provides a tentative validation timeline organized per test sites and services being validated at each site, where the overarching principle is to provide about a year of physical testing (that should cover all seasons) which is preceded by a shorter, four-month period of cyber-physical testing which can be used to fully test and optimize the control services before they are deployed for physical testing in the grid. The final chapter of the document provides a general overview of the strategies which will be used to ensure the reliability of the results. At the end of the document there is, of course, a conclusion and the list of references, as well as four annexes: the first annex contains the data capability matrix, the second annex contains the list of KPIs, the third annex contains the list of DRiVE actors (which feature in use cases), and the fourth annex contains the list of requirements for each use case.

Document Information

IST Project Number	H2020 - 774431	Acronym	DRIVe
Full Title	Demand Response Integration tEchnologies: Unlocking the demand response potential in the distribution grid		
Project URL	https://www.h2020-drive.eu/		
Document URL	https://www.h2020-drive.eu/publications/		
EU Project Officer	Francesco Liberati		
Acknowledgement	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Grant Agreement n°774431.		
Disclaimer	<p>The opinion stated in this report reflects the opinion of the authors and not the opinion of the European Commission nor that of the Innovation Networks Executive Agency.</p> <p>All DRIVe consortium members are also committed to publish accurate and up to date information and take the greatest care to do so. However, the DRIVe consortium members cannot accept liability for any inaccuracies or omissions nor do they accept liability for any direct, indirect, special, consequential or other losses or damages of any kind arising out of the use of this information.</p>		

Deliverable	Number	D7.1	Title	Validation plan
Work Package	Number	WP7	Title	Demonstration and Validation

Date of Delivery	Contractual	M12	Actual	M12
Status	version 1.00		For submission: final version	
Nature	Report			
Dissemination level	Public			

Authors (Partner)	Jan Bastiaensens & Eric Smets (ENER), Sergio Valentino Costa (COMSA), Murilo Alemeida, Victor Maryama, Jovana Markovic, Nikola Lepojevic & Aleksandar Kavagic (TH), Frits Maas (SCHOLT), Fanlin Meng and Monjur Mourshed (CU), Matthieu Gay (AIRBUS), Amy Taylor (BGCBC), and Raymond Sterling (R2M)
--------------------------	---

Deliverable leader	Name	Meritxell Vinyals	E-mail	Meritxell.vinyals@cea.fr
	Partner	CEA	Phone	+33 (0)1 69 08 14 70

Abstract (for dissemination)	This deliverable, D7.1 “Validation plan” provides the overview of validation scenarios that will serve as a reference throughout the project for all demonstration and validation activities. It will serve all partners as a reference point on how individual DRiVE services should be tested and validated, as well as what key performance indicators (KPIs) to use for each service.
Keywords	validation, validation plan, key performance indicator, KPI, scenario descriptions, use cases, step-by-step scenario

Version Log			
Issue Date	Rev. No.	Author	Change
2018-04-10	0.1	Aleksandar Kavagic	Outline of the document drafted for WP7 no. 5 meeting
2018-04-25	0.2	Aleksandar Kavagic	Feedback from WP7 no. 5 meeting integrated: removed tables that have been done in D2.3 and D2.4
2018-05-09	0.3	Aleksandar Kavagic	Number identifiers for use cases and test sites added into Table 1, also a couple of typos corrected
2018-05-22	0.4	Aleksandar Kavagic	Table 1 and all other sections updated in accordance with the latest version of the Summary table (section 4.6) from D2.3
2018-06-19	0.5	Murilo Almeida, Aleksandar Kavagic	The draft version of the unified list of actors added, the general description of Voltage Control use case/validation scenario added
2018-07-04	0.6	Aleksandar Kavagic	Major changes to the outline: decisions from the technical workshop and GA meeting implemented (simplified scenario descriptions, cybersecurity not a use case in its own right, etc.)
2018-08-04	0.7	Sergio Valention Costa, Jan Basteins, Frits Maas, Jovana Markovic, Nikola Lepojevic, Aleksandar Kavagic	Main Use Case sections (chapter 3) have been drafted by COMSA, Enervalis, SCHOLT and Typhoon HIL.
2018-08-20	0.8	Jan Basteins, Jovana Markovic, Nikola Lepojevic, Aleksandar Kavagic	Additional info on community optimization, voltage control, power quality support and frequency containment/restoration reserve have been added; updates to KPI
2018-09-14	0.85	Eric Smets, Aleksandar Kavagic	Updates to KPIs which make them implementable in the porta and GUI; cyber security KPIs added as a separate section
2018-09-25	0.9	Aleksandar Kavagic	Harmonization of the document, improving consistency and cohesion, minimization of acronym usage; updates to the section on the validation platform and validation timeline
2018-09-31	0.91	Aleksandar Kavagic	Formatting issues regarding table/figure naming and numbering
2018-10-05	0.92	Aleksandar Kavagic	Harmonization of the document, improving consistency and cohesion,

			minimization of acronyms; updates to the section on the validation platform and validation timeline
2018-10-20	0.95	Raymond Sterling Aleksandar Kavgic	Suggestions from R2M reviewers integrated: removal of the Woerden site description and various stylistic/grammar changes
2018-10-23	0.97	Eric Smets	Suggestions from CEA reviewer integrated and the addition of the NRGcoin description
2018-10-26	1.0	Aleksandar Kavgic	List of actors and requirements moved to the annex: fixes to table and figure numbering Terminological consistency issues fixed (test site vs. pilot site, consumer portal vs. customer portal, kWmax vs. KWmax, etc.) Conclusion added Strategies for ensuring the reliability of the validation results is a separate chapter before conclusion

Table of Contents

1	INTRODUCTION	16
1.1	Purpose and scope	16
1.2	Structure of the document	16
1.3	Standards used.....	17
1.4	Relationships to previous outcomes and specific contents of this document	18
2	BACKGROUND: VALIDATION AIMS, MODES AND PRE-EXISTING KPIS	19
2.1	Validation platform	19
2.2	Validation activities: modes of validation	21
2.2.1	Modes of validation: physical testing	21
2.2.2	Modes of validation: non-physical testing	22
2.2.3	Modes of validation for each DR service and each test site	24
2.3	Validation activities: data collection.....	25
2.4	Validation activities: pre-existing KPIs for DR.....	26
2.4.1	The purpose of DR	27
2.4.1.1	Types of DR	27
2.4.2	General info on KPIs for DR	27
2.4.2.1	Consumption efficiency KPIs	28
2.4.2.2	Energy shift KPIs	29
2.4.2.3	Demand reduction KPIs for DR systems with Load Serving Entities (LSEs) and third-party aggregators.....	30
2.4.2.4	Prediction accuracy KPI.....	31
2.4.2.4.1	Prediction and forecast: definition of terms.....	31
2.4.2.4.2	Prediction KPIs	31
2.4.2.5	Forecast accuracy KPI.....	31
2.4.2.5.1	Load/Demand Forecast KPIs	31
2.4.2.5.2	Renewable Generation Forecast KPIs	32
2.4.2.6	Economic-related KPIs	32
2.4.2.7	Technical KPIs	33
2.4.3	KPIs for the DRiVE platform	34
3	VALIDATION SCENARIOS	35
3.1	In-building services for the prosumer: validation scenarios	35
3.1.1	ToU optimisation: validation scenarios	36
3.1.1.1	General info on the scenario.....	36
3.1.1.1.1	Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario	36
3.1.1.2	Diagrams of the validation scenario.....	37
3.1.1.3	Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario	38
3.1.1.3.1	Overview of the scenario	38
3.1.1.3.2	Steps of the scenario	39
3.1.1.4	ToU optimisation: validation scenarios for Blaenau Gwent District	42
3.1.1.5	ToU optimisation: validation scenarios for COMSA Head Office	43
3.1.2	kWmax Control: validation scenarios.....	43
3.1.2.1	General info on the scenario.....	44
3.1.2.1.1	Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario	44
3.1.2.2	Diagrams of the validation scenario.....	46
3.1.2.3	Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario	47
3.1.2.3.1	Overview of the scenario	47
3.1.2.3.2	Steps of the scenario	48
3.1.2.4	kWmax Control: validation scenarios for Blaenau Gwent District.....	53

3.1.2.5	kWmax Control: validation scenarios for the ADO Stadium	54
3.1.2.6	kWmax Control: validation scenarios for COMSA Head Office	54
3.1.3	Consumer Portal: validation scenarios	54
3.1.3.1	General info on the scenario.....	55
3.1.3.1.1	Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario: Consumer Portal	57
3.1.3.2	Diagrams of the validation scenario.....	59
3.1.3.2.1	Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario	60
3.1.3.2.2	Overview of the scenario	60
3.2	Community services: validation scenarios	63
3.2.1	Smart community based on NRGcoin market principles.....	64
3.2.1.1	General info on the scenario.....	64
3.2.1.1.1	Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario	65
3.2.1.2	Diagrams of the validation scenario.....	66
3.2.1.2.1	Overview of the scenario	67
3.2.1.2.2	Steps of the scenario	68
3.2.1.3	Community Optimisation: specificities of validation scenarios at test sites.....	69
3.3	Flexibility services for the BRP: validation scenarios	69
3.3.1	Portfolio management: validation scenarios	69
3.3.1.1	General info on the scenario.....	69
3.3.1.1.1	Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario	69
3.3.1.2	Diagrams of the validation scenario.....	70
3.3.1.3	Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario	71
3.3.1.3.1	Overview of the scenario	71
3.3.1.3.2	Steps of the scenario	71
3.3.1.4	Portfolio management: validation scenarios for the DEVO Residential District.....	73
3.3.1.5	Portfolio management: validation scenarios for the ADO stadium	73
3.3.1.6	Portfolio management: validation scenarios for the Giessenwind wind farm	73
3.3.1.7	Portfolio management: validation scenarios for the Woerden site	73
3.4	Flexibility services for the DSO: validation scenarios.....	74
3.4.1	Congestion management: validation scenarios	74
3.4.1.1	General info on the scenario.....	74
3.4.1.1.1	Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario	75
3.4.1.2	Diagrams of the validation scenario.....	77
3.4.1.3	Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario	78
3.4.1.3.1	Overview of the scenario	78
3.4.1.3.2	Steps of the scenario	79
3.4.1.4	Congestion management: validation scenarios for the DEVO.....	81
3.4.1.5	Congestion management: validation scenarios for the ADO Stadium.....	81
3.4.1.6	Congestion management: validation scenarios for the Giessenwind wind farm	81
3.4.2	Voltage control: validation scenarios.....	81
3.4.2.1	General info on the scenario.....	82
3.4.2.1.1	Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario	82
3.4.2.2	Diagrams of the validation scenario.....	83
3.4.2.3	Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario	83
3.4.2.3.1	Overview of the scenario	83
3.4.2.3.2	Steps of the scenario	84
3.4.2.4	Voltage control: validation scenarios for the Giessenwind wind farm	86
3.4.2.5	Voltage control: validation scenarios for the COMSA Head Office	87
3.4.2.6	Voltage control: validation scenarios for the Woerden site	87
3.4.3	Power quality support: validation scenarios	87
3.4.3.1	General info on the scenario.....	87
3.4.3.1.1	Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario	88
3.4.3.2	Diagrams of the validation scenario.....	88
3.4.3.3	Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario	89
3.4.3.3.1	Overview of the scenario	89

3.4.3.3.2	Steps of the scenario	90
3.4.3.4	Power quality support: validation scenarios for the Giessenwind wind farm.....	92
3.4.3.5	Power quality support: validation scenarios for the COMSA Head Office	92
3.4.3.6	Power quality support: validation scenarios for the Woerden site.....	92
3.5	Flexibility services for the TSO: validation scenarios	92
3.5.1	Frequency containment reserve: validation scenarios	93
3.5.1.1	General info on the scenario.....	93
3.5.1.1.1	Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario	93
3.5.1.2	Diagrams of the validation scenario.....	94
3.5.1.3	Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario	94
3.5.1.3.1	Overview of the scenario	94
3.5.1.3.2	Steps of the scenario	95
3.5.1.4	Frequency containment reserve: validation scenarios for the ADO stadium.....	97
3.5.1.5	Frequency containment reserve: validation scenarios for the Giessenwind Wind Farm	97
3.5.1.6	Frequency containment reserve: validation scenarios for the COMSA Head Office	97
3.5.1.7	Frequency containment reserve: validation scenarios for the Woerden site	97
3.5.2	Frequency restoration reserve: validation scenarios	97
3.5.2.1	General info on the scenario.....	97
3.5.2.1.1	Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario	98
3.5.2.2	Diagrams of the validation scenario.....	98
3.5.2.3	Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario	99
3.5.2.3.1	Overview of the scenario	99
3.5.2.3.2	Steps of the scenario	99
3.5.2.4	Frequency restoration reserve: validation scenarios for the DEVO Residential District.....	101
3.5.2.5	Frequency restoration reserve: validation scenarios for the ADO stadium	101
3.5.2.6	Frequency restoration reserve: validation scenarios for the Giessenwind wind farm.....	101
3.5.2.7	Frequency restoration reserve: validation scenarios for the COMSA Head Office	102
3.5.2.8	Frequency restoration reserve: validation scenarios for the Woerden site.....	102
3.6	Cyber security: validation scenarios.....	102
3.6.1	Forecast correlation: validation scenario	102
3.6.2	Intrusion on AMQP message queue: validation scenario	103
3.6.3	Malicious firmware upload: validation scenario.....	103
3.6.4	Unauthorized access to HMI: validation scenario	103
3.6.5	Summary of cyber security KPIs	104
4	VALIDATION TIMELINE	105
4.1	Validation timeline for in-building services for the prosumer	106
4.2	Validation timeline for Community services	107
4.3	Validation timeline for Flexibility services for the BRP	107
4.4	Validation timeline for Flexibility services for the DSO.....	107
4.5	Validation timeline for Flexibility services for the TSO	108
5	STRATEGIES TO ENSURE RELIABILITY OF RESULTS.....	109
5.1	Strategies for ensuring the reliability of the results of physical testing.....	109
5.2	Strategies for ensuring the reliability of the results of non-physical (virtualized) testing.....	109
6	CONCLUSION.....	111
7	REFERENCES	112
ANNEX A	MATRIX OF DATA CAPABILITIES OF EACH TEST SITES.....	113
ANNEX B	KPIS DEvised FOR VALIDATION OF DRIVE SERVICES.....	114
ANNEX C	A UNIFIED LIST OF USE CASE ACTORS	122

ANNEX D A UNIFIED LIST OF USE CASE REQUIREMENTS 127

List of figures

Figure 1: DRIVe validation platform: initial version from the Grant Agreement	20
Figure 2: DRIVe validation platform: the new version, as of month 12 (M12), which shows the developments introduced beyond the version in the GA	20
Figure 3: DRIVe validation platform modes of testing: physical testing.....	22
Figure 4: DRIVe validation platform modes of testing: hybrid cyber-physical testing	24
Figure 5: Diagram of the ToU use case as shown in D2.3 Section 3.1.2.....	37
Figure 6: Sequence Diagram of the General kWmax Optimisation Use Case	38
Figure 7: kWmax VC 02: Loss of communication with MPC.....	41
Figure 8: ToU02: Loss of communication with MPC	42
Figure 9: Diagram of the kWmax use case, as described in D2.3 section 3.2.2	46
Figure 10: Sequence Diagram of the General kWmax Optimisation Use Case	47
Figure 11: kWmax KWM2	51
Figure 12: kWmax KWM3	52
Figure 13: kWmax KWM4	53
Figure 14: Actors and interactions for use case consumer portal	60
Figure 15: A possible visual representation of NRGcoin operation in the graphical user interface.....	65
Figure 16: Actors and interactions for the use case Smart Community Based on NRGcoin Market Principle (adapted from D2.3).....	67
Figure 17: The diagram of the general Porfolio management scenario	70
Figure 18: The USEF timing cycle, as used in the Netherlands	75
Figure 19: The diagram of the general Congestion Management scenario.....	78
Figure 20: The diagram of the general Voltage Control scenario.....	83
Figure 21: The diagram of the general Power Quality Support scenario.....	89
Figure 22: The diagram of the general Frequency Containment Reserve scenario	94
Figure 23: The diagram of the general Frequency Restoration Reserve scenario	99
Figure 24: High-level strategies for validating models and ensuring the reliability of the results	110

List of tables

Table 1: Services tested at each test site and their simulation mode (based on outcomes from D2.3), where ● means that the scenario will definitively be implemented and ○ means that the scenario will potentially be implemented, depending on potential issues, or lack thereof, in setting up the DRiVE platform and integrating its components	24
Table 2: KPIs for measuring the energy efficiency of DR programs/systems	28
Table 3: KPIs for measuring the energy shift efficiency of DR programs/systems.....	29
Table 4: KPIs for the general ToU validation scenario.....	36
Table 5: Scenario conditions for the general ToU validation scenario	38
Table 6: Step-by-step description of the general ToU optimisation validation scenario TOU01.....	39
Table 7: Step-by-step description of the failure scenario Loss of communication with MPC (TOU02).	41
Table 8: Step-by-step description of the alternative Occupant override of DRiVE solution validation scenario TOU03.	42
Table 9: KPIs for the general kWmax Contol validation scenario	44
Table 10: Scenario conditions for the general kWmax Contol validation scenario.....	47
Table 11: Step-by-step description of the kWmax Control validation scenario KWM1.	49
Table 12: Step-by-step description of the failure scenario for the loss of communication with MPC (KWM2).....	51
Table 13: Step-by-step description of the alternative occupant override of DRiVE solution validation scenario KWM3.	52
Table 14: Customer portal (adapted from D2.3)	55
Table 15: Customer portal energy saving (adapted from D2.3).....	56
Table 16: KPIs for the general Consumer Portal validation scenario	57
Table 17: Scenario conditions for the general Consumer Portal validation scenario	61
Table 18: KPIs for the general Community Optimisation validation scenario	65
Table 19: Scenario conditions for the general Community Optimisation validation scenario	67
Table 20: Step-by-step description of the general Community Optimisation validation scenarios CS1, CS2 and CS3	68
Table 21: KPIs for the general Portfolio Management validation scenario	69
Table 22: Scenario conditions for the general Portfolio Management validation scenario	71
Table 23: Step-by-step description of the general Portfolio Management validation scenario PM01 ..	71
Table 24: Step-by-step description of the general Portfolio Management validation scenario PM02 ..	72
Table 25: KPIs for the general Congestion Management validation scenario	75
Table 26: Scenario conditions for the Congestion Management validation scenarios	78
Table 27: Step-by-step description of the Congestion Management validation scenarios CM1, CM2 and CM3	80
Table 28: KPIs for the general Voltage Control validation scenario	82
Table 29: Scenario conditions for the general Voltage Control validation scenario	83
Table 30: Step-by-step description of the Voltage Control validation scenario VC1	84
Table 31: Step-by-step description of the Voltage Control validation scenario VC2.....	85
Table 32: KPIs for the general Power Quality Support validation scenario	88
Table 33: Scenario conditions for the Power Quality Support validation scenarios.....	89
Table 34: Step-by-step description of the Power Quality Support validation scenario PQS1	90
Table 35: Step-by-step description of the general Power Quality Support validation scenario PQS2 ..	90
Table 36: KPIs for the general Frequency Containment Reserve validation scenario.....	93
Table 37: Scenario conditions for the Frequency Containment Reserve validation scenario.....	95
Table 38: Step-by-step description of the Frequency Containment Reserve validation scenario FCR1	95
Table 39: KPIs for the general Frequency Restoration Reserve validation scenario.....	98
Table 40: Scenario conditions for the Frequency Restoration Reserve validation scenario.....	99

Table 41: Step-by-step description of the Frequency Restoration Reserve validation scenario FRR1	100
Table 42: KPIs for Cyber Security	104
Table 43: General validation timeline for all DRiVE functionalities at all test sites (orange = physical testing, green = emulation and/or hybrid cyber-physical testing, grey =offline simulation)	105
Table 44: Validation timeline for in-building services for the prosumer	106
Table 45: Validation timeline for community services	107
Table 46: Validation timeline for flexibility services for the BRP	107
Table 47: Validation timeline for flexibility services for the DSO	107
Table 48: Validation timeline for flexibility services for the TSO	108
Table 49: A unified list of 22 actors that play a role in Use Case scenarios	122
Table 50: A unified list of technical requirements for Use Case scenarios	127
Table 51: A unified list of pilot-site requirements for Use Case scenarios.....	128

List of abbreviations and acronyms

As this document sets out to outline the validation scenarios and key performance indicators for the assessment of next-generation, multi-agent demand response systems, it is rather broad in its scope. Consequently, the of abbreviations and acronyms may be slightly longer than in some other documents, but this represents a reflection of the nature and scope of the document. Over the course of writing the document (approximately 8 months), constant care was taken by the contributors and peer reviewers to minimize the use of acronyms and abbreviations - for the sake of semantic transparency and general readability of a public deliverable. Nonetheless, some frequently used terms are given in the text as acronyms, in particular the ones given in the table below.

BRP	Balance Responsible Party
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CUSP	Computational Urban Sustainability Platform, a forecasting and offline simulation platform: superseded by REEFS
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
FCR	Frequency Containment Reserve
FRR	Frequency Restoration Reserve
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HIL	Hardware In the Loop
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEC	Local Energy Community
LEG	Local Energy Gateway
LOI	Letter of Intent
LV	Low Voltage
MAS	Multi Agent System
MPC	Model Predictive Control
MV	Medium Voltage
OPEX	Operating Expenses
REEFS	Real-time Energy and Environmental Forecasting and Simulation: a platform developed by CU, previously called CUSP
REST API	REpresentational State Transfer Application Program Interface; a program interface that uses HTTP requests to GET, PUT, POST and DELETE data
USEF	Universal Smart Energy Framework

VC	Voltage Control
----	-----------------

1 INTRODUCTION

This section provides information on the purpose and scope of the document, an outline of the structure of the document, standards used in the document and the relationship to other project activities and outcomes.

1.1 PURPOSE AND SCOPE

This document provides general information on validation scenarios which are envisaged to be used in the DRiVE project to both validate the functionality of the DRiVE solution and to validate its upgrades and benefits, as specified in the project proposal and grant agreement (taken from DRiVE Abstract): “Overall, DRiVE will make available average 20% of load in residential and tertiary buildings for use in DR, resulting in up to 30% cost-saving (price-based DR) and also maximizing revenue for prosumers (incentive-based DR). DRiVE will also allow a minimum 25% increase of renewable hosting capacity (distribution grid) and up to 30% of overall reduction of CAPEX and OPEX costs for DSOs.”

Ultimately, the goal of the document is to provide a methodological framework for how to conduct (validation scenarios) and assess (key performance indicators) services provided by the DRiVE solution using the testing and validation environment being developed in Task 7.3 (to be reported in D7.2), but also to provide a tentative timeline for conducting test and validation activities in Task 7.4 (to be reported in D7.3).

In regard to the ultimate goal of the document, as specified above, two disclaimers and/or clarification are in order. First, it should be noted that the methodological framework, including key performance indicators for assessing the performance and upgrade in the state-of-the-art of various services to be provided by DRiVE, is firmly established and should be considered immutable. On the other hand, the validation timeline is labelled as “tentative” for practical reasons which are not entirely within the control of the consortium: 1) at the time of writing, the validation platform of DRiVE is still being specified and set up, so it is possible that some tests will be moved on the timeline in order to accommodate technical difficulties (or the lack thereof) in setting up the validation platform and making it operational, and 2) the DRiVE services which can be tested in each test site (particularly at the Giessenwind Wind Farm, ADO Stadium and the Woerden site) were, at the time when this document was finalized, still being negotiated among the site operators, site owners, site inhabitants and other relevant stakeholders and decisionmakers, meaning that there is non-negligible margin of possibility that the consortium will not be allowed to pilot and validate some of the originally DRiVE services originally planned for each test site.

1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The document is organized so as to first provide relevant background information (Chapter 2), then the validation methodology, scenarios and key performance indicators (Chapter 3), and, finally, the tentative validation timeline. Annexes contain data capabilities of test sites, as well as the integral version of all key performance indicators: the KPIs are given in each section for each type of service, but the annex summarizes them all in a single place for better readability.

First, the document provides background information on the types of testing and validation activities which were envisaged in the Grant Agreement and presents background information on KPIs which have been previously used, either in other DR projects and/or in industry, to assess various aspects of DR programs and systems. This section also provides additional information on test sites, in particular

the information which only became available after the submission of deliverables from the WP2 which contained detailed descriptions of test sites.

After this general discussion, in its most exhaustive sections, the document provides detailed descriptions of validation scenarios which will be used to test and validate each DR service provided by the DRiVe platform. These sections are organized by the type of service which is being provided, and not by test site: these sections first provide a universal validation scenario and key performance indicators for a particular service and then, if it was deemed necessary, provide details on the specificities and peculiarities of how each service is to be tested and validated at each test site where it was envisaged for it to be tested.

Finally, the document provides a tentative timeline of how the testing and validation scenarios are to be implemented in the project, which is followed by a brief description of the strategies which will be used to ensure the reliability of the results.

1.3 STANDARDS USED

The main standards and/or frameworks used in this document are Smart Grid Architecture Methodology (SGAM), Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) and IEC 62559-2.

The Smart Grid Architecture Methodology (SGAM) and the Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) are rarely referenced in this document, but the document is entirely based on them. Namely, these standards were used in deliverables from Work Package 2 which formed the basis and input for this document: D2.3 DRiVe design and development requirements, D2.4 DRiVe integration requirements and D2.5 DRiVe ICT infrastructure. As this document only defines KPIs and maps and characterizes test scenarios for the use cases and test sites, which are all already defined in WP2 reports, USEF and SGAM compliance is inherited, i.e. it stems from the USEF and SGAM compliance of the previously mentioned deliverables.

The IEC 62559-2 standard for use case methodology is used in this document for descriptions and specifications of validation scenarios, but the standard is used in a modified, streamlined form which suits the purpose of a public report. There were two main reasons why the IEC 62559-2 standard was streamlined. The first reason for streamlining of the standard is the public nature of the deliverable: a less complex and more readable presentation of the contents benefits the overarching aim of this deliverable in terms of public visibility and transparency. The second reason for streamlining of the IEC 62559 standard was conciseness. More explicitly, it was the fact that an IEC 62559-compliant document which describes five use cases with several scenarios for each use case at several test sites would grow in size to four or five hundred pages of detailed technical descriptions which would be contrary to the purpose of the deliverable, as a transparent, public report on how to test next-generation demand response systems that provide ancillary services and how to assess their performance.

For the sake of avoiding any terminological confusion, in this document the term “use case” refers to one or more “test/validation scenarios” which serve the purpose of validating a specific functionality (e.g. voltage control) of the DRiVe platform at one or more test sites. It is important to emphasize that the terms “test scenario” and “validation scenario”, as well as terms “test site” and “pilot site”, are considered to be interchangeable and are assumed to have the same meaning, but this report, for the sake of consistency, uses only the term “validation scenario” and “test site”

1.4 RELATIONSHIPS TO PREVIOUS OUTCOMES AND SPECIFIC CONTENTS OF THIS DOCUMENT

As a part of a project, and as it has already been indirectly explained in the previous section on the standards used, this document does not provide the entire use case specification. Instead, it builds upon the foundations of use case descriptions set in D2.3, D2.4 and D2.5 which feed this document with a) the general descriptions of use cases, b) diagrams for each use case, c) technical details (including actors, use case conditions, classification information and references), d) requirements and e) common terms and definitions.

In other words, this document focuses on:

- a) step-by-step analysis of validation scenarios in each use case, which specifically includes validation scenario conditions and validation scenarios themselves,
- b) key performance indicators (KPIs) for each scenario,
- c) validation timeline, and
- d) identification of general strategies for ensuring the reliability of results.

It should be noted that the document does not provide the definitive specification for a), and c) mentioned above. It is assumed that scenario conditions and steps may need to be altered during the process of setting up the testing environments and identification of best practices for validation of DRIVe. In short, the definitive scenarios and scenario conditions will be specified in D7.2, i.e. in the report on “Testing environments setting up & best practices” (due to be finished in M24). Likewise, the validation timeline may also have to be altered in line with practical issues encountered during the process of setting up the testing environments. Hence, the definitive versions of information exchanged, as well as KPIs, will also be provided in D7.2.

Ultimately, this document provides the best-case version of validation scenarios, KPIs and validation timeline. On the other hand, D7.2 will provide the actual overview of the implemented scenarios, actual information exchanged and the final definitions of KPIs. Similarly, D7.2 and D7.3 will provide more details on how the strategies for ensuring the reliability of results have been implemented.

2 BACKGROUND: VALIDATION AIMS, MODES AND PRE-EXISTING KPIS

Having in mind that the primary objective of WP7 is to show and prove that DRiVe flexibility solutions developed in WP2-WP6 are fully functional in real-life grid-connected applications – both in terms of effective management of flexibility and provision of cyber security services – the project must rely on a wide set of testing activities to validate and demonstrate the benefits and upgrades of the state of the art provided by the DRiVe technologies and its flexibility management platform. The ultimate goal of the entire WP7 is to develop a comprehensive, modular validation platform which can run a set of validation scenarios for the purpose of demonstrating the functionality and benefits of the DRiVe platform.

For the sake of terminological unambiguity, the term ‘validation’ in this document is used in its standardized definition, as specified in the fourth sense division of the ISO/IEC/IEEE International Standard on Systems and software engineering – Vocabulary: “the process of evaluating a system or component during or at the end of the development process to determine whether a system or component satisfies specified requirements.” [1] As such, validation activities verify the fittingness and comprehensiveness of the product and/or system and confirm that the system actually meets the requirements and specifications devised in the development phase.

2.1 VALIDATION PLATFORM

Within the DRiVe project, the specification and setting-up of the validation platform is the scope of T7.3 (providing D7.2 in M24) on “Testing environments setting up & best practices”. However, for the sake of full transparency and clarity, the validation plan should include a brief description of the validation platform which will be used to conduct validation activities, which is the purpose of this section

The initial architecture of the validation platform, as specified in the Grant Agreement, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: DRIVe validation platform: initial version from the Grant Agreement

It should be noted that the architecture depicted in Figure 1 was based on the relatively vague understating of technical detail relating to partners’ technologies and technical solutions, which is why the architecture lacks some details. Moreover, one of the main components changed its name: CUSP (Computational Urban Sustainability Platform) by CU has been renamed to REEFS (Real-time Energy and Environmental Forecasting and Simulation). The change of name from CUSP to REEFS was done after extensive research and careful considerations by CU, mainly because CUSP is static and does not reflect the real-time forecasting nature determined in the project programme. REEFS, on the other hand is focused on real-time streaming data architecture and can also better reflect that from its literal meaning.

Over the first ten months of intense and focused drill-down into current capabilities of partners systems and solutions, and their possible demand-response-related upgrades, it became clear that the overall architecture of the validation platform will be more complex, and, therefore, different from the initially envisaged one, but, simultaneously, that some elements of it will be placed in different positions within the overall architecture. Despite that fact that the activities on specifying and setting-up the validation platform were still on-going at the time when this deliverable was submitted, it can be claimed with a great deal of confidence that the final architecture of the validation platform would contain the components (with key partners providing them also indicated) shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: DRIVe validation platform: the new version, as of month 12 (M12), which shows the developments introduced beyond the version in the GA

As can be seen in Figure 2, the DRIVe validation platform is almost identical to the DRIVe production platform (see D2.5) as to be test-run at test sites: the central part of the platform is the cloud-hosted SmartPower Suite which is controlling aggregated resources (at test sites) through local energy

gateways (LEGs) which also host local agents/clients: the cloud is also interfaced to optimisation, forecasting and security components while also providing benchmarking and reporting based on key performance indicators (KPIs). The main difference between the production and testing/validation platform is in the modes of operation: while, just like the production platform, the validation platform can be used for physical testing, it can also be used for hybrid (or cyber-physical) real-time emulation. This multi-mode approach to validation allows for secure, staged deployment of the platform. The modes of validation are fully defined and further elaborated in the next section.

2.2 VALIDATION ACTIVITIES: MODES OF VALIDATION

Validation of the DRIVe solution are to be conducted at the service level, using two primary modes of validation:

- non-physical testing, which can take the form of:
 - offline simulation,
 - real-time emulation (software-in-the-loop), and
 - hybrid (or cyber-physical) real-time emulation, where controllers are real (physical), but are interfaced to a real-time emulated grid (hardware-in-the-loop); as well as
- physical testing, which assumes grid-tied tests of various assets at test sites.

This combination of non-physical and physical testing allows the consortium to use the validation platform for verification and optimization of DRIVe services and algorithms in the non-physical domain, in order to use thoroughly tested solutions for the physical tests. This staged approach is also reflected in the validation timeline so as to make sure that physical testing will be conducted as smoothly and error-free as possible, but it can also be used to address potential concerns of the owners and/or stakeholders in test sites: the stability, reliability and potential benefits of the solution can be shown without deploying the solution to the physical test sites.

2.2.1 Modes of validation: physical testing

Figure 3 shows the general architecture and layers to be used in physical testing. As can be seen, the validation platform for DRIVe is actually the DRIVe platform itself: local energy gateways aggregate physical devices and are controlled by DRIVe logic via the DRIVe execution platform. The DRIVe logic (as shown in Figure 2) is providing validation reporting based on key performance indicators. Additionally, the local energy gateways and the DRIVe platform are fed with real-time data and forecast from both social and economic actors.

Physical testing, as shown here, is the natural final stage of testing and validation activities. The reason why it should be the final stage stems from its very nature of being “physical”, as it assumes remote cloud-based control of aggregated grid-tied devices which can have the planned, beneficial effects of shifting loads and providing ancillary services to market parties, but, in the worst case scenario, might cause unplanned, undesirable effects to the grid, including even an emergency blackout. Exactly for this reason, the DRIVe validation platform was devised to provide an additional validation mode which will allow the consortium to thoroughly test, verify and optimize the DRIVe logic before advanced services are deployed to physical assets: non-physical testing in the form of offline simulation, real-time emulation, and, in particular, hybrid (or cyber-physical) real-time emulation.

Figure 3: DRiVE validation platform modes of testing: physical testing

2.2.2 Modes of validation: non-physical testing

Of the three subtypes of non-physical testing mentioned at the end of the previous section, one is commonly used in process simulation throughout various industries for technical systems as diverse as chemical plants, production plants, and power stations: offline simulation. The term offline simulation, as used here, refers to having a model of the relevant buildings and demand response assets which are virtually simulated and not connected to sensors, DRiVE logic and other devices, whereby the evolution of simulated time does not match the evolution of the actual time.

Within the scope of the DRiVE project, offline simulation will only be used to assess the behind-meter time-of-use and kW-max optimization behind the meter, based on the building models and historical data from the Blaenau Gwen test site. This offline simulation will be conducted inside Cardiff University's REEFS platform and will not involve DRiVE logic, because both optimizations are done behind the meter and without direct control from DRiVE logic.

Unlike offline simulation, real-time emulation and real-time hybrid cyber-physical emulation (hardware in the loop) are not traditionally associated with demand response testing and validation. Real-time emulation is similar to the offline simulation mentioned above but assumes that the evolution of simulated time does match the evolution of the actual time and the models being simulated are fed with real or historical data from sensors and DRiVE logic. Within the scope of the DRiVE project real-time emulation can be used to test, verify and optimize early versions of DRiVE logic using virtualized components, but is not envisaged as being central neither in terms of verification nor validation of the DRiVE solution because it does not provide direct insight into real behaviour of control algorithms due to the fact that the system is tested without hardware devices: the system is virtualized, but works in a real-time mode. This validation mode is primarily a by-product of the decision to use FPGA-powered real-time emulators for hybrid cyber-physical testing.

It is hybrid cyber-physical testing which is assumed to provide the biggest benefits to testing and validating the overall DRiVE solution before its deployment to test sites, and which may be said to represent the main innovation of the DRiVE project in terms of verifying, validating, optimizing and demonstrating next-generation, multi-agent demand response systems.

As its name implies, hybrid cyber-physical testing combines physical testing with real-time emulation and provides direct insight into the behaviour of the system. It does so by combining the actual DRiVE logic and communication layer, together with the actual local energy gateways, but interfaced to high-fidelity real-time models of grid-tied devices which are emulated in Typhoon HIL's FPGA-powered devices. In short, all the logic layers and top-level communication layers of the DRiVE solution are real (i.e. not models), but they control high-fidelity models of local devices behind each gateway. In such a configuration, the consortium can assess, verify and validate DRiVE logic without dangers inherently present in physical testing which involves real power, real devices and real interactions with the grid. This mode of validation is shown in Figure 4.

The hybrid cyber-physical mode of testing is further designed to facilitate two separate modes of emulation: with historical data and with real-time data. When hybrid cyber-physical validation is executed on the basis of pre-collected historical data, it is possible to assess the impact of the DRiVE logic and algorithms and assess the benefits of demand response (and ancillary) services – as opposed to having no such services. Additionally, historical data can be modified to create worst-case, emergency scenarios, which can be used to validate the proper operation of the DRiVE platform even in situations which are safety critical, but rarely occur in real life. On the other hand, when hybrid cyber-physical validation is executed on the basis of real-time data, the validation platform can be used as the final step prior to physical testing, where the consortium partners can troubleshoot interoperability and prepare the DRiVE platform for deployment to real assets and devices at test sites. For example, Modbus register maps can be prepared and verified in the validation environment and then deployed to real assets without costly and time-consuming on-site work.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that the validation platform, when run in this mode, will provide data collection and reporting from emulated devices to the DRiVE cloud, via REST API. This means that the same reporting and benchmarking functions from the DRiVE cloud logic which is used for physical testing can also be used for hybrid cyber-physical testing, which simplifies the time for developing reporting functions based on key performance indicators. Naturally, this reporting functionality, if both physical and hybrid cyber-physical testing are executed simultaneously, can also be used to fine-tune emulation properties and prove the fidelity, reliability and accuracy of emulation.

Figure 4: DRIVe validation platform modes of testing: hybrid cyber-physical testing

2.2.3 Modes of validation for each DR service and each test site

In line with the general overview of validation modes specified in the project proposal, and in the preceding sections, the consortium has, through a series of WP7 meetings, determined that the most optimal and insightful distribution of various validation modes is the one presented in the table below.

The abbreviations used in the table mean the following:

- to be implemented,
 - to be potentially implemented,
- OFF = offline simulation,
EM = real-time emulation,
HYB = hybrid, cyber-physical emulation, and
PHY = physical tests.

The label “potentially” mentioned in the table should be interpreted in line with the purpose of this document, as specified in the Introduction: the document provides the ideal validation scenarios, which may have to be modified depending on technical, practical, ethical and organizational challenges encountered in the process of setting up the test, validation and demonstration environment.

Table 1: Services tested at each test site and their simulation mode (based on outcomes from D2.3), where ● means that the scenario will definitively be implemented and ○ means that the

scenario will potentially be implemented, depending on potential issues, or lack thereof, in setting up the DRiVE platform and integrating its components

MODES OF VALIDATION ACTIVITIES PER SERVICE AND TEST SITE		Blaenau Gwent District (PS1)	DEVO Residential District (PS2)	ADO Stadium (PS3)	Giessenwind (PS4)	Woerden site (Site X) (PS5)	COMSA head office (PS6)
<i>In-building services for the Prosumer</i>	ToU optimisation (UC01)	● OFF					● PHY
	kWmax Control (UC02)	● OFF		● PHY		○ EM/HYB	● PHY
	Consumer portal (UC03)		● PHY	● PHY	● PHY	● PHY	● PHY
<i>Community services</i>	Community optimisation (UC04)		● PHY			● HYB/PHY	
<i>Flexibility services for the BRP</i>	Portfolio management (UC05)		○ HYB ● PHY	● PHY	● EM/HYB	● PHY/EM to be decided	
<i>Flexibility services for the DSO</i>	Congestion management (UC06)		○ HYB ○ PHY	● PHY	○ EM/HYB	● HYB ● PHY	
	Voltage control (UC07)				● EM/HYB/PHY	optional	○ EM/HYB
	Power quality support (UC08)				● EM/HYB/PHY	optional	○ EM/HYB
<i>Flexibility services for the TSO</i>	Frequency Containment Reserve (UC9)			● PHY	○ EM/HYB/PHY	depends on the availability of the battery	○ EM/HYB
	Frequency Restoration Reserve (UC10)		○ HYB/PHY	● PHY	○ EM/HYB/PHY	depends on the availability of the battery	○ EM/HYB

2.3 VALIDATION ACTIVITIES: DATA COLLECTION

For all non-physical tests, it is necessary to have relevant baseline data for the relevant test sites of the DRiVE project where non-physical testing is to be conducted. Explicitly, insightful, relevant and rich datasets represent one of the key requirements for conducting offline and real-time simulation, as well as a baseline for measuring/benchmarking the performance and benefits of the fully-developed DRiVE platform. Therefore, this task, Grid Data Collection, can be considered as a being vital for non-physical demonstration and validation activities of the DRiVE solution.

This report builds upon the initial assessment of data capabilities for all test sites, where a matrix of data capabilities was created for all sites. The matrix of data capabilities in that sense, represented a valuable orientation point for development of KPIs for various use cases, providing a broad frame of reference on what can realistically be obtained data-wise from a test site, and what is beyond the current capabilities of each test site.

The matrix of data capabilities of each site is provided in Annex A.

The importance of data matrix for the test sites stems from the fact that real data represents the only common denominator for all non-physical testing scenarios, no matter if different configurations and

services of the DRiVE platform are assessed technology-wise, performance-wise or both. The reason for this is that each test site will be subject to different types of testing, demonstration and validation activities focusing on different aspects of the DRiVE solution (e.g. fast demand response, LEC management, etc.), but all of which will be using one or several methodologies which are data-dependent: a) simulation-based tests (offline tests on a modelled grid, fed by real data); b) emulation-based test (real-time tests on an emulated grid, fed by real data), and c) hybrid physical/emulation-based test (tests on a partly emulated grid, with some real devices, fed by real data). Therefore, real data collected from the grid is the primary requirement for initial stages of testing/validation/demonstration methodologies specified in the project proposal, i.e. the development of the DRiVE solution.

Moreover, real datasets are the key enabling feature for using the Typhoon test-bench to assess DRiVE tools' impact on the distribution grid in the safety of real-time simulated power, before the actual physical tests can commence. In this way, the datasets represent the main link between a very elaborate simulation framework and a highly performant execution framework. Furthermore, data sharing between the simulated and the real test framework will enable performance improvement of both simulated tests and the actual performance of the DRiVE system in a grid-tied mode of operation.

What this means is that data collection activities envisaged in T7.1 fundamentally represent merely the initial stage of data collection, where kinds of data and types of data collection processes are identified and implemented. Data collection continues throughout the WP7 as new components of the DRiVE solution (and new versions of those components) are tested and demonstrated. Thus, these continuously increased datasets serve a dual purpose: on the one hand, they demonstrate to energy market and grid stakeholders that the DRiVE solution can be safely implemented in real contexts and with real benefits, and, on the other hand, they constantly feeding the research and development activities with the data that enables optimization and further development of the DRiVE components.

In the most succinct form, the continuous process of data collection is the foundation for reporting validation results of the DRiVE solution and for presenting tangible impact of the DRiVE solution in real-life applications.

Data collection activities, at the time when this deliverable was being finalized, were still ongoing. The current (at the time of submission) version of the data capabilities matrix for all test sites can be found in the appendix of this document. The data being collected is to be stored in Enervalis' cloud as a database which can be queried using REST API by the consortium and the validation platform. The data is GDPR compliant in the sense that no piece of data can be considered personal data, nor can it be used to identify a person.

2.4 VALIDATION ACTIVITIES: PRE-EXISTING KPIS FOR DR

In order to define Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for DRiVE as an enabling solution for Demand Response (DR), it is essential to be aware of KPIs which have already been used to assess DR programs and systems, as well as to define what DR is and how it is implemented. This section and its sub-sections therefore provide definitions of DR in the context of validation activities, types of DR and, finally, distinct kinds of KPIs for assessing its performance. As it will be clear upon reading this section, most of the existing KPIs are not suitable for pilot projects as they are focused on the entire grid, nation-wide utility network or similar large-scale concepts, but do not focus on particular services, nor are necessarily compatible with multi-agent cloud-coordinated infrastructure, which was why use cases in the main chapter of this document contain specific KPIs devised for DRiVE, which can be universally applied for service-level validation within DR programs.

2.4.1 The purpose of DR

Generally speaking, in order to define KPIs it is first necessary to define what is being assessed performance-wise – which, in this case, is DR. In the context of use cases and validation activities, the purpose of a DR program is understood to be the reduction of electricity demand during the peak load time periods and the increase of demand during off-peak time periods, where time periods are usually termed *event periods* and are typically measured in hours (but can be also shorter periods, e.g. 15 minutes, or even seconds in case of fast DR and DR assets being used for ancillary services) [2]. Ultimately, a DR program, therefore, ensures that the electricity demand and supply match.

2.4.1.1 Types of DR

Traditionally (based on [2] and [3]), DR programs can be classified as belonging to one of the two main types, based on what criteria are used to control the behaviour of a DR system:

- 1) Incentive (or controllable) DR, and
- 2) Price-responsive DR.

Incentive-based DR programs (or controllable DR systems) imply that end users modify their demand patterns in accordance with particular, clearly specified incentives, or in accordance with an agreement with a Load Serving Entity (LSO). Typical examples of Incentive-based DR systems are Direct Load Control (DLC) DR programs and Indirect Load Control (ILC) DR programs.

Price-responsive DR programs imply that the end users are subject to dynamic electricity pricing. Depending on the criterion/criteria used to determine the dynamics of the price, Price-responsive DR programs are typically realized as a) Price-to-Retailer (PTR), b) Real-time Pricing (RTP), c) Critical Peak Pricing (CPP), d) Time-of-Use (TOU) and e) Critical Peak Rebate (CPR) DR programs.

2.4.2 General info on KPIs for DR

Despite the fact that there is a considerable variation in how various DR programs work, their purpose is the same - to modify patterns of electricity consumption – which means that high-level KPIs for DR programs are fundamentally similar, highly overlapping or the same: the most basic KPI for any DR program is the change in energy consumption during event periods, while a more advanced KPI would be the amount of correlation between the demand and the energy production costs [3]. In short, these can be termed *consumption efficiency KPIs* and *energy shift DR KPIs*. Naturally, these general KPIs have to be adapted to individual DR programs and each represents a set comprising several individual KPIs, which is the content of subsequent sections. Authors in [3] have also identified a primitive KPI for assessing the prediction.

In sum, the pre-existing KPIs for DR which can be found in relevant sources include:

- a) consumption efficiency,
- b) energy shift (or DR-induced demand variation and reshaping),
- c) prediction accuracy,
- d) economic-related KPIs, and
- e) technical KPIs.

2.4.2.1 Consumption efficiency KPIs

In general, consumption efficiency KPIs depend on the existence of smart meter data, or some other datasets which allow the measurement of the efficiency in energy consumption and energy savings. The typical KPIs, which can be used for both utilities and end users are given in the table below and are based on the outcomes of the project S3C (Smart Consumer, Smart Customer, Smart Citizen) [4]. It is worth noting that the S3C consortium makes a distinction among three types of end users – households, SME and industry – where the implication is that not KPIs are equally applicable to all end users.

Table 2: KPIs for measuring the energy efficiency of DR programs/systems

KPI	TARGET OF THE KPI	DEFINITION
Absolute energy savings [kWh]	Households, SME	The difference between measured data and reference/forecast data
Relative energy savings (expressed in share of the total consumption)	Utility	The difference between measured data and reference/forecast data divided by total .
Consumption per entity - household	Utility	The averaged total consumption per household
Consumption per entity size (number of inhabitants, size of flat)	Utility, households, SME	Individual total consumption divided by entity parameter .
Consumption per product	SME, industry	The individual total divided by production result .
Cost savings	Household, SME	The difference between the measured data and reference data multiplied by price .
Consumption per employee	SME, industry	The individual total divided by presence of employees .
Operating hours (Energy consumed divided by peak consumption)	SME, industry	The individual total divided by individual peak consumption .

In addition to KPIs listed in Table 2, [3] lists three additional KPIs for assessing consumption efficiency of DR programs and systems, although the source does not identify the targets for these KPIs (utilities, end users, etc.). The KPIs are taken as direct citations from [3] and are:

- **Change in the total electricity consumption per day.** The original consumption is measured before starting the DR program and the new consumption is measured after the program inception, according to this formula:

$$\frac{\text{original consumption} - \text{new consumption}}{\text{original consumption}}$$

- **Change in the total electricity consumption during peak hours**, measured according to this formula:

$$\frac{\text{original peak consumption} - \text{new peak consumption}}{\text{original peak consumption}}$$

- **Change in the total electricity consumption during the off-peak hours**, measured according to this formula:

$$\frac{\text{original off-peak consumption} - \text{new off-peak consumption}}{\text{original off-peak consumption}}$$

2.4.2.2 Energy shift KPIs

In general, energy shifts are the main goal of all DR programs, as energy shifts represent the evidence of a DR system’s ability to perform optimization of demand. Energy shift KPIs therefore require data on peak consumption but not necessarily the amount of flexible energy [4]. The recommendation given in [4] is that both peak consumption and flexible energy be expressed in a dimensionless form. In that sense, the KPI for performance is a dimensionless form of peak consumption to average consumption power ratio, which enables observing the main measured effect – peak reduction [4]. On the other hand, the KPI for flexibility is the ratio of the flexible energy and the average daily consumption, expressed in a dimensionless form, which is not an optimal solution as it does not take into consideration the flexibility time, which is very important for the service provider. [4].

The typical energy shift KPIs, which can be used for both utilities and end users are given in the table below and are based on the outcomes of the project S3C [4].

Table 3: KPIs for measuring the energy shift efficiency of DR programs/systems

KPI	TARGET OF THE KPI	DEFINITION
Peak to average ratio	Utility, SME	The peak power consumption divided by average power .
Energy shift ratio	Households, SME, Utility	Shifted energy divided by total daily consumption .
Consumption per tariff	Household, utility	Amount during the tariff divided by total consumption .
Peak reduction capacity	Utility	Peak load capacity divided by total daily consumption .
Demand response reliability	Utility	The amount of requested energy shift divided by

		the amount of realized energy shift.
--	--	--------------------------------------

2.4.2.3 Demand reduction KPIs for DR systems with Load Serving Entities (LSEs) and third-party aggregators

Authors in [3] also identify two additional KPIs for demand variation when DR programs include third-party energy aggregators or load serving entities (LSEs), and when load shedding is the focus of DR events: a) uncertainty of demand shed (with 3 sub-KPIs: variance, entropy and risk) and b) delay responsiveness of demand shed (with 3 sub-KPIs: variance, entropy and risk). These KPIs can be used to assess if the customers are provided with the right kind of incentives and if these incentives provide the right amount of demand reduction [3].

Uncertainty of demand shed, according to [2] and [3], is calculated from a time series, such as $\{x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n\}$, where each item in a time series represents the difference between the baseline demand (i.e. calculated/estimated demand) and the actual demand. Such a time series can then be used to measure the uncertainty of demand reduction by means of three separate KPIs which are given below as direct citations from [3]:

- Variance of demand reduction, calculated as $Var(x)$. This KPI is interpreted positively if the variance is low, which means that the uncertainty is low. On the other hand, the higher the variance is, the higher also the uncertainty is.
- Entropy can be used as a KPI, because higher entropy implies higher uncertainty in demand reduction. Entropy is calculated by discretizing x from the original time series into k bins with thresholds $\{b_0, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k\}$. The entropy can be calculated as $H(x) = -\sum_{i=1}^k p_k \log(p_k)$, where $p_k = \Pr(x_i \in [b_{k-1}, b_k])$.
- Risk is a KPI which calculates the uncertainty associated with the demand reductions of a customer. Risk is calculated as a probability that the customers reduction is at least b_k (as defined in b), entropy). The formula for risk, r_k is $r_k = \Pr(x \geq b_k)$. Of course, the lower probability should be interpreted as higher risk.

Delay responsiveness of demand shed, just like uncertainty of demand shed, is calculated from a time series, such as $\{D_1, D_2, D_3, \dots, D_n\}$, where each item in a time series represents the time required by a customer to shed their demand (during the previous n DR events). Fundamentally, delay responsiveness indicates how fast demand reductions can be dispatched by each customer or DR asset. As was the case with uncertainty of demand shed, delay responsiveness of demand shed can be measured by means of three separate KPIs which are given on the basis of [2] and [3]:

- Variance of delay responsiveness, calculated as $Var(D)$. This KPI is interpreted positively if the variance is low, which means that the delay is low. On the other hand, the higher the variance is, the higher also the delay is.
- Entropy can be used as a KPI, because higher entropy implies higher delay in demand shed. Entropy is calculated by discretizing D from the original time series into k bins with thresholds $\{b_0, b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k\}$. The entropy can be calculated as $H(D) = -\sum_{i=1}^k p_k \log(p_k)$, where $p_k = \Pr(x_i \in [D_{k-1}, D_k])$.
- Risk is a KPI which calculates the uncertainty associated with the delay in demand shedding by a customer. Risk is calculated as a probability that the customers reduction is at least as fast as the time interval b_k (as defined in b), entropy). The formula for risk,

r_k is $r_k = \Pr(D \geq b_k)$. Of course, the lower probability should be interpreted as higher delays in demand shedding.

2.4.2.4 Prediction accuracy KPI

This section provides a basic prediction KPI after outlining the difference between prediction and forecasting as two similar, related, but non-identical concepts.

2.4.2.4.1 Prediction and forecast: definition of terms

Before presenting the prediction accuracy KPIs, it is crucial to make a distinction between seemingly synonymous terms which are used in this chapter: “prediction” and “forecast”. Prediction, at least in the scope of this document, is understood to refer to the use of explanatory variables for the purpose of characterizing the expected outcome or expected response. In contrast, forecasting is understood to refer to trends in observation that characterize the expected outcome or expected response. In summary, forecasting takes an observed response to characterize a timely expectation while prediction uses explanatory variables or predictors to characterize expectation: prediction is the general term which is independent of time, while forecasting is a subtype of prediction with time as a dependent variable.

2.4.2.4.2 Prediction KPIs

The available literature identifies only the “the most primitive” and basic KPI for prediction in DR programs: the variance (σ_Δ) of the difference (Δ_{PA}) between the predicted consumption (p_p) and the actual consumption (p_t), where t_i is the initial time of the measurement period (in seconds) and t_f is the final times of the measurement period (in seconds) [3]:

$$\sigma_\Delta = \frac{1}{(t_f - t_i)} \sqrt{\int (\Delta_{PA}(t) - \overline{\Delta_{PA}})^2 dt}$$

According to this KPI, the smaller the variance is, the better the prediction is, and vice versa: the bigger the variance, the worse the prediction. The most logical way of using this KPI is to measure this variance in two different scenarios: without DR feedback to customers, and with DR feedback to customers [3].

2.4.2.5 Forecast accuracy KPI

The forecast (as defined and differentiated from prediction in the previous subsection) is assessed by means of forecast accuracy KPIs which are defined separately for each type of forecast, in particular load/demand forecast, and renewable generation forecast. Therefore, the specific forecast KPIs can be referred later in each validation scenario, as needed.

2.4.2.5.1 Load/Demand Forecast KPIs

The load/demand forecast KPIs defined below are universally applicable. However, specifically within the DRivE project, they apply to the COMSA HQ building test site in Spain, BGCBC test site in the UK, as well as to the Woerden and DEVO test sites in the Netherlands.

- **Mean Average Percentage Error (MAPE):** $MAPE = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \left| \frac{A_t - F_t}{A_t} \right|$ where A_t is the actual consumption and F_t is the forecast consumption at time t and T is the total data points. The value range is between 0 and 1 and the higher the better.

- **Root mean square error (RMSE):** $RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{t=1}^T (A_t - F_t)^2}{T}}$ where A_t is the actual value and F_t is the forecast value at time t and T is the total data points. The value is in kwh (consumption).
- **The coefficient of determination (R^2):** $R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T (A_t - F_t)^2}{\sum_{t=1}^T (A_t - \bar{A})^2}$ where A_t is the actual value and F_t is the forecast value at time t and T is the total data points, and \bar{A} is the mean of the actual values $A_t, t = 1, 2, \dots, T$. The value range is between 0 and 1 and the lower the better.

In addition to the KPIs mentioned above, there is also a KPI which is used in the building sector for absolute variables: the coefficient of variation of the mean square error. It provides a measure of variability that is independent from the measurement unit.

2.4.2.5.2 Renewable Generation Forecast KPIs

Due to its distinct characteristics compared with loads, the KPIs should be defined separately. Within the DRivE project, these KPIs generally apply to the Giessen wind and DEVO/Pilot Woerden (with PV) forecasting.

The KPIs for renewable energy generation MAPE, RMSE and R^2 (defined in the previous subsections), as well as the NRMSE, as defined below.

- **Normalised Root mean square error (NRMSE):** $NRMSE = \frac{RMSE}{A_{max} - A_{min}}$ where RMSE is the root mean square error and A_{max} is the maximum value and A_{min} is the minimum value. This gives a comparative metrics for forecast errors by normalising the RMSE against the range of values (which are something similar to the rated capacity of wind farm or PV).

2.4.2.6 Economic-related KPIs

According to various sources referenced, quoted and summarized in [3], the economic-related KPIs are generally based on price elasticity, participation rate and (dis)comfort level. For the sake of transparency it is worth noting here that [2] and [3] identify three main types of price elasticity – self-elasticity, cross-elasticity and substitution elasticity – which measure demand reduction due to a specific price in a specific time interval, effect of reduced electricity usage on the price and purchase of other goods and services, and the rate at which customers substitute off-peak consumption for peak usage as a consequence of the changing ratio of off-peak and peak prices, respectively. As the validation of the DRivE platform is primarily technical in scope, most KPIs devised in this document are not economic in nature, which is further caused by the fact that price models for DR services and ancillary services differ among EU member states to a great extent. The following economic related KPIs are, therefore, listed primarily for the sake of fully referential transparency.

The most general KPI for DR is the net economic benefit of implementing a DR program, which can be calculated a simple fraction of the profit after the DR program has been implemented and the profit before the DR program had not been implemented, as shown in the formula below [3]. As the formula implies, the DR program can only be considered a success if *NetEconomicBenefit* is more than one but should preferably be closer to two (or more).

$$NetEconomicBenefit = \frac{profit_{after}}{profit_{before}}$$

In addition to *NetEconomicBenefit*, there are also additional KPIs which can be used to assess other, less general economic aspects of DR programs, most of which focus on the customer. One such KPI is the demand price elasticity [3], which is also called self-elasticity [2], and which is calculated as a fraction shown in the formula below, where δ_e is the change in energy demand and δ_p is the change in price.

$$DemandPriceElasticity = \frac{\delta_e}{\delta_p}$$

In addition to the two economic KPIs listed above, there are also other customer-centric KPIs, such as customer responsiveness, absolute (or relative) load impact, absolute discomfort impact and discomfort level against total energy consumption [3]. Customer responsiveness is a KPI which is usually based on the ratio between the total number of DR signals sent to the customer and the activation signals sent back by the customer. As such, customer responsiveness is not a good fit for automated, cloud-based DR programs where human activation and/or operation of DR assets is neither necessary nor expected. Similarly, the absolute (or relative) load impact is a KPI which is applicable only if there is a customer interaction with DR signals and if the customer operated the DR assets. Namely, the absolute (or relative) load impact is a KPI which measures the number of kW of which had been curtailed. The two discomfort KPIs – the absolute discomfort level and the discomfort level against total energy consumption – assess to what extent the customer's comfort changes in DR programs, but from slightly different perspectives. The absolute discomfort level, as a KPI, can be measured in many different ways depending on how comfort is defined in a specific instance (e.g. an increase in room temperature in the summer when the air-conditioner is turned off, or a decrease in room temperature in the winter when the heating is temporarily turned off).

Finally, in the domain of customer-centred KPIs, there are also those which, instead of focusing on comfort, focus on discomfort [2]. The most commonly used such KPI (as per [2] and [3]) is the total energy reduction against discomfort level constraints, which is about achieving maximum reduction without exceeding a specific discomfort threshold. As the comfort-level KPI, this KPI can be formulated in many ways, depending on the type and other features (e.g. season) of the DR service and/or DR event request.

2.4.2.7 Technical KPIs

In contrast with KPIs for consumption efficiency, energy shifts, demand variation, demand, reduction, prediction accuracy and economic KPIs, which may be collectively termed “functional” KPIs, there is also a separate group of KPIs which may be termed “technical”. In this sense, functional KPIs are those which assess how well the unit or a system functions, i.e. how well it performs the function for which it was designed. On the other hand, technical KPIs assess the technical prerequisites for performing the function, i.e. they assess the technical basis necessary for the function to be performed. For example, successful activation of the frequency containment reserve assets would be a functional KPI, whereas the proper exchange of signal between the assets and the aggregator would be a technical KPI (measured e.g. as the number of dropped packets). Technical KPIs are commonly platform dependant and, as their name suggests, ‘technical’ i.e. they focus on technical aspects of the unit or a system, not on its functional aspects.

2.4.3 KPIs for the DRIVe platform

As the goal of validation activities within the DRIVe project is to develop a next-generation DR platform that will enable 20% of load in residential and tertiary buildings for use in DR and ancillary services, resulting in up to 30% cost-saving (price-based DR) and also maximizing revenue for prosumers, and to achieve it through a multi-agent, cloud-based system that can coordinate a theoretically unlimited number of devices aggregated through local energy gateways, it is clear that the general KPIs presented in the previous sections, except for prediction and forecast KPIs, do not represent the best fit for the project, as they are devised from the point of view of large utilities and/or energy traders. It is for this reason, that KPIs for the DRIVe platform were designed specifically for each service and each use case and why they represent a combination of both functional and technical KPIs, which serve the dual purpose of validation both the operation and function of the DRIVe platform.

3 VALIDATION SCENARIOS

This chapter provides detailed descriptions of validation scenarios for each use case and, where a particular service is to be tested and validated at various test sites, specific validation scenarios for each test site. The chapter is primarily organized according to groups of use cases, as elaborated in the bulleted list below.

The chapter is typically divided in the following subsections:

- validation scenarios for **in-building services for the prosumer**
 - validation scenarios for ToU optimisation
 - validation scenarios for kWmax control
 - validation scenarios for the Consumer Portal
- validation scenarios for **community services** (one service: community optimisation based on NRGcoin)
- validation scenarios for **flexibility services for the BRP** (one service: portfolio management)
- validation scenarios for **flexibility services for the DSO**
 - validation scenarios for congestion management
 - validation scenarios for voltage control
 - validation scenarios for power quality support
- validation scenarios for **flexibility services for the TSO**
 - validation scenarios for frequency containment reserve
 - validation scenarios for frequency restoration reserve

It should be noted that cybersecurity provisions in the validation plan are not addressed as a separate use case (or use cases). Instead, the cybersecurity provisions are addressed separately in a subsection (3.6) at the end of this chapter.

Each main section is organized in accordance with the simplified, streamlined IEC 62559 standard for use case methodology.

The unified lists of use case actors and use case requirements are provided in the appendices, i.e. annexes.

3.1 IN-BUILDING SERVICES FOR THE PROSUMER: VALIDATION SCENARIOS

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for the following services: ToU optimisation, kWmax control, and the Consumer Portal. These scenarios are to be tested in two modes: offline simulation and physical testing. Offline simulation will be conducted on the basis of data collected from the Blaenau Gwent test site and will be conducted by means of Cardiff University's REEFS (Real-time Energy and Environmental Forecasting and Simulation) platform, while physical tests will be conducted at the DEVO Residential District, the ADO Stadium, and in COMSA's head office. As explained in a relevant subsection of the updated D2.3 report, the consortium decided to add an additional test site – the Woerden – in order to compensate for the lack of controllable assets at the DEVO site. At the time when this deliverable was being finalized, the definitive status of the site and the possible scenarios to be implemented there (pending the owner's approval) were not fully known

and were subject to further discussions and negotiations. In the context of in-building services, the Woerden site, at the time of finalizing this deliverable, was planned to be potentially used for kWmax (emulation and/or hybrid cyber-physical testing) and Consumer Portal (physical testing) use cases. Any information regarding these use cases as to be implemented at the Woerden site that is potentially missing from this report will be added in the subsequent reports on the validation platform and validation activities themselves.

3.1.1 ToU optimisation: validation scenarios

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for ToU optimisation in general, while relevant subsections at its end briefly provide information on specifics of validation scenarios at each validation site.

3.1.1.1 General info on the scenario

The objective of the ToU optimisation Use Case (ID: ToU Optimisation) is to achieve energy cost savings through “implicit” demand response actions- deferring energy consumption over the course of a day to time periods with lower per-kWh consumption costs- while still maintaining building occupant comfort. The application of this use case is highly dependent on the conditions outlined in the site’s contract with their energy supplier.

The ToU optimisation Use Case description is provided in detail in D2.3 as it applies to the COMSA building, where the focus is managing HVAC equipment and a possible storage battery through the LEG to minimize monthly energy consumption costs without negatively impacting occupant comfort. In the context of COMSA within the DRiVE project (as mentioned in D2.3), it is to be considered in concert with the kWmax Control Use Case (3.3.2) in order to optimize the reduction of the total energy bill, due to possible cross-effects between these two use cases. In other contexts, depending on the specific energy bill that applies to a site, it may be relevant to consider only ToU optimisation. For this reason, these use cases have been presented separately.

3.1.1.1.1 Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario

This section provides the KPIs for ToU optimization, which combine economic and customer-centric KPIs measuring the savings on the energy bill and the comfort of the customers/occupants.

Table 4: KPIs for the general ToU validation scenario

<i>Key performance indicators</i>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Reference to mentioned use case objectives</i>
tou_kpi_01	Energy Bill Savings	The total energy bill savings (in euros) will be calculated using the actual billing method used at the considered sites. Therefore, the equation for this KPI is entirely dependent on the site’s contract with their energy supplier. In cases where kWmax is also considered (such as COMSA), this KPI can be summed with the kwmax_kpi_01 in order to optimise the energy bill as a whole.	Objective: Minimize energy consumption costs (D2.3 Table 3)
tou_kpi_02	Occupant Comfort	Temperature must remain within an acceptable range as defined by the building manager (also considering the occupancy schedule). This can be quantified by measuring the % of time that the temperature is outside of the acceptable range, with 0% representing optimum performance. $\% \text{ Time Outside Range} = \frac{(Hou + Huu)}{8760h}$	Objective: Maintain indoor comfort (D2.3 Table 3)

	<p>where H_{ou} is the total number of hours during the time the building is occupied annually where temperature inside the building is outside the threshold set by the building manager, and H_{uu} is the total number of hours during the unoccupied period where temperature inside the building is outside the building manager threshold. Temperature can represent the real temperature or a “heat index” temperature (temperature adjusted to account for relative humidity), depending on the definition agreed by the building manager.</p>	
--	--	--

3.1.1.2 Diagrams of the validation scenario

This section contains the diagram of the ToU use case, as well as a sequence diagram of the general kWmax optimisation use case, which are partially taken from D2.3.

Figure 5: Diagram of the ToU use case as shown in D2.3 Section 3.1.2

Figure 6: Sequence Diagram of the General kWmax Optimisation Use Case

3.1.1.3 Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario

The step by step description of the ToU optimisation Use Case is shown in the sequence diagram above (Figure 5), with the requirements for building this connection shown in Figure 6. The sequence diagram represents the expected validation case (TOU01) and should cycle over a time period previously agreed to. This validation case, as well as possible alternative and failure states, are described in the subsections below.

It should be noted that the step-by-step process for ToU optimisation is very similar to that of the kWmax Control, although how those constraints are defined, the priorities of the optimisation and what actions should be taken can differ significantly between the two cases. For this reason, these models have been presented as two separate use cases, but it is recommended to combine the optimisation in cases where both Use Cases are relevant.

3.1.1.3.1 Overview of the scenario

Table 5 depicts the conditions regarding the primary validation case (Energy Bill Optimisation) as well as several critical alternative and failure cases.

Table 5: Scenario conditions for the general ToU validation scenario

Deliverable D7.1(PUBLIC) Validation Plan	38	Version 1.00 30 November 2018
This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement n°774431		

<i>Scenario conditions</i>						
<i>No.</i>	<i>Scenario name</i>	<i>Scenario description</i>	<i>Primary actor</i>	<i>Triggering event</i>	<i>Precondition</i>	<i>Postcondition</i>
01	TOU01	Energy Bill Optimisation	LEG	DRIVE control enabled	Historical weather data, energy data, site and asset characteristics, and tariff and operational schedules provided to MPC	Energy bill optimised for ToU. Overall energy bill optimised if combined with kWmax.
02	TOU02	Loss of communication with MPC	LEG	No connection with MPC or Forecast server	Control actions from MPC already provided to LEG	MPC control actions followed and failsafe settings implemented
03	TOU03	Occupant override of DRiVE solution	User	User overrides control of one or more controllable assets locally	Control actions from MPC already provided to LEG	MPC control actions revised to consider occupant override

3.1.1.3.2 Steps of the scenario

The following steps represent the possible validation scenarios of the ToU optimisation use case. Specific sequence diagrams are referenced in order to better describe the considered situation. The term Site Manager refers to anyone responsible for managing the site- for a tertiary building this could be a building manager while for a residential home; this could be simply a resident.

This Use Case assumes critical information is already provided regarding the site characteristics, assets, and optimisation constraints (req_tec_bmpc_5, req_tec_bmpc_6, req_tec_bmpc_7), historical weather data (req_tec_forecast_5) and historical energy demand (req_tec_forecast_4). It also assumes connection with the DRiVE platform is active, live access to local weather data is in place at the site, and that the MPC and Forecasting Service has sufficient processing power to perform the analysis (req_tec_forecast_1, req_tec_forecast_2). Lengths of optimisation cycles, measurement cycles and number of cycles of acceptable downtime are also previously determined (a cycle is one full iteration of the general ToU optimisation validation scenario TOU01).

With this information, an initial model of the building is created and the forecasting models are tuned to advise the building on appropriate actions. Table 6 describes the general ToU optimisation validation scenario while the subsequent tables and figures describe variations from those scenarios.

Table 6: Step-by-step description of the general ToU optimisation validation scenario TOU01.

<i>TOU1</i>			
<i>Scenario name</i>		<i>Energy Bill Optimisation</i>	
<i>No.</i>	<i>Event</i>	<i>Name of process/activity</i>	<i>Description of process/activity</i>
01	Beginning of optimisation cycle	Send building state to MPC	LEG updates information regarding the state of building assets and relevant comfort data to the Cloud Platform and the MPC module
			Requirement ID:
02	Beginning of optimisation cycle	Send weather data to LEG	Weather data is gathered from the local station and sent to the LEG
			Requirement ID:

03	Weather data received by LEG	Send weather and electricity data to Forecast module	LEG updates weather data, current electricity consumption data and energy production data in the Cloud Platform and the Forecasting module	
			Requirement ID:	
04	Weather data received by Forecast module	Forecast weather, electricity consumption and energy production	Weather, electricity consumption and local energy production are forecast for a predetermined period of time based on the weather conditions (historical and current), electricity consumption, and historical energy production.	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_forecast_3 req_tec_forecast_4 req_tec_forecast_5 req_tec_forecast_6
05	Weather, electricity consumption and energy production is forecast	Send forecast to MPC module	Forecast of weather, electricity consumption and energy production is sent as an input to the MPC module.	
			Requirement ID:	
06	Forecasts received by MPC module	Optimise electricity use	Considering the constraints provided, the forecasts received, and thermal inertia in the building, identify specific control actions for the predetermined number of cycles that would enable the building to achieve the lowest energy bill from power demand.	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_bmpc_1 req_tec_bmpc_2 req_tec_bmpc_3 req_tec_bmpc_4 req_tec_bmpc_5 req_tec_bmpc_6 req_tec_bmpc_7 req_ps_comsa_4
07	Optimized control actions identified	Send control actions to LEG	Optimized control actions are sent to the LEG via the Enervalis Cloud platform	
			Requirement ID:	
08	Control actions received by LEG	LEG implements control actions	LEG sends control actions through the local building systems and implements them at the site, verifying that the actions have been completed	
			Requirement ID:	req_ps_comsa_1
09	Sufficient delay from the implementation of control actions	Send building state to MPC	LEG updates information regarding the state of building assets and relevant comfort data to the Cloud Platform and the MPC module	
			Requirement ID:	
10	Building state received by MPC	Validate control actions	MPC validates that the building state is in line with those performed by the control actions and the electricity consumption and production is in line with predicted values. If there is a deviation, go to step 06	
			Requirement ID:	
11	Control actions validated	End of cycle	Assuming no change of state, no new action is performed until the predetermined cycle is complete. Once this is completed, go to step 01	
			Requirement ID:	

The sequence diagram in Figure 7 presents this in detail.

Figure 7: kWmax VC 02: Loss of communication with MPC

Table 7: Step-by-step description of the failure scenario Loss of communication with MPC (TOU02).

TOU2			
Scenario name		Loss of communication with MPC	
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity
01	No control action received after sending building state	LEG alerts loss of connection	LEG alerts site manager and attempts to alert the MPC, Forecast and Cloud Platform that it has lost connection to the MPC platform. Requirement ID:
02	No control action received after sending building state	Local MPC module calculates next control action	If the LEG has a forecast for the current cycle stored, local MPC module calculates the control action for the next cycle and implements the action locally and goes to step 04. If there is no forecast for the current cycle stored, go to step 3. Requirement ID:
03	No forecast for current cycle stored in LEG	Revert to failsafe settings until connection is re-established	LEG reverts to the predetermined failsafe settings, allowing only local control until connection with the MPC platform is re-established. Requirement ID:
04	Control actions validated	End of cycle	Assuming no connection is re-established, no new action is performed until the predetermined cycle is complete. Once this is completed, go to step 01

			Requirement ID:	
--	--	--	-----------------	--

The sequence diagram in Figure 8 presents this in detail.

Figure 8: ToU02: Loss of communication with MPC

Table 8: Step-by-step description of the alternative Occupant override of DRiVE solution validation scenario TOU03.

<i>TOU3</i>				
<i>Scenario name</i>		<i>Occupant override of DRiVE solution</i>		
<i>No.</i>	<i>Event</i>	<i>Name of process/activity</i>	<i>Description of process/activity</i>	
01	Site manager overrides one or more assets locally	Send building state to MPC and Forecast	LEG updates information regarding the state of locally overridden building assets to the Cloud Platform, the MPC module and the Forecast module	
			Requirement ID:	req_ps_comsa_2
02	Building state received by MPC	Optimise electricity use	Excluding the locally overridden assets, MPC performs a normal optimisation as described in TOU01 step 06. Return to TOU01 step 07.	
			Requirement ID:	req_ps_comsa_2

3.1.1.4 ToU optimisation: validation scenarios for Blaenau Gwent District

Since the Blaenau Gwent test site will have no direct locally controllable assets (all tests will be performed virtually by means of the REEFS platform by Cardiff University), no capacity for 3rd party access to the BMS (such as through a LEG) and no real-time data on operating parameters, all tests regarding the Blaenau Gwent site will be performed in a virtual environment. Considering this,

validation case TOU01 and TOU03 can be tested at the test site virtually, using the historical data to calculate predicted savings of “flexible” loads using pre-determined constraints (req_ps_bgcbc_01, req_ps_bgcbc_02). In the case of TOU03, override actions could take the form of site-level control actions- it is not expected that there will be control actions initiated by local actors.

The ToU load schedules considered for optimisation will be provided by Blaenau Gwent, and includes three tariff periods daily as well as three “triad” peak days where additional fees for high consumption are assessed (req_ps_bgcbc_04). Since there is no specific “demand charge” on Blaenau Gwent’s bill, the maximum kW demand (kW_{max} control use case) can be considered separately as an optimisation constraint attached to the monthly energy bill (see 3.1.2.4).

3.1.1.5 ToU optimisation: validation scenarios for COMSA Head Office

In the case of the COMSA head office, the ToU optimisation and kW_{max} Control Use Cases will be combined into a single optimisation. This is because both factors are relevant when considering the overall energy bill at the COMSA site. While this does imply additional complexity in the optimisation problem, it does not necessarily result in additional validation cases. For example, if the building manager chooses to disable DRiVE implementation at the floor level through the Enervalis Cloud Portal and an individual employee overriding their local thermostat both require a process outlined in TOU03- the key difference being the scale of the corrective actions required. The step-by-step process will remain the same (signal sent from building manager to the LEG, to the Enervalis Cloud, and finally sent to the MPC as an update in the building conditions).

A local building manager will take the role of the Site Manager/Resident. The building manager will have the ability to disconnect the DRiVE solution via a physical switch (similar TOU03 if applied to all assets on the building), allowing for only local control of the assets. Additionally, the building manager will have the ability to selectively disconnect individual floors through the Consumer Portal (similar to TOU03 if applied to all assets on that floor), allowing for only local control of that floor’s assets (req_ps_comsa_3).

The contract with the energy supplier is determined by an internal process, with no possibility to include explicit demand response actions. Therefore, the ToU optimisation and kW_{max} Control should represent the energy savings that can be achieved solely under implicit demand response actions. Approval from all relevant parties regarding validation activities is being gathered and all relevant constraints and KPIs for the optimisation are being communicated to DRiVE partners. The constraints gathered so far have been described in detail in D2.3 section 3.2 kW_{max} Control.

How specifically the commands are translated from the LEG to the physical devices at the COMSA site are described in detail in D2.3 section 3.2 kW_{max} Control, D2.4 section 2.14 Building Energy Management System, D2.4 Annex C: Memory Map for COMSA BMS, and D2.5 Figure 16 Hierarchical structure of COMSA pilot. These sections should be referenced when validating the DRiVE use case at the COMSA site.

3.1.2 kW_{max} Control: validation scenarios

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for kW_{max} Control in general, while relevant subsections provide brief information on high-level specifics of validation scenarios at each validation site. The kW_{max} scenario is to be validated at the following test sites: Blaenau Gwent (offline simulation), ADO stadium (physical testing), the Woerden site (potentially, either emulation or hybrid cyber-physical testing) and at the COMSA Head Office (physical testing). Due to the definitive status of the Woerden still being not confirmed at the time of submission of this report, any specificities of the kW_{max} scenario at the Woerden site will be added in the subsequent reports on the validation platform and validation activities themselves.

3.1.2.1 General info on the scenario

The objective of the kWmax Control Use Case (ID: kWmax_control) is to achieve energy cost savings through “implicit” demand response actions- leveling power consumption of a site over the course of a day to minimize or eliminate large peaks- while still maintaining building occupant comfort. The application of this use case is highly dependent on the conditions outlined in the site’s contract with their energy supplier.

The kWmax Control Use Case description is provided in detail in D2.3 as it applies to the COMSA building, where the focus is managing HVAC equipment and a possible storage battery through the LEG to minimize energy bill costs relating to power demand without negatively impacting occupant comfort. In the context of COMSA within the DRivE project (as mentioned in D2.3), it is to be considered in concert with the ToU optimisation Use Case (3.3.1) in order to optimize the reduction of the total energy bill, due to possible cross-effects between these two use cases. In other contexts, depending on the specific energy bill that applies to a site, it may be relevant to consider only kWmax control. For this reason, these use cases have been presented separately.

3.1.2.1.1 Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario

This section provides the KPIs for kWmax control, which, just as ToU KPIs, combine economic and customer-centric KPIs measuring the savings on the energy bill and the comfort of the customers/occupants.

Table 9: KPIs for the general kWmax Control validation scenario

<i>Key performance indicators</i>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Reference to mentioned use case objectives</i>
kwmax_kpi_01	Energy Bill Savings	The total energy bill savings (in euros) will be calculated using the actual billing method used at the considered sites. Therefore, the equation for this KPI is entirely dependent on the site’s contract with their energy supplier. In cases where ToU is also considered (such as COMSA), this KPI can be summed with the tou_kpi_01 in order to optimise the energy bill as a whole.	Objective: Minimize power demand costs (D2.3 Table 3)
kwmax_kpi_02	Occupant Comfort	Temperature must remain within an acceptable range as defined by the building manager (also considering the occupancy schedule). This can be quantified by measuring the % of time that the temperature is outside of the acceptable range, with 0% representing optimum performance. $\% \text{ Time Outside Range} = \frac{(Hou + Huu)}{8760h}$	Objective: Maintain indoor comfort (D2.3 Table 3)

		<p>where Hou is the total number of hours during the time the building is occupied annually where temperature inside the building is outside the threshold set by the building manager, and Huu is the total number of hours during the unoccupied period where temperature inside the building is outside the building manager threshold. Temperature can represent the real teamperature or a “heat index” temperature (temperature adjusted to account for relative humidity), depending on the definition agreed by the building manager.</p>	
kw_kpi_03	Max kW demand in considered period	<p>While in many cases this value will be a necessary input to the calculation of kwmax_kpi_01, it is important to track this value separately. The exact definition of the considered period depends on the site’s contract with their energy supplier. Examples of possible considerations include, but are not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Billing periods dependant on the time of day - Billing periods dependant on the time of year - The time period or schedule over which kW demanded should be averaged to determine the max kW demand. 	Objective: Minimize power demand costs (D2.3 Table 3)

3.1.2.2 Diagrams of the validation scenario

Figure 9: Diagram of the kWmax use case, as described in D2.3 section 3.2.2

Figure 10: Sequence Diagram of the General kWmax Optimisation Use Case

3.1.2.3 Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario

The step by step description of the kWmax Control Use Case is shown in the sequence diagram above (Figure 10), with the requirements for building this connection shown in Figure 11. The sequence diagram represents the expected validation case (KWM1) and should cycle over a time period previously agreed to. This validation case, as well as possible alternative and failure states, are described in the subsections below.

It should be noted that the step-by-step process for kWmax Control is very similar to that of the ToU Optimisation, although how those constraints are defined, the priorities of the optimisation and what actions should be taken can differ significantly between the two cases. For this reason, these models have been presented as two separate use cases, but it is recommended to combine the optimisation in cases where both Use Cases are relevant.

3.1.2.3.1 Overview of the scenario

Table 10 depicts the conditions regarding the primary validation case (Energy Bill Optimisation) as well as several critical alternative and failure cases.

Table 10: Scenario conditions for the general kWmax Control validation scenario

<i>Scenario conditions</i>						
<i>No.</i>	<i>Scenario name</i>	<i>Scenario description</i>	<i>Primary actor</i>	<i>Triggering event</i>	<i>Precondition</i>	<i>Postcondition</i>
01	KWM1	Energy Bill Optimisation	LEG	DRIVE control enabled	Historical weather data, energy data, site and asset characteristics, and tariff and operational schedules provided to MPC	Energy bill optimised for kWmax. Overall energy bill optimised if combined with ToU optimisation.
02	KWM2	Loss of communication with MPC	LEG	No connection with MPC or Forecast server	Control actions from MPC already provided to LEG	MPC control actions followed and failsafe settings implemented
03	KWM3	Occupant override of DRiVE solution	User	User overrides control of one or more controllable assets locally	Control actions from MPC already provided to LEG	MPC control actions revised to consider occupant override
04	KWM4	Power demand projected above threshold	LEG	Average power demanded within the kWmax measurement limit is above the demand charge threshold provided	Control actions from MPC already provided to LEG	MPC control actions revised to reduce power consumption within the current cycle

3.1.2.3.2 Steps of the scenario

The following steps represent the possible validation scenarios of the kWmax Control use case. Specific sequence diagrams are referenced in order to better describe the considered situation. The term Site Manager refers to anyone responsible for managing the site- for a tertiary building this could be a building manager while for a residential home; this could be simply a resident. It should be noted that scenarios KWM1, KWM2 and KWM3 in the table above are identical for both ToU and kWmax, but although the scenario steps are virtually the same, they focus on a different service.

This Use Case assumes critical information is already provided regarding the site characteristics, assets, and optimisation constraints (req_tec_bmpc_5, req_tec_bmpc_6, req_tec_bmpc_7), historical

weather data (req_tec_forecast_5) and historical energy demand (req_tec_forecast_4). It also assumes connection with the DRiVE platform is active, live access to local weather data is in place at the site, and that the MPC and Forecasting Service has sufficient processing power to perform the analysis (req_tec_forecast_1, req_tec_forecast_2). Lengths of optimisation cycles, measurement cycles and number of cycles of acceptable downtime are also previously determined (a cycle is one full iteration of the general kWmax Control validation scenario KWM1).

With this information, an initial model of the building is created and the forecasting models are tuned to advise the building on appropriate actions. Table 14 describes the general kWmax Control validation scenario while the subsequent tables and figures describe variations from those scenarios.

Table 11: Step-by-step description of the kWmax Control validation scenario KWM1.

<i>KWM1</i>			
<i>Scenario name</i>		<i>Energy Bill Optimisation</i>	
<i>No.</i>	<i>Event</i>	<i>Name of process/activity</i>	<i>Description of process/activity</i>
01	Beginning of optimisation cycle	Send building state to MPC	LEG updates information regarding the state of building assets and relevant comfort data to the Cloud Platform and the MPC module Requirement ID:
02	Beginning of optimisation cycle	Send weather data to LEG	Weather data is gathered from the local station and sent to the LEG Requirement ID:
03	Weather data received by LEG	Send weather and electricity data to Forecast module	LEG updates weather data, current electricity consumption data and energy production data in the Cloud Platform and the Forecasting module Requirement ID:
04	Weather data received by Forecast module	Forecast weather, electricity consumption and energy production	Weather, electricity consumption and local energy production are forecast for a predetermined period of time based on the weather conditions (historical and current), electricity consumption, and historical energy production. Requirement ID: req_tec_forecast_3 req_tec_forecast_4 req_tec_forecast_5 req_tec_forecast_6
05	Weather, electricity consumption and energy production is forecast	Send forecast to MPC module	Forecast of weather, electricity consumption and energy production is sent as an input to the MPC module. Requirement ID:

06	Forecasts received by MPC module	Optimise electricity use	Considering the constraints provided, the forecasts received, and thermal inertia in the building, identify specific control actions for the predetermined number of cycles that would enable the building to achieve the lowest energy bill from power demand.
			Requirement ID: req_tec_bmpc_1 req_tec_bmpc_2 req_tec_bmpc_3 req_tec_bmpc_4 req_tec_bmpc_5 req_tec_bmpc_6 req_tec_bmpc_7 req_ps_comsa_4
07	Optimized control actions identified	Send control actions to LEG	Optimized control actions are sent to the LEG via the Enervalis Cloud platform
			Requirement ID:
08	Control actions received by LEG	LEG implements control actions	LEG sends control actions through the local building systems and implements them at the site, verifying that the actions have been completed
			Requirement ID: req_ps_comsa_1
09	Sufficient delay from the implementation of control actions	Send building state to MPC	LEG updates information regarding the state of building assets and relevant comfort data to the Cloud Platform and the MPC module
			Requirement ID:
10	Building state received by MPC	Validate control actions	MPC validates that the building state is in line with those performed by the control actions and the electricity consumption and production is in line with predicted values. If there is a deviation, go to step 06
			Requirement ID:
11	Control actions validated	End of cycle	Assuming no change of state, no new action is performed until the predetermined cycle is complete. Once this is completed, go to step 01
			Requirement ID:

The sequence diagram in Figure 11 presents this in detail.

Figure 11: kWmax KWM2

Table 12: Step-by-step description of the failure scenario for the loss of communication with MPC (KWM2).

KWM2			
Scenario name		Loss of communication with MPC	
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity
01	No control action received after sending building state	LEG alerts loss of connection	LEG alerts site manager and attempts to alert the MPC, Forecast and Cloud Platform that it has lost connection to the MPC platform. Requirement ID:
02	No control action received after sending building state	Local MPC module calculates next control action	If the LEG has a forecast for the current cycle stored, local MPC module calculates the control action for the next cycle and implements the action locally and goes to step 04. If there is no forecast for the current cycle stored, go to step 3. Requirement ID:

03	No forecast for current cycle stored in LEG	Revert to failsafe settings until connection is re-established	LEG reverts to the predetermined failsafe settings, allowing only local control until connection with the MPC platform is re-established.
			Requirement ID:
04	Control actions validated	End of cycle	Assuming no connection is re-established, no new action is performed until the predetermined cycle is complete. Once this is completed, go to step 01
			Requirement ID:

The sequence diagram in Figure 12 presents this in detail.

Figure 12: kWmax KWM3

Table 13: Step-by-step description of the alternative occupant override of DRiVE solution validation scenario KWM3.

KWM3			
Scenario name		Occupant override of DRiVE solution	
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity
01	Site manager overrides one or more	Send building state to MPC and Forecast	LEG updates information regarding the state of locally overridden building assets to the Cloud Platform, the MPC module and the Forecast module

	assets locally		Requirement ID: req_ps_comsa_2
02	Building state received by MPC	Optimise electricity use	Excluding the locally overridden assets, MPC performs a normal optimisation as described in KWM1 step 06. Return to KWM1 step 07.
			Requirement ID: req_ps_comsa_2

The sequence diagram in Figure 13 presents this in detail.

For the power demand projected above threshold kWmax Control validation case (KWM4), the procedure is identical to the one outlined in KWM1, with a specific focus on power consumption. The optimisation should therefore, consider shutting down any non-critical systems without sacrificing comfort in order to reduce the power demand within the current period. The process for this is shown in Figure AB below.

Figure 13: kWmax KWM4

3.1.2.4 kWmax Control: validation scenarios for Blaenau Gwent District

As mentioned in 3.1.1.4, all tests regarding the Blaenau Gwent site will be performed virtually, enabling KWM1 and KWM3 to be tested in this environment (req_ps_bgcbc_01, req_ps_bgcbc_02). An application of KWM4 can be tested as well, focusing on optimising the contracted power limit with the goal of lowering the monthly bill and minimizing potential penalties for exceeding a

certain power demand. In this way, the ideal contracted power demand should be optimised virtually considering the available assets and flexibility (req_ps_bgcbc_03).

3.1.2.5 kWmax Control: validation scenarios for the ADO Stadium

Unlike the case of the COMSA head office, the kWmax Control Use Cases will not be combined with ToU into a single optimisation at the ADO Stadium site. This means that the implementation of the scenario will not imply any additional complexity in the optimisation problem, i.e. there are no specifics outside the previously described scenarios and steps which should be addressed separately.

3.1.2.6 kWmax Control: validation scenarios for COMSA Head Office

In the case of the COMSA head office, the ToU optimisation and kWmax Control Use Cases will be combined into a single optimisation. This is because both factors are relevant when considering the overall energy bill at the COMSA site. While this does imply additional complexity in the optimisation problem, it does not necessarily result in additional validation cases. For example, if the building manager chooses to disable DRiVE implementation at the floor level through the Enervalis Cloud Portal and an individual employee overriding their local thermostat both require a process outlined in KWM3- the key difference being the scale of the corrective actions required. The step-by-step process will remain the same (signal sent from building manager to the LEG, to the Enervalis Cloud, and finally sent to the MPC as an update in the building conditions).

A local building manager will take the role of the Site Manager/Resident. The building manager will have the ability to disconnect the DRiVE solution via a physical switch (similar KWM3 if applied to all assets on the building), allowing for only local control of the assets. Additionally, the building manager will have the ability to selectively disconnect individual floors through the Consumer Portal (similar to KWM3 if applied to all assets on that floor), allowing for only local control of that floor's assets (req_ps_comsa_3).

The contract with the energy supplier is determined by an internal process, with no possibility to include explicit demand response actions. Therefore, the ToU optimisation and kWmax Control should represent the energy savings that can be achieved solely under implicit demand response actions. Approval from all relevant parties regarding validation activities is being gathered and all relevant constraints and KPIs for the optimisation are being communicated to DRiVE partners. The constraints gathered so far have been described in detail in D2.3 section 3.2 kWmax Control.

How specifically the commands are translated from the LEG to the physical devices at the COMSA site are described in detail in D2.3 section 3.2 kWmax Control, D2.4 section 2.14 Building Energy Management System, D2.4 Annex C: Memory Map for COMSA BMS, and D2.5 Figure 16 Hierarchical structure of COMSA pilot. These sections should be referenced when validating the DRiVE use case at the COMSA site.

3.1.3 Consumer Portal: validation scenarios

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for Consumer Portal and, in contrast to ToU and kWmax, there are no specific validation scenario for particular validation site at the end of the section, because the Consumer Portal is implemented at all sites in exactly the same way. All Consumer Portal validation activities will be conducted by means of physical testing.

It should be noted that in D2.3 the use case “Consumer Portal” is actually described in two separate sections, “Customer portal” and “Customer portal energy savings “. In this report, the validation

scenarios for both cases are described simultaneously because Consumer Portal and achieving energy saving through Consumer Portal are inextricable and completely intertwined.

3.1.3.1 General info on the scenario

The use case for the consumer portal has the intent to provide all relevant stakeholders to be able to consult the data. Table 14 below has been adopted from D2.3 and outlines the formal identification of the “consumer portal” use case.

Table 14: Customer portal (adapted from D2.3)

<i>Use Case Identification</i>		
<i>ID</i>	<i>Area Domain(s)/Zone(s)</i>	<i>Name of the Use Case</i>
Portal_generic	Customer premise, DER/Field, operation, enterprise	The service delivers the needed interactions to the different parties in a strict division of data visibility and editable.

It should be noted that the formal name is “portal generic” as the consumer portal for a specific project has the intent of giving all the relevant stakeholders their own insight in the data and the most important KPI’s, but only these for which they should have access to on a “need to know” basis, as explained in the list below.

- For example, when we would have a pilot in an residential area for which DRIVe would have the intent to perform congestion management or portfolio management as contracted by a social housing company or an energy provider (i.e. DEVO) . Then the resident of one house should have access to its data only, or to relevant KPI’s to guard its own energy performance.
- The social housing company or its delegate acting as the data-owner¹ would need to have access to all the data and control settings which is relevant for the district allowing them to guard and manage the services on district level.
- The DRIVe partners who need to perform optimisation for this pilot or who need to validate the use cases would have access to key data needed for their specific responsibility
- All the data is restricted to pseudonymised data only for everyone, unless it is strictly necessary to have access to personal data to perform their job. I.e. a maintenance technician would need to know the address for a technical intervention, a site administrator would need to have access to all the data as he needs to manage all the data in the database and the representation towards the stakeholders)
- Optionally, the balance responsible party BRP or the DSO or TSO which would be paying for the services could have access to an (interactive) webpage displaying the relevant business performance parameters.

All the above transactions should be compliant to local privacy laws and GDPR. In the DRIVe project it is the intent to implement an automatic and GDPR compliant system to cater for user consent, data removal and the right to be forgotten.

¹ Assuming that the social housing company or its delegate has collected GDPR compliant consent from the resident to act on their behalf.

Next to the consumer portal there should also be an API where all the relevant data can be accessed, and which applies the same access rules as the consumer portal.

In general, the consumer portal would be a website, but it is the explicit intent in DRiVE to also implement a local terminal. Research has shown that a terminal in the house itself (smart thermostat) is a much more effective feedback medium than a webpage or an app. The first serves as a constant reminder due to its prominent visibility and is also accessible by people having poor internet skills. The latter are known to be accessed heavily in the beginning of a project, but as soon as the novelty is over, the use of the website declines rapidly.

Effective influencing of the resident is particularly important for the “energy savings” use case, the definition of which is taken from D2.3 and represented in Table 17.

Table 15: Customer portal energy saving (adapted from D2.3)

<i>Use Case Identification</i>		
<i>ID</i>	<i>Area Domain(s)/Zone(s)</i>	<i>Name of the Use Case</i>
Portal_energy_saving	Customer premises/Field, operation, enterprise	This service describes and gives feedback to the customer to implement energy saving behaviour.

Objectives of both “consumer portal” and “consumer portal: energy savings”

The objectives of both use cases are:

1. To implement a consumer portal for each relevant DRiVE test site, which are:
 - a. DEVO residential area
 - b. The Woerden residential area
 - c. ADO pilot
 - d. Giesenwind Pilot
 - e. Comsa pilot

NOTE: The initial plan for the objective number 1 was to also use the Blaenau Gwent site for validation of Consumer Portal. However, as it is currently not possible (because of infrastructure and IT architecture of the site) to make the Blaenau Gwent real-time data available to the DRiVE platform via API, this use case will be trialled at the five test sites identified in the list above.

2. The relevant actors for each pilot should be defined. The access rule settings of each relevant test site should be documented and compliant to GDPR.
3. For each resident of a residential pilot either a local terminal or an individual website should be implemented to give the user insight in the collected information and the performance of the local optimisations done on their behalf
4. The consumer portal should allow the resident (the end user) to handle
 - a. User consent
 - b. User defined retention period
 - c. User request to be forgotten (which should remove all data out of the database)

- d. Individual configurations (ie comfort settings)
 - e. Input of metadata (i.e. number of inhabitants in the house)
5. The consumer portal also gives the possibility for external systems TSO/DSO/BRP to interact with the platform
6. For each residential pilot having a local objective to reduce the total power consumption or power cost on a household level it should give suitable and easy to read input on the local terminal or individual website to” nudge” the residents into the right behaviour or to give them suitable feedback of the benefits of the automatic optimising on their behalf. It should give them individual advice what could be done to reduce their total cost (i.e. shorter showers) or save energy

3.1.3.1.1 Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario: Consumer Portal

The table below contains a list KPIs to validate the Consumer Portal. It should be noted that the terms Consumer Portal and Consumer Portal are used interchangeably here. Additionally, some of the KPIs, such as cp_kpi_05, have two sub-KPIs depending on the conditions: e.g. if the KPIs is used for local operation or for web-based operation.

Table 16: KPIs for the general Consumer Portal validation scenario

<i>Key performance indicators</i>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Reference to mentioned use case objectives</i>
cp_kpi_01	Consumer Portal implementation	Number of test sites for which a consumer portal is implemented vs where it is planned.	Objective 1 The target is 1-5 (of the objectives identified in the text preceding the table)
cp_kpi_02	Documented Access rule settings	For each pilot the relevant actors are defined, and it is documented to which data they should have access. The access rule settings should be GDPR compliant and reviewed by the relevant stakeholders.	Objective 2 The target is 1-5 (of the objectives identified in the text preceding the table)
cp_kpi_03	Individual portal for the residents	For each resident in a residential pilot, an individual portal exists for representation of user relevant performance data and interactive setting of user configurations	Objective 3 Target = 95%

cp_kpi_04	Local terminal implementation	A local terminal “smart thermostat” is implemented, specifically designed to allow interactive communication with the residents in the DRiVE context (DEVO pilot for NRGcoin , Woerden pilot for automatic optimisation)	Objective 3 Target = 90 % of the planned local terminals are operational
cp_kpi_05 cp_kpi_05w Web cp_kpi_05l Local	Individual portal usage	The usage of the individual portals either local or web based is tracked # of interactions per user and per month.	Objective 3 Target: cp_kpi_05l > 2* cp_kpi_05w
cp_kpi_06	Portal user satisfaction	For all the stakeholder portals user satisfaction data is collected Remarks are used to steer the roadmap	Objective 3 Target cp_kpi_06a = 80% of stakeholders is reached Target cp_kpi_06b = 70% of the stakeholders is either satisfied or neutral in their judgement
cp_kpi_07	GDPR compliant user interactivity	For all residents of the DRiVE residential pilots GDPR compliant user interactivity is implemented and available either via website or via a local terminal	Objective 4 Target cp_kpi_07 = available for 100% of the relevant residents.
cp_kpi_08	Customer portal for external systems	For all the external systems requiring automatic access a website is foreseen for the operator of such a system giving insight in the performance of the relevant services and the operational status of remote data access	Objective 5 cp_kpi_08a Target = 100% external systems have a website cp_kpi_08b Target = 99% availability of the interfaces toward the external services

cp_kpi_09	Energy savings nudging	For each pilot having a local objective to save energy an individual webpage or a local terminal should give insight in the energy usage and give advice (nudging) to the end users in order to save energy or energy cost	cp_kpi_09. Target 100% of relevant residential users reached
cp_kpi_10	Energy savings nudging effectivity	For each relevant user the effectivity of the “nudging” should be monitored by comparing the actual savings of the “nudged” users with a control group.	cp_kpi_09 Target = X% of energy (cost) savings increase due to nudging

It should be noted that the KPIs specified in The table below contains a list KPIs to validate the Consumer Portal. It should be noted that the terms Consumer Portal and Consumer Portal are used interchangeably here. Additionally, some of the KPIs, such as cp_kpi_05, have two sub-KPIs depending on the conditions: e.g. if the KPIs is used for local operation or for web-based operation.

Table 16 are not expressed as complex mathematical formulas, but mostly as numerical targets for the coverage of functionality of the Consumer Portal. The nature of KPIs, as devised here, stems from the fact that Consumer Portal KPIs are focused on a human-machine interface realized as a web accessible service. As such, these KPIs are different from KPIs used in other use cases which are predominantly technical and therefore use a different set of KPIs. This is also reflected in the specific approach to defining the validation scenarios for this use case, which is again different from other scenarios – due to a different kind of entity (i.e. portal) being tested and validated.

3.1.3.2 Diagrams of the validation scenario

This section contains a basic functional diagram of the Consumer Portal. As can be seen from the figure below, the Consumer Portal is the junction where users and external systems can gain insight into the current measurements, control signals, forecasts and control information which are being executed on the local energy gateway.

Figure 14: Actors and interactions for use case consumer portal

3.1.3.2.1 Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario

The step by step analysis subsection of the Consumer Portal use case contains a description of the scenario conditions, primary actors, triggering events, preconditions and postconditions, which also serve the dual purpose of a step-by-step description of the scenario. This divergence from other use case descriptions stems from the fact that the Consumer Portal, as explained in the paragraph below the list of KPIs (see page 59), is different in nature from other use cases which pertain to energy management, while this pertains to user interactions and human-machine interface.

3.1.3.2.2 Overview of the scenario

The table below provides a detailed overview of the Consumer Portal validation scenario. It should be noted that the Consumer Portal, as previously mentioned on several occasions, is a significantly specific use case, which is not similar to traditional validation scenarios for devices and equipment, which, in turn, necessitated a specific approach.

Table 17: Scenario conditions for the general Consumer Portal validation scenario

<i>Scenario conditions</i>						
<i>No.</i>	<i>Scenario name</i>	<i>Scenario description</i>	<i>Primary actor</i>	<i>Triggering event</i>	<i>Precondition</i>	<i>Postcondition</i>
01	DSO portal	The portal as visible for the DSO	DSO	A user logs on and get its dashboards as well as the environment for configuring its data	DSO user profiles and users are defined Required meta data fields are defined Suitable logging period is available	All data is visible in the portal Control settings are captured and registered in the smart power suite
02	BRP portal	The portal as visible for the BRP	BRP	A user logs on and get its dashboards as well as the environment for configuring its data	BRP user profiles and users are defined Required meta data fields are defined Suitable logging period is available	All data is visible in the portal Control settings are captured and registered in the smart power suite
03	TSO portal	The portal as visible for the TSO	TSO	A user logs on and get its dashboards as well as the environment for configuring its data	TSO user profiles and users are defined Required meta data fields are defined Suitable logging period is available	All data is visible in the portal and retrievable via API, Control settings are captured and registered in the smart power suite
04	Resident portal	The portal as visible for the resident	Resident	A user logs on and get its dashboards as well as the environment for configuring	Resident user profiles and users are defined Required meta data fields are defined Suitable logging period	All data is visible in the portal and retrievable via API, Control settings are captured and registered in

				its data.	is available	the smart power suite
05	Resident portal User consent	The resident can give her consent to use their personal data compliant with GDPR	Resident	A user logs on and takes action to change to grant user consent	User consent OFF	User consent ON Personal data logging starts
06	Resident portal User consent denied	Resident portal User consent denied	Resident	A user logs on and takes action to deny user consent	User consent is ON Data logging active	User consent OFF Data logging disabled
07	Resident portal User data removal	Resident portal User data removal	Resident	A user logs on and exercises their right to be forgotten	User consent is ON Data logging active Suitable data logging exists	User consent OFF Data logging is removed out of the database
08	Operator portal	The portal as visible for the operator	Operator	A user logs on and get its dashboards as well as the environment for configuring its data.	The operator group access defined Data and meta data models are defined	The operator gets access to all resident user site as defined under his group access All data is pseudonymised
09	Admin portal	The portal as visible for the administrator	Administrator	A user logs on and get its dashboards as well as the environment for configuring its data.		The administrator gets access to all resident data, configuration data and personal data Is visible (ie address)

10	Data acquisition	Data from external devices are logged in the database for each pilot. Control actions are executable if applicable	Smart Power Suite	Smart power suite will retrieve data from the LEG at predefined intervals	Data models have been defined. External devices have been connected and are operational	Retrieved data is available in the database
11	API	Pilot Data is retrievable from the smart power suite via the API. Control data can be sent to the pilot via the API	External system Partner backends	An external system is able to retrieve and control data via the API	Data model is defined, Suitable data logging period has provide data in the database	Data is available at the external system. Control actions can be executed by external system

3.1.3.3 Steps of the scenario

For other use cases, the scenarios listed in the previous sub-section are described in more detail in this section. However, given the specific nature of Consumer Portal as a use case, the scenario steps are deemed unnecessary because triggering events, preconditions and postconditions identified in Table 17 already represent the steps for each of the scenarios.

3.1.3.4 Consumer Portal: specificities of validation scenarios at test sites

As Consumer Portal is hosted in the cloud and is identical regardless of where it is accessed from, the subsections which are, in other use case descriptions, used to address specificities of idiosyncrasies of individual sites are not relevant for this case because there are is no additional information necessary for each test site (that has not already been supplied in previous sections). Depending on the exact scope of testing at the new test site, i.e. the Woerden Site, which at the time when this report was being finalized, was subject to further discussions, pending signing of the contract, it may be possible that the Woerden site could also be used for validation the Consumer Portal. Should this be the case, any information missing from this document will be contained in the report on validation activities and the report on setting up the validation platform.

3.2 COMMUNITY SERVICES: VALIDATION SCENARIOS

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for the following DRiVE service: smart community based on NRGcoin market principles. This scenario is to be tested in two modes hybrid, cyber-physical testing and physical testing. Physical testing will be conducted at the DEVO district, while hybrid and physical testing, if proven to be feasible, should be conducted at the Woerden site. In line with the rationale provide in a relevant subsection of the updated D2.3 report, the consortium decided to add an additional test site – the Woerden site– in order to compensate for the lack of controllable assets at the DEVO site. At the time when this deliverable was being finalized, the

definitive status of the site and the possible scenarios to be implemented there (pending the owner's approval) were not fully known and were subject to further discussions and negotiations. In the context of community services, the Woerden site, at the time of finalizing this deliverable, was planned to be potentially used for both hybrid, cyber-physical mode of validation and the physical mode of validation of community services.

3.2.1 Smart community based on NRGcoin market principles

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for community optimisation in general, while there are no subsections on specific validation scenarios at different validation sites, which is deemed unnecessary because, at the time when this document was being finalized, this service is to be tested in a physical manner at the DEVO test site. A possible inclusion of the Woerden site will be addressed in subsequent reports, pending the final confirmation of the site's status and availability.

3.2.1.1 General info on the scenario

In the community optimisation based on NRGcoin there are two ways of optimisation, as defined below:

1. Manual action

The optimisation of the community is done based on input the inhabitant will receive via a local terminal or a webpage. The participants in the community are asked to change their consumption/production pattern for electricity based on individual and community targets, but essentially the action is voluntary. The action is incentivised by a reward in Energy Coin. Valuation of the energy coin can be done by subtracting the value from the consumer energy bill. The GUI for the resident will contain the forecast for the local energy production and consumption, based on this information the resident can shift his energy consumption to a timeslot where more local energy is available, this action will result in earning more energy coins for the local community this reward is a double reward as the local produced energy costs less for buying and the one who "sells" the energy has a higher reward, the detailed GUI design and interaction is part of another work package.

2. Automatic action

The inhabitants will authorise an aggregator to perform remotely controlled actions on flexible elements in their house. (i.e. heat pump, solar curtailment, home battery, district battery, etc.). The automatic optimisation will then take the NRGcoin price as an input for their optimisation schemes. This automatic action of optimising local energy consumption can also be combined with the manual actions.

A possible visual representation of the NRGcoin in the graphical user interface (GUI) is given in Figure 15 below. It should be emphasized that the visual representation of this use case was, at the time when this report was being finalized, not fully started: it should only be taken as a mock-up/concept of the actual GUI which will be implemented. What Figure 15 shows is that for every 1kWh of green energy the consumer pays 1 NRGcoin directly to the Smart Contract. This ratio (1kWh=1NRGcoin) always holds, regardless of the retail value of electricity. The Smart Contract then pays all grid fees and taxes to the DSO from the coins paid by the consumer. After that, the Smart Contract then validates the reported injection of green energy by prosumers using a variety of methods. If all reports check out, the Smart Contract mints new NRGcoins and rewards prosumers for their injected green energy. Prosumers can then sell those coins in a currency market or use them to pay for green energy later on. The currency market is where consumers buy their NRGcoins from in order to pay for their consumption. When energy is paid, the associated coins are not destroyed, but remain in circulation. To prevent excessive inflation, the minting rate decreases with time.

Figure 15: A possible visual representation of NRGcoin operation in the graphical user interface

The objectives of this use case are to:

1. Maximize revenue and savings for prosumers participating in the community DR programs, and
2. Maximize the consumption of local variable renewable energy sources within the community.

3.2.1.1.1 Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario

In the scenario of manual action, the controlling element is the inhabitant portal, many of the KPI's of the manual case are covered by the consumer portal KPI's. What is presented in the table below (Table 18) are only additions to the KPIs specified in the Consumer Portal section (please, see section 3.1.3, pg. 55).

Table 18: KPIs for the general Community Optimisation validation scenario

<i>Key performance indicators</i>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Reference to mentioned use case objectives</i>
cs_kpi_01	Consumer cost savings via manual optimisation	Difference of the annual bill under NRG coin and that of a baseline mechanism in % The optimisation of cost savings is done via manual control of the end user	Objective 1
cs_kpi_02	Consumer cost savings via automatic optimisation	Difference of the annual bill under NRG coin and that of a baseline mechanism in % The optimisation of cost savings is done via automatic control of the end user loads and energy production.	Objective 1

cs_kpi_03	Community RES self-consumption Baseline	Locally produced renewable energy that is instantly consumed by the local community in % and in absolute value for a baseline scenario	Objective 2
cs_kpi_04	Community RES self-consumption Manual optimisation	Locally produced renewable, energy that is instantly consumed by the local community in % and in absolute value when the users have manual control of the deferrable loads	Objective 2
cs_kpi_05	Community RES self-consumption Automatic optimisation	Locally produced renewable energy that is instantly consumed by the local community in % and in absolute value when the aggregator controls deferrable and other controllable load	Objective 2
cs_kpi_06	Flexibility provision accuracy In %	We will measure the ratio in % between the offered flexibility and the delivered flexibility	Avoid congestion

3.2.1.2 Diagrams of the validation scenario

This section contains a basic functional diagram of the Smart Community Based on NRGcoin Market Principle. As can be seen from the figure below, this service allows the prosumer to optimize the consumption and production of controlled devices via a local GUI. This local GUI is also used to provide automatic and manual control of aggregated devices.

Given the fact that interactions are taking place within GUI, which is related to the Consumer Portal, this use case partially overlaps with the Consumer Portal. This is reflected in both KPIs and scenario descriptions, which follow the same principles as the ones defined in section 3.1.3. and external systems can gain insight into the current measurements, control signals, forecasts and control information which are being executed on the local energy gateway.

Figure 16: Actors and interactions for the use case Smart Community Based on NRGcoin Market Principle (adapted from D2.3)

3.2.1.2.1 Overview of the scenario

The step by step analysis subsection of the Smart Community use case contains a description of the scenario conditions, primary actors, triggering events, preconditions and postconditions. Although the scenario is related to Consumer Portal, this description does not also serve the dual purpose of a step-by-step description of the scenario, in the sense that step-by-step description of the scenario is provided as a separate table.

Table 19: Scenario conditions for the general Community Optimisation validation scenario

<i>Scenario conditions</i>						
<i>No.</i>	<i>Scenario name</i>	<i>Scenario description</i>	<i>Primary actor</i>	<i>Triggering event</i>	<i>Precondition</i>	<i>Postcondition</i>
CS1	Community management manual optimisation	Community members optimise the community via information received on local GUI	AGR	Receipt of flex request from external party DSO, BRP, TSO Or emulator	Baseline has been determined Members have local GUI with optimisation instructions	Optimisation has been executed. Verify KPI 1-5 for a reference period
CS2	Community management automatic optimisation	Aggregator (DRiVE) optimises the community via automatically controlled elements (site specific)	AGR	Receipt of flex request from external party DSO, BRP, TSO Or emulator	Baseline has been determined List of controllable elements agreed by local users (via local GUI)	Optimisation has been executed. Verify KPI 1-5 for a reference period

CS3	Community management combined scenario's	Both manual and automatic controls are active (but not at the same time for one device)	AGR	Receipt of flex request from external party DSO, BRP, TSO Or emulator	Baseline has been determined List of controllable elements agreed by local users (via local GUI) Mixed control is enabled	Optimisation has been executed. Verify KPI 1-5 for a reference period
-----	--	---	-----	---	---	--

3.2.1.2.2 Steps of the scenario

The scenarios steps are highly summarised, they are described in such level of detail which should be understandable by a human validator. It is possible that during the course of the DRiVE project (parts of) this validation will be replaced by an automatic test suite, but as this is a research project in relation to which the consortium is keeping their options open.

The steps need to be repeated for inputs received from DSO, TSO and BRP as they will have different boundary values. They also need to be repeated for the manual and the automatic scenario as well as for the mixed scenarios.

During the project clear priorities will have to be set, as it is very likely that the consortium will not be able to test every variant and combination possible. These priorities will be based on the set of possibilities offered by the pilots and the budget and time restrictions of DRiVE as specified in the GA.

Table 20: Step-by-step description of the general Community Optimisation validation scenarios CS1, CS2 and CS3

<i>Scenario 1-3</i>			
<i>Scenario name</i>		Community management manual optimisation (DSO, BRP, TSO)	
<i>No.</i>	<i>Event</i>	<i>Name of process/activity</i>	<i>Description of process/activity</i>
01	Receipt of D prog request from AGR	Forecast	Verify if plan A scenario's can be made in a reliable way > 99 % Requirement ID:
02	Receipt of Flex request from external party	Flexibility aggregation	Verify if community flex offers are made in a reliable way > 99% Requirement ID:
03	Receipt of flex order	Flexibility dis-aggregation	Verify if flex order is correctly translated in dispatched information to the individual users and represented on the local terminal Requirement ID:
04	Day after execution	KPI determination	KPI 1-6 need to be determined, KPI's should be automatically reporting in the DRiVE portal Requirement ID:

3.2.1.3 Community Optimisation: specificities of validation scenarios at test sites

Just as it was the case with Consumer Portal, Community Optimisation is provided via a cloud-hosted service and is identical regardless of where it is accessed from. Therefore, the subsections which are, in other use case descriptions, used to address specificities of idiosyncrasies of individual sites are not relevant for this case because there are no additional information necessary for each test site (that has not already been supplied in previous sections). Depending on the exact scope of testing at the new test site, i.e. the Woerden Site which, at the time when this report was being finalized, was subject to further discussions, pending signing of the contract, it may be possible that the Woerden site could also be used for validation the Community Optimisation. Should this be the case, any information missing from this document will be contained in the report on validation activities and the report on setting up the validation platform.

3.3 FLEXIBILITY SERVICES FOR THE BRP: VALIDATION SCENARIOS

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for the following services: portfolio management. This scenario is to be tested in two modes: hybrid, cyber-physical testing and physical testing. Physical testing will be conducted at the DEVO Residential District and the ADO stadium, while the Giessenwind farm will be used for emulated/hybrid testing only. The DEVO Residential District may also be potentially used for hybrid, cyber-physical testing, but only if it becomes necessary during the actual validation tasks: the lack of controllable assets at the site makes its inclusion less insightful than, for example, the Woerden test site. As it has been mentioned in several previous use cases, the inclusion of the Woerden site is still ongoing at the time when this document is being finalized, which includes discussions on the scope of DR services which will be permitted for testing. Should the Woerden site be included among the test sites, the Portfolio Management use case will be tested there in the hybrid cyber-physical mode.

3.3.1 Portfolio management: validation scenarios

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for portfolio management in general, while relevant subsections provide information on specific validation scenarios at each validation site.

3.3.1.1 General info on the scenario

The detailed description of Portfolio management use case (ID: Portfolio_management) descriptions is provided in D2.3, where its scope is understood to be to actively adjust the production or offtake of a grid connected asset and with the objective to 1) reduce sourcing costs, 2) lower risk to high imbalance costs, and 3) lower imbalance costs or increase imbalance revenue (as specified in D2.3).

3.3.1.1.1 Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario

The table below outlines two KPIs which can be used to assess the validity and functionality of Portfolio Management within the DRiVE platform: 01) Portfolio management spot market performance, 02) Portfolio management imbalance market performance. Both KPIs can be claimed to be functional and market-oriented in their nature.

Table 21: KPIs for the general Portfolio Management validation scenario

Deliverable D7.1(PUBLIC) Validation Plan	69	Version 1.00 30 November 2018
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement n°774431		

Key performance indicators			
ID	Name	Description	Reference to mentioned use case objectives
pm_kpi_01	Portfolio management spot market performance	When flexibility is being used to optimize the load profile of an asset on the SPOT market, it combines the normal forecast of the load with a forecast of the SPOT prices. $\sum_{n=1 \dots 96} Forecast_{original} Price_{SPOT} - Forecast_{adjusted} Price_{SPOT}$ $S.T. \sum Forecast_{original} = Forecast_{adjusted}$	This KPI references the following objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reduce sourcing costs
pm_kpi_02	Portfolio management imbalance market performance	When flexibility is being used to optimize the load profile of an asset on the imbalance market, the asset reacts directly to the imbalance price signal. $\sum_{n=1 \dots 96} (Allocation_{original} - Forecast) Price_{Imbalance} - (Allocation_{adjusted} - Forecast) Price_{Imbalance}$	This KPI references the following objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lower risk to high imbalance costs • lower imbalance costs or increase imbalance revenue

3.3.1.2 Diagrams of the validation scenario

Figure 17: The diagram of the general Portfolio management scenario

3.3.1.3 Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario

The following subsections contain the detailed overview of the Portfolio management use case scenario, starting from the Scenario Conditions, and followed by a human-friendly description and a machine-friendly steps of the scenario and the list of information exchanges.

3.3.1.3.1 Overview of the scenario

This section presents a tabular overview of the scenario conditions and identifies the primary actor which initiates the scenario as well as the triggering event, i.e. the condition necessary for the scenario to begin. The portfolio management scenarios are classified depending on one criterion: the chronological order of the scenario. The scenarios specified can be combined for creating maximum value of the flexibility but can also be executed separately dependant on the characteristics of the available flexibility.

Table 22: Scenario conditions for the general Portfolio Management validation scenario

<i>Scenario conditions</i>						
<i>No.</i>	<i>Scenario name</i>	<i>Scenario description</i>	<i>Primary actor</i>	<i>Triggering event</i>	<i>Precondition</i>	<i>Postcondition</i>
01	PM01	Asset's flexibility is used for optimization on the spot market	BRP	Day ahead forecast BRP	- SPOT price forecast - Asset forecast	- Optimized program - Steering signal
02	PM02	Asset's flexibility is used for optimization on the imbalance market	BRP	Imbalance price signal	- Imbalance price - BRP portfolio imbalance forecast	- Steering signal

3.3.1.3.2 Steps of the scenario

The table below contains a detailed step-by-step description of the general Portfolio Management validation scenario: PM01, which corresponds to the used of optimization on the spot market, and PM02, which corresponds to the used of optimization on the imbalance market.

Table 23: Step-by-step description of the general Portfolio Management validation scenario PM01

<i>Scenario</i>			
<i>Scenario name</i>		PM01	
<i>No.</i>	<i>Event</i>	<i>Name of process/activity</i>	<i>Description of process/activity</i>
01	Daily asset forecast at 11:00	BRP creates forecast for the asset	On basis of past consumption, weather information and all other information that can be used to make the best forecast possible the BRP creates a forecast for the asset without using any price forecasts.
			Requirement ID: req_tec_forecast_3 req_tec_forecast_4 req_tec_forecast_6
02	BRP creates forecast for the asset	BRP creates forecast for the SPOT price	On basis of past prices, weather information and all other information that can be used to make the best forecast possible the BRP creates a forecast for the SPOT prices of the next day.

			Requirement ID:	req_tec_forecast_3 req_tec_excommgmt_3
03	BRP creates forecast for the SPOT price	Get volumes that can be controlled	Get the specifics of the controllable asset, the prosumer's preference and all other constraints regarding the demand response capabilities of the asset	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_1 req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
04	Get volumes that can be controlled	Create optimised program	Adjust program of asset to optimise on SPOT prices with regards to the constraints of the assets.	
			Requirement ID:	
05	Create optimised program	Trade energy	Trade the adjusted program on the SPOT market	
			Requirement ID:	
06	Trade energy	Adjust asset's behaviour	Let the asset follow the program created	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_8
07	Start settlement run supplier	Settle DR with prosumer	Based on the contractual arrangements the delivered DR is settled with the prosumer.	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_3 req_tec_excommgmt_7

Table 24: Step-by-step description of the general Portfolio Management validation scenario PM02

<i>Scenario</i>				
<i>Scenario name</i>		PM02		
<i>No.</i>	<i>Event</i>	<i>Name of process/activity</i>	<i>Description of process/activity</i>	
01	Start of day 00:00	Get BRP position	Get the information from the BRP what its position is for the current PTU	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_forecast_3
02	Get BRP position	Forecast BRP position	Based on the information available, such as current BRP position, updated renewable forecast, weather information and trades, forecast the BRP position for the upcoming PTUs.	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_forecast_3 req_tec_forecast_4 req_tec_forecast_5 req_tec_forecast_6
03	Forecast BRP position	Calculate current imbalance price	Use the information from the TSO to calculate the imbalance price for the current PTU	
			Requirement ID:	
04	Calculate current imbalance price	Forecast imbalance price	Based on the information available, such as current imbalance price, updated renewable forecast, weather information and trades, forecast the imbalance price for the upcoming PTUs.	
			Requirement ID:	
05	Forecast imbalance price	Get volumes that can be controlled	Get the specifics of the controllable asset, the prosumer's preference and all other constraints regarding the demand response capabilities of the asset	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_1 req_tec_excommgmt_6
06	Get volumes that can be controlled	Create optimised program	Adjust program of asset to optimise on imbalance prices with regards to the constraints of the assets.	

			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5
07	Create optimised program	Adjust asset's behaviour	Let the asset follow the program created	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_8
07	Start settlement run supplier	Settle DR with prosumer	Based on the contractual arrangements the delivered DR is settled with the prosumer.	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_3
				req_tec_excommgmt_7

3.3.1.4 Portfolio management: validation scenarios for the DEVO Residential District

The DEVO Residential District has virtually no controllable electrical devices which can be utilized in this scenario, as control is limited to the site's heating network. Consequently, after the DRiVe platform itself and the DRiVe validation platform become operational, it may become clear that the Portfolio Management may not be fully tested at this site. Should this happen, the rationale and detailed explanation will be provided in the validation reports, i.e. subsequent reports on setting-up the validation platform and on conducting validation activities.

3.3.1.5 Portfolio management: validation scenarios for the ADO stadium

The ADO Stadium will only be used for physical testing of the Portfolio Management. As the site is already a part of SCHOLT's portfolio and as SCHOLT has obtained the necessary permissions, the scenario was devised so as to be directly implementable at the site. In sum, at the time when the deliverable was submitted no modifications to the scenario are considered necessary.

3.3.1.6 Portfolio management: validation scenarios for the Giessenwind wind farm

The Giessenwind Windfarm will only be used for hybrid cyber-physical testing of the Portfolio Management. As such, the validation activities can be completed in complete safety of emulation with no risks of potential losses or imbalances in the grid. In short, at the time when the deliverable was submitted the scenario is considered to be implementable at the site as is.

3.3.1.7 Portfolio management: validation scenarios for the Woerden site

The Woerden site offers a plethora of controllable assets, including PV panels, house batteries, and a district-level battery. In that respects, the Woerden site is a good match for a short period of hybrid, cyber-physical testing (with real LEGs but virtualized house devices and batteries), followed by a lengthy period of physical testing. Be that as it may, the final status of the Woerden was still unknown at the time when this document was being finalized and any changes to this initial plan will be addressed in subsequent reports on the validation platform and validation activities in M24 and M34, respectively.

3.4 FLEXIBILITY SERVICES FOR THE DSO: VALIDATION SCENARIOS

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for the following services: congestion management, voltage control, and power quality support. These scenarios are to be tested in two modes: hybrid, cyber-physical emulation and physical testing. A combination of hybrid tests and/or physical tests will be conducted in the DEVO Residential District and at the Giessenwind Wind Farm. The ADO Stadium will be used only for physical testing only.

3.4.1 Congestion management: validation scenarios

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for congestion management in general, while relevant subsections provide specific information, if any, on particularities of implementing the validation scenarios at each validation site. One should bear in mind that the Congestion Management scenarios will be conducted at the test sites located in the Netherlands, meaning that the scenario is entirely adapted to the requirements of the energy market and energy-relevant regulations in the Netherlands. The scenarios, should they be used at different sites or different projects, must be modified in accordance with respective market regulations and standards.

3.4.1.1 General info on the scenario

For this scenario this section will refer highly to the USEF framework² as published on the USEF website, which is here referenced in the form in which it was accessible as of October 2018.

Objectives of congestion management:

- Avoid the thermal overloads of grid components
- Delay grid reinforcement
- Avoid grid reinforcement

By changing the electrical consumption and production pattern of all prosumers connected to a congestion point on the low voltage grid.

Scenario

DRiVE addresses the congestion management during the Plan and Validate phases of the USEF framework. As part of the Plan phase, the Aggregator establishes its initial A-plan. Responding with the flexibility to the DSO at a Congestion Point impacts an Aggregator's A-plan. Thus, the Plan and the Validate phases represent an iterative process where an Aggregator may repeatedly adjust its A-plan. By the time the gate closes, the A-plans and D-prognoses must be aligned, and all related issues should be resolved. This is the Aggregator's responsibility.

When the plan and validate phases are handled, the DRiVE components will dispatch the agreed plan towards the flexible components in the pilot (USEF operate phase). These commands will then be executed either in a virtual pilot (test-environment) or in a real customer environment depending on the grade of maturity of the applications and the authorisations obtained by the data-owners. It should be emphasized that the description of the scenario provided here includes the USEF "Operate" phase, which is not mentioned in D2.3, but is actually a DRiVE requirement.

² <https://www.usef.energy/download-the-framework>

DRIVe will restrict itself to the normal operation modes of USEF, it will not consider the orange and red regimes.

For validation purposes in this document we will restrict ourselves to a few key cases out of a USEF automatic test suite which will be made in the course of this project.

All USEF input (e.g. forecasts, A-plan, etc.) should align to the recommended USEF cycle timing for the Netherlands.

Figure 18: The USEF timing cycle, as used in the Netherlands

As it is important that the timing of the day ahead and intraday cycles are followed, we will also take some performance measurements

- How long does it take to provide an initial D-prog for the district ? (= plan A)
- How long does it take from the received flex request to the flex offer? (= Plan B)

The validation activities should also assess the solar and load forecasting accuracies, the KPIs for which were generally presented in 2.4.2.5.1 and 2.4.2.5.2.

3.4.1.1.1 Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario

The table below provides the list of 10 KPIs for assessing and validating Congestion Management. It should be noted that nine out of ten KPIs have the same overarching objective of avoiding congestions, but assess it from various the standpoints, as can be seen from descriptions below. One KPI (cm_kpi_09) has the overarching objective of ensuring prosumer comfort.

One should note that the Plan A and D-prog are treated as synonymous in the table below.

Table 25: KPIs for the general Congestion Management validation scenario

<i>Key performance indicators</i>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Reference to mentioned use case objectives</i>

cm_kpi_01	Solar production Forecast accuracy day ahead	<p>In the USEF day ahead cycle for DSO's a forecast needs to be made of the electrical energy production and consumption at the site. For this KPI we will measure the solar forecast accuracy comparing the one sent in for the last flex offer, with the real data at operation time.</p> <p>We will compare and benchmark this figure with free online tools as offered by weather services.</p> <p>To be repeated for each relevant pilot</p>	Avoid congestion
cm_kpi_02	Load Forecast accuracy day ahead	<p>In the USEF day ahead cycle for DSO's a forecast needs to be made of the electrical energy production and consumption at the site. For this KPI we will measure the electrical consumption forecast accuracy comparing the one sent in for the last flex offer, with the real data at operation time.</p> <p>We will compare and benchmark this figure with free online tools as offered by weather services.</p> <p>To be repeated for each relevant pilot</p>	Avoid congestion
cm_kpi_03	Solar production Forecast intraday	<p>In the USEF day ahead cycle for DSO's a forecast needs to be made of the electrical energy production and consumption at the site. For this KPI we will measure the solar forecast accuracy comparing the one sent in for the last flex offer, with the real data at operation time.</p> <p>We will compare and benchmark this figure with free online tools as offered by weather services.</p> <p>To be repeated for each relevant pilot</p>	Avoid congestion
cm_kpi_04	Load Forecast accuracy intraday	<p>In the USEF day ahead cycle for DSO's a forecast needs to be made of the electrical energy production and consumption at the site. For this KPI we will measure the electrical consumption forecast accuracy comparing the one sent in for the last flex offer, with the real data at operation time.</p> <p>We will compare and benchmark this figure with free online tools as offered by weather services.</p> <p>To be repeated for each relevant pilot</p> <p>Accuracy to be measured for a set of 52 PTU's</p>	Avoid congestion
cm_kpi_05	Time for plan A	We will measure the time it takes for the USEF end -to-end chain to provide an initial D-prog after the receipt of the request for D-prog from the aggregator	Avoid congestion
cm_kpi_06	Time from Flex request to flex offer	We will measure the time it takes for the USEF end -to-end chain to provide a flex offer after the receipt of the flex request as issued by the DSO	Avoid congestion
cm_kpi_07	Flexibility provision accuracy In %	We will measure the ratio in % between the offered flexibility and the delivered flexibility	Avoid congestion

cm_kpi_08	Number of outages/ months	We will count the number of outages which would occur if the virtual boundary as set by the DSO would be breached Target = 0	Avoid congestion
cm_kpi_09	Prosumer comfort	Depending on the kind of flexible elements in the demonstrator we will define comfort parameters for the end user/prosumer. We will measure or count comfort breaches as occurring due to the optimisation The minimum set is: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of cases where significant cold water at the outflow was detected <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ cold=$\leq 45^{\circ}\text{C}$ ○ Very cold=$\leq 40^{\circ}$ • % volume of cold water <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ cold =$\leq 45^{\circ}\text{C}$ ○ Very cold=$\leq 40^{\circ}\text{C}$ • Differences with control group to be assessed 	Prosumer comfort
cm_kpi_10	Volume of offered flexibility	Over a period of at least 2 summer months and 2 winter months (preferably a whole year), the validator will test how much flexibility was delivered to the DSO in kWh/day, This KPI will be split up over the flexible elements in the congestion points	Avoid congestion

3.4.1.2 Diagrams of the validation scenario

The diagram in the figure below shows the Congestion Management validation scenario, together with key actors and services necessary to execute the scenario, i.e. service.

Figure 19: The diagram of the general Congestion Management scenario

3.4.1.3 Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario

As described above, the consortium will perform end-to-end measurements in a normal USEF cycle for congestion management. Several key values will be measured, the message flow will be monitored and should confirm the USEF message flows as described in the USEF framework [9].

3.4.1.3.1 Overview of the scenario

The table below contains high-level descriptions of the steps involved in the Congestion Management validation scenario.

Table 26: Scenario conditions for the Congestion Management validation scenarios

<i>Scenario conditions</i>						
<i>No.</i>	<i>Scenario name</i>	<i>Scenario description</i>	<i>Primary actor</i>	<i>Triggering event</i>	<i>Precondition</i>	<i>Postcondition</i>

CM1	USEF conformity	<p>The validator will check the conformity with USEF of message flows of the day ahead and intraday cycles</p> <p>An automatic test suite will be written to check conformity with all variants of message flow in the normal regime.</p>	Aggregator	Start of day ahead cycle	<p>Connection with simulated DSO has been made</p> <p>CRO (Common Reference Operator) contains the congestion point definitions (CRO is a USEF role which is responsible for operating the Common Reference (CR), which contains information about connections and Congestion Points in the network.</p>	<p>USEF message flow variants result in D prog Flex offer Executed flex order Conform spec</p>
CM2	Forecast accuracy and timing	<p>The validator will measure the accuracy of the D-prog forecast for a set of 52PTU's</p> <p>On a real congestion point in all relevant demonstrators. Values for 10, 20, 30, 40 houses will be recorded</p> <p>Production and consumption forecast to be measured separately</p> <p>Day ahead and intraday cycle to be tested</p> <p>Timing between request and offer to be measured</p>	Aggregator	Request for D-prog from AGR to forecasting service	<p>Conformance with USEF message flow has been checked</p> <p>Real or simulated congestion point connected to forecasting service</p>	KPI set 1-6 determined for each step of the scenario
CM3	Flexibility performance and duration Test	<p>Write</p> <p>The validator will assess the flexibility cycle in the normal USEF regime over a period of at least 4 months on a real congestion point. With flexible elements</p> <p>All relevant pilots to be tested</p>	Aggregator	Start of day ahead and intraday cycles	USEF congestion management is running between DSO and aggregator for at least 1 congestion point in 1 pilot	During this test KPI 1-10 will be recorded and assessed

3.4.1.3.2 Steps of the scenario

At this stage the IEC 62559-2 standard calls for a step by step description of the validation scenarios. The logic behind this step is to be able to define a set of automatic validation tests which can be run in order to verify proper implementation of the code.

However, as we are using the IEC standard in the course of a research project, exploring situations beyond state of the art, we expect that in the course of this project many iterations will occur in order to reach a viable result as is normal in a learning process.

In most cases, and especially for USEF, one of the learning points is to create such a USEF conformance and performance test suite or at least give an onset to be used in follow up projects

For this reason, the desired outcomes of the validation are specified at a high level rather than going into the kind of detail as required by an automatic test suite. The validation scenarios are mostly described by one step only and at the level of detail which ensures and facilitates straightforward interpretation by a human validator.

Table 27: Step-by-step description of the Congestion Management validation scenarios CM1, CM2 and CM3

<i>Scenario</i>			
<i>Scenario name</i>		<i>Applies to CM1, CM2 and CM3</i>	
<i>No.</i>	<i>Event</i>	<i>Name of process/activity</i>	<i>Description of process/activity</i>
01	Start of day ahead cycle	USEF day ahead cycle	Check USEF message conformity for the DSO in normal regime of the day ahead cycle. Check different message sequences Requirement ID: all
01	Start of intraday cycle	USEF intraday cycle	Check USEF message conformity for the DSO in normal regime of the intraday cycle. Check different message sequences, check if responses are within the Dutch timings for cut-off. Requirement ID: all
02	Request for D-prog from AGR to forecasting service	Forecast accuracy day ahead cycle	The validator will measure the accuracy of the D-prog forecast for a set of 52PTU's On a real congestion point in all relevant demonstrators. Values for 10, 20 ,30 ,40 houses will be recorded Production and consumption forecast to be measured separately Averages based on least 1 week data per recorded value Timings between request and offer to be recorded Requirement ID: all
02	Request for D-prog from AGR to forecasting service	Forecast accuracy intraday cycle	The validator will measure the accuracy of the D-prog forecast for a set of 52PTU's On a real congestion point in all relevant demonstrators. Values for 10, 20 ,30 ,40 houses will be recorded Production and consumption forecast to be measured separately Averages based on least 1 week data per recorded value Timings between request and offer to be recorded Requirement ID: all
03	Start of day ahead and intraday cycles	Flexibility duration and performance test	During this test KPI 1-10 will be recorded and assessed Requirement ID:

3.4.1.4 Congestion management: validation scenarios for the DEVO

DEVO pilot will most probably not be used for congestion management because, at the time, there are no controllable elements in the residential pilot. The residential part of the pilot will be used for community services with NRG coin.

For district congestion management we are looking for another pilot where we can test. Pre-agreement is made but needs to be formalised (status end of October 2018)

The characteristics of the replacement test site, i.e. the Woerden site (preliminary):

- 40 houses with controllable heat pump and hot water storage of 200l
- PV installation with solar curtailment possibilities (pending suitable funding)
- Leased residential battery of 200kW/2000kWh current lease period until May 2019, extendable
- Leased home batteries of 7.8kW/7.8kWh 1-3, extendable lease period
- DSO region of Stedin

Standard scenarios CM1, CM2, and CM3 are sufficient.

3.4.1.5 Congestion management: validation scenarios for the ADO Stadium

No specific validation scenarios are needed and generic scenarios CM1, CM2, and CM3 can be used as specified above.

The only additional piece of information worth mentioning is that, in the case of the ADO Stadium test site, the flexible elements are:

- Battery of 650kW/650kWh
- 10 charge stations for E-vehicles

3.4.1.6 Congestion management: validation scenarios for the Giessenwind wind farm

No specific validation scenarios are needed and generic scenarios CM1, CM2 and CM3 can be used as specified above.

It should be mentioned that flexible elements at the Giessenwind Windfarm include:

- Battery with a capacity of 1 MW (1 MW Alfen Sopra 40-04 Energy Storage System)
- Three wind turbines with a total capacity of 9 MW (3x 3MW Enercon E-82). However, with the state of usage agreements at the time when this document was being finalized, it was not clear yet which control actions would be allowed to be performed on the wind turbines.

3.4.2 Voltage control: validation scenarios

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for voltage control (VC) in general, while relevant subsections provide information on specific validation scenarios at each validation site.

It should be noted that the current EU grid codes somewhat limit the ability of DSOs to export reactive power to transmission grids and that there are also physical operating boundaries which must not be crossed with regard to voltage control [5]. Having said that, with advanced monitoring and coordination which is provided by systems such as DRivE, distributed generation and DR assets can be used by DSOs for voltage control and losses management [8].

3.4.2.1 General info on the scenario

The detailed description of Voltage Control Use Case (ID: Voltage_control) descriptions is provided in D2.3, where its scope is understood to be to achieve optimal voltage regulation by the usage of the available demand response resources, and with the objective to 1) contribute on voltage regulation for distribution systems, 2) defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement), and 3) create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DERs to make it more attractive economically (as specified in D2.3).

3.4.2.1.1 Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario

The table below outlines two KPIs which can be used to assess the validity and functionality of VC within the DRivE platform: 01) reactive power provided, 02) voltage control activation time. Both KPIs can be claimed to be both functional and technical in nature.

Table 28: KPIs for the general Voltage Control validation scenario

<i>Key performance indicators</i>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Reference to mentioned use case objectives</i>
vc_kpi_01	Voltage variation	<p>This KPI measures the difference between the actual voltage that aggregated devices are supplying to either the LV or MV network and the aggregator’s reference value set for the activation of voltage control service. This KPI is measured in percent and it should be as close to 0 as possible.</p> $kpi_{voltageVariation} = \frac{V_{measured} - V_{ref}}{V_{ref}}$	<p>This KPI references the following objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contribute on voltage regulation for distribution systems • defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement) • create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DERs to make it more attractive economically
vc_kpi_02	Voltage control activation and ramp-up time	<p>The activation time and ramp-up (<i>actRampTVC</i>) time for voltage control should be under 5 seconds. Ideally, this should be as close to 0 as possible, while the scenario can be considered successful as long as the KPI is lower or equal to 1. The scenario should be deemed a fail if the KPI is more than 1. It should be noted that only battery storage systems can provide ramp-up times that would satisfy this KPI: for combined power and heating plants (and spinning reserves), the time constant should be longer than 5s.</p> $kpi_{actRampTVC} = \frac{activation\ time_{seconds}}{5\ s}$	<p>This KPI references the following objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contribute on voltage regulation for distribution systems • defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement) • create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DERs to make it more attractive economically

3.4.2.2 Diagrams of the validation scenario

The diagram given below (taken from D2.3) visually presents the preferred way in addressing an instantaneous voltage congestion point.

Figure 20: The diagram of the general Voltage Control scenario

3.4.2.3 Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario

The following subsections contain the detailed overview of the Voltage Control Use Case Scenario, starting from the Scenario Conditions, and followed by a human-friendly description of the steps of the scenario.

3.4.2.3.1 Overview of the scenario

This section presents a tabular overview of the scenario conditions and identifies the primary actor which initiates the scenario as well as the triggering event, i.e. the condition necessary for the scenario to begin. The voltage control scenarios are classified depending on the criterion of the forecast voltage being either below or above the permissible threshold. Theoretically, the scenarios specified below could be merged into a single, complex scenario, but the current granularity enables streamlined, focused testing and validation activities, devoid of complexities which the merged scenario would entail.

Table 29: Scenario conditions for the general Voltage Control validation scenario

Scenario conditions						
No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Precondition	Postcondition
01	VC01	Voltage congestion point is below the threshold	DSO	Voltage over the permissible range	Fluctuations in consumption/production create a voltage congestion point	Voltage is within the permissible range
02	VC02	Voltage congestion point is over the threshold	DSO	Voltage under the permissible range	Fluctuations in consumption/production create a voltage congestion point	Voltage is within the permissible range

3.4.2.3.2 Steps of the scenario

The steps of the Voltage Control scenario are provided in the detailed table below.

Table 30: Step-by-step description of the Voltage Control validation scenario VC1

Scenario			
Scenario name		VC1	
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity
01	Aggregator makes a forecast and reserves capacities for voltage control	Forecast and capacity reservation	The aggregator has a preliminary forecast that there may be voltage-related issues in the network (voltage below the threshold) and this forecast, together with the reserved capacity for voltage control, is sent to the DSO
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_2 req_tec_excommgmt_3
02	The DSO is notified of the forecast and reserved	Forecast and reserved capacity submission to the DSO	The DSO receives the forecast from the aggregators and the reserved capacity. The DSO assesses whether the forecast and capacities are acceptable or not. The DSO receives forecasts from all aggregators and then undertakes network analysis measures.
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_4
03	DSO accepts the forecast and reserves the aggregator's capacity for a possible voltage control action	DSO capacity reservation for voltage control	The outcome of the network analysis is that there is a high likelihood that the DSO may require a voltage control action and the DSO accepts the reserved capacity for voltage control from the aggregator
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_7
04	DSO sends an activation request	Voltage control activation by the DSO	DSO registers a voltage congestion point during the operation phase and sends a request for activating voltage control and also sends a reference value for voltage control to the aggregator
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_6 req_tec_excommgmt_5
05	The aggregator receives the DSO request for voltage control	Voltage control activation request reception by the aggregator	The aggregator receives a voltage control activation request and the reference value from the DSO
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6

06	The aggregator activates the reserved voltage control capacities	Voltage control activation by the aggregator	The aggregator activates the reserved capacity and ramps up production in line with the reference value sent by the DSO ($\pm 3\%$)	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6 req_tec_excommgmt_7
07	The aggregator tracks the voltage control reference value	Voltage control reference tracking by the aggregator	The aggregator monitors and modifies the behavior of agents providing voltage control support in line with the reference value sent by the DSO ($\pm 3\%$)	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
08	The DSO determines that the acceptable voltage profile has been achieved	Required voltage profile achieved	The DSO's monitoring system determines that the acceptable voltage profile has been achieved ($\pm 3\%$)	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
09	DSO sends a deactivation request	Voltage control deactivation by the DSO	DSO sends a request for deactivation of the voltage control support by the aggregator	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
10	The aggregator receives the DSO deactivation request for voltage control	Voltage control deactivation request reception by the aggregator	The aggregator receives from the DSO a request for deactivating voltage control support	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
11	The aggregator deactivates the reserved voltage control capacities	Voltage control deactivation by the aggregator	The aggregator deactivates the reserved capacity and ramps down production to the level before the scenario	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_8

Table 31: Step-by-step description of the Voltage Control validation scenario VC2

<i>Scenario</i>			
<i>Scenario name</i>		VC2	
<i>No.</i>	<i>Event</i>	<i>Name of process/activity</i>	<i>Description of process/activity</i>
01	Aggregator makes a forecast and reserves capacities for voltage control	Forecast and capacity reservation	The aggregator has a preliminary forecast that there may be voltage-related issues in the network (voltage above the threshold) and this forecast, together with the reserved capacity for voltage control, is sent to the DSO
			Requirement ID:
02	The DSO is notified of the forecast and reserved	Forecast and reserved capacity submission to the DSO	The DSO receives the forecast from the aggregators and the reserved capacity. The DSO assesses whether the forecast and capacities are acceptable or not. The DSO receives forecasts from all aggregators and then undertakes network analysis measures.
			Requirement ID:
03	DSO accepts the forecast and reserves the aggregator's	DSO capacity reservation for voltage control	The outcome of the network analysis is that there is a high likelihood that the DSO may require a voltage control action and the DSO accepts the reserved capacity for voltage control from the aggregator
			Requirement ID:

	capacity for a possible voltage control action			
04	DSO sends an activation request	Voltage control activation by the DSO	DSO registers a voltage congestion point during the operation phase and sends a request for activating voltage control and also sends a reference value for voltage control to the aggregator	Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_6 req_tec_excommgmt_5
05	The aggregator receives the DSO request for voltage control	Voltage control activation request reception by the aggregator	The aggregator receives a voltage control activation request and the reference value from the DSO	Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
06	The aggregator activates the reserved voltage control capacities	Voltage control activation by the aggregator	The aggregator activates the reserved capacity and ramps down production and/or increases consumption in line with the reference value sent by the DSO ($\pm 3\%$)	Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6 req_tec_excommgmt_7
07	The aggregator tracks the voltage control reference value	Voltage control reference value tracking by the aggregator	The aggregator monitors and modifies the behavior of agents providing voltage control support in line with the reference value sent by the DSO ($\pm 3\%$)	Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
08	The DSO determines that the acceptable voltage profile has been achieved	Required voltage profile achieved	The DSO's monitoring system determines that the acceptable voltage profile has been achieved ($\pm 3\%$)	Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
09	DSO sends a deactivation request	Voltage control deactivation by the DSO	DSO sends a request for deactivation of the voltage control support by the aggregator	Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
10	The aggregator receives the DSO deactivation request for voltage control	Voltage control deactivation request reception by the aggregator	The aggregator receives from the DSO a request for deactivating voltage control support	Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
11	The aggregator deactivates the reserved voltage control capacities	Voltage control deactivation by the aggregator	The aggregator deactivates the reserved capacity and ramps up production to the level before the scenario, or decreases consumption.	Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_8

3.4.2.4 Voltage control: validation scenarios for the Giessenwind wind farm

The Voltage Control scenarios at the Giessenwind wind farm will be tested in three modes: physical, emulation and hybrid cyber-physical emulation. No specific validation scenarios are needed and generic cases VC1 and VC2 can be used as specified above. Should the consortium obtain the

permission to operate wind generators (as opposed to only the battery), these scenarios may have to be updated. Should this be the case, the changes will be elaborated in the reports on the validation platform setting up and the report on validation activities, in the second and third year of the project, respectively.

3.4.2.5 Voltage control: validation scenarios for the COMSA Head Office

The Voltage Control scenarios at the COMSA Head Office will potentially be tested in two modes: emulation and hybrid cyber-physical emulation. The exact specification of the battery and inverters which will be installed in COMSA Head Office are still not absolutely certain (as of October 2018). At the time when the deliverable was being finalized, no specific validation scenarios are deemed necessary and generic cases VC1 and VC2 can be used as specified above.

3.4.2.6 Voltage control: validation scenarios for the Woerden site

The Voltage Control scenarios at the Woerden site may potentially be tested in three modes: physical testing, emulation and hybrid cyber-physical emulation. Should the consortium obtain the permission to use the Woerden site for voltage control, these scenarios may have to be updated. Should this be the case, the changes will be elaborated in the reports on the validation platform setting up and the report on validation activities, in the second and third year of the project, respectively.

3.4.3 Power quality support: validation scenarios

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for power quality support in general, while relevant subsections provide information on specific validation scenarios at each validation site. Power quality support will be validated at the Giessenwind test site (physical testing, emulation and hybrid cyber-physical testing) and, should the site become available, at the Woerden site (emulation and hybrid cyber-physical testing).

3.4.3.1 General info on the scenario

The detailed description of Voltage Control Use Case (ID: Power_quality_support) descriptions is provided in D2.3, where its scope is understood to be to improve the distribution grid power quality by the use of specialized functions present (or functions yet to be added) in the available DR resources. The objective of the use case is to improve the distribution grid power quality in terms of harmonic distortions and voltage sags and swells, as well as to, potentially, mitigate power interruption effects.

As explained in D2.3, Power Quality Support functions generally require fast local control loops paired with high-speed advanced metering and monitoring infrastructure, which is, among other features, equipped with sensors capable of real-time, sub-second timestep measurements of total harmonic distortion (THD) and power factor (PF).

Having in mind that the current data capability matrix does not include the aforementioned capabilities, it is conceivable that this service may neither be implemented, nor validated in DRivE, which is the possibility that was also identified early in the project, in D2.3. The reason why the scenarios are, nonetheless, given in this document stems from the fact that upgrades of metering and sensor infrastructure at test sites, which were either ongoing or yet to be commenced at the time when this deliverable was being finalized, may provide capabilities necessary to implement one or both Power Quality Support scenarios identified in this section. Be that as it may, power quality support services represent a considerable implantation challenge because of their possible negative effects on other services. Specifically, power factor correction is a difficult service to implement, because it may

have a negative effect on congestion management, while THD mitigation may, in worst case circumstances, necessitate turning off inverters, which could in turn have dire consequences on the stability of the local grid (for details, please see D2.3, section 3.9).

Additionally, it should be stressed that the market for power quality support services, as defined and identified here, is in its infancy and it is not known at the time how big the financial benefits of implementing these services may actually be, especially from the point of view of individual prosumers/consumers. Financial considerations aside, power quality services represent a valuable service for the DSO.

3.4.3.1.1 Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario

This section provides two KPIs for power quality support services, one for total harmonic distortion (THD) correction and one for power factor (PF) correction. In line with what was mentioned earlier, it is quite possible that it would not be feasible to implement pqs_kpi_01 (THD) and its respective use case, while pqs_kpsi_02 (PFC) is more feasible, but still dependent on the speed of monitoring and sensor capabilities accessible to LEGs, as well as run-time requirements of local agents running at LEGs.

Table 32: KPIs for the general Power Quality Support validation scenario

<i>Key performance indicators</i>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Reference to mentioned use case objectives</i>
pqs_kpi_01	THD correction	Voltage total harmonic distortion at the measuring point within the scope of the aggregator's control should be $\leq 8\%$ at all times. This KPI is the ratio of time when THD was over the limit and the time when THD was within the permissible limits: ideally it should be close to 0. $kpi_{thdratio} \frac{t(THD_{over})}{t(THD_{within})}$	This KPI references the following objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contribute to power quality support in the distribution systems • defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement)
pqs_kpi_02	Power factor correction	Power factor within the scope of the aggregator's control should be ≥ 0.95 at all times. This KPI is the ratio of time when power factor was over the limit and the time when power factor was within the permissible limits: ideally it should be close to 0. $kpi_{PFratio} \frac{t(PF_{under95})}{t(PF_{over95})}$	This KPI references the following objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contribute to power quality support in the distribution systems • defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement)

3.4.3.2 Diagrams of the validation scenario

The diagram shown below, depicting power quality support services, exemplifies what was already mentioned in the introductory description of this use case/scenarios: power quality support are fast local services which cannot be initiated by the aggregator due to latency of the communication channel interconnecting the local device, LEG, aggregator and market parties. The services, pending wide-

scale roll-out of 5G networks, must operate locally and their interaction with the cloud-based DR systems such as DRiVE are limited to reporting on the services provided and receiving notification on the monetary compensation for the given services.

Figure 21: The diagram of the general Power Quality Support scenario

3.4.3.3 Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario

The following subsections contain the detailed overview of the Power Quality Support Use Case Scenario, starting from the Scenario Conditions, and followed by a human-friendly description of the steps of the scenario.

3.4.3.3.1 Overview of the scenario

This section presents a tabular overview of the scenario conditions and identifies the primary actor which initiates the scenario as well as the triggering event, i.e. the condition necessary for the scenario to begin. The power quality support scenarios are classified depending on the type of power quality support which they supply: THD mitigation or PF correction.

Table 33: Scenario conditions for the Power Quality Support validation scenarios

Scenario conditions						
No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Precondition	Postcondition
PQS1	THD	Voltage total harmonic distortion at key bus is: $V_{THD} \leq 8\%$	DSO	V_{THD} is over the permissible value	Fluctuations in the operation of grid connected inverters and/or EV chargers produce too many harmonic	V_{THD} is equal to or under the permissible value

PQS2	Degree of deviation from the reference value of the power factor	The condition of connection to the network is that the power factor is > 0.95 (HIGH POWER FACTOR), in this scenario a situation will be described what if the power factor is not > 0.95	DSO	Power factor is under the permissible value	Fluctuations in the operation of grid connected inverters and/or EV chargers cause the power factor to fall below the permissible value	V_{THD} is equal to over the permissible value
------	--	--	-----	---	---	--

3.4.3.3.2 Steps of the scenario

The steps of the Power Quality Support scenarios are provided in detail in the table below.

Table 34: Step-by-step description of the Power Quality Support validation scenario PQS1

<i>PQS1</i>			
<i>Scenario name</i>		<i>Power Quality Support through lowering of THD</i>	
<i>No.</i>	<i>Event</i>	<i>Name of process/activity</i>	<i>Description of process/activity</i>
01	THD exceeded the allowed value	Identifying problems	Based on smart meter THD measurement, it was detected that THD has exceeded the allowed value
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2
02	Activating algorithm for THD	Activation of the algorithm	When the smart meter detects that an error will occur in THD, the algorithm is activated
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2
03	THD came out of the permissible limit range	Identifying problems	Based on the measurement of smart meters, it has been concluded that THD will go beyond the allowed limits
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2
04	Changing battery parameters	Changing battery parameters	If THD does not come out of the range of allowable values, but it can disturb the operation of some consumers, it can be tried with changing the battery parameters (if the echoes of the current taken from the batteries or the current to which the battery is charged will also decrease the amplitude of the higher harmonics)
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2
05	Inverter is switching off	Inverter turned off	If THD goes out of the allowable range too much then the smartest solution would be if the inverter is turned off (the inverters are turned off by priority, the inverters that mostly affect THD rise are first disabled).
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2
06	THD stopped growing	THD stopped	When measures were taken to prevent the rise of THD, it stopped growing
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2

Table 35: Step-by-step description of the general Power Quality Support validation scenario PQS2

<i>PQS2</i>

Scenario name		Power Quality Support through Power Factor Correction	
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity
01	The power factor deviates from the reference value	Deviation of power factor	The condition of connection to the network is that the power factor is > 0.95 . A group of consumers at the local level have a deviation of the power factor from the reference value.
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2
02	Measure PF to determine the degree of deviation	Degree of deviation	The power factor is measured to determine the degree of deviation and accordingly an appropriate solution has been taken
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2
03	The power factor has a small degree of deviation from the required value	Small degree of deviation	Based on the measurement, it is concluded that the power factor has a small degree of deviation from the required value
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2
04	Inverter based on the PFC option manages to regulate the power factor	PFC regulate power factor	If the power factor does not deviate much from the reference value, PFC provides a solution to the problem
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2
05	Power factor is at the require value	The power factor has been corrected	With PFC, the power factor has been corrected and is now at the required valu
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2
06	The power factor has a high degree of deviation from the required value	High degree of deviation	Based on the measurement, it is concluded that the power factor has a high degree of deviation from the required value
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2
07	Inverter is switching off	Inverter is turned off	The power factor has a large degree of deviation from the required value and the best solution is that the inverter is switched off to prevent low power factor
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2
08	Power factor is at the require value	The power factor has been corrected	Power factor is again at the required value
			Requirement ID: req_tec_rtcommgmt_1 req_tec_rtcommgmt_2

3.4.3.4 Power quality support: validation scenarios for the Giessenwind wind farm

The Power Quality Support scenarios at the Giessenwind wind farm will be tested in three modes: physical, emulation and hybrid cyber-physical emulation. No specific validation scenarios are needed and generic cases PQS1 and PQS2 can be used as specified above, on the condition that the necessary metering and sensor data is available. Should the consortium obtain the permission to operate wind generators (as opposed to only the battery), these scenarios may have to be updated. Should this be the case, the changes will be elaborated in the reports on the validation platform setting up and the report on validation activities, in the second and third year of the project, respectively.

3.4.3.5 Power quality support: validation scenarios for the COMSA Head Office

The Voltage Control scenarios at the COMSA Head Office will potentially be tested in two modes: emulation and hybrid cyber-physical emulation. The exact specification of the battery and inverters which will be installed in COMSA Head Office are still not absolutely certain (as of October 2018). At the time when the deliverable was being finalized, no specific validation scenarios are deemed necessary and generic cases PQS1 and PQS2 can be used as specified above, provided that the necessary metering, sensor and control capabilities are made available.

3.4.3.6 Power quality support: validation scenarios for the Woerden site

The Power Quality Support scenarios at the Woerden site may potentially be tested in three modes: physical testing, emulation and hybrid cyber-physical emulation. Should the consortium obtain the permission to use the Woerden site for power quality support, these scenarios may have to be updated. Should this be the case, the changes will be elaborated in the reports on the validation platform setting up and the report on validation activities, in the second and third year of the project, respectively.

3.5 FLEXIBILITY SERVICES FOR THE TSO: VALIDATION SCENARIOS

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for the following services: frequency containment reserve (FCR) and frequency restoration reserve (FRR). These scenarios are to be tested in two modes: hybrid, cyber-physical emulation and physical testing. A combination of hybrid tests and/or physical tests will be conducted at the Giessenwind wind farm and the Woerden site. COMSA Head Office will be used only for hybrid, emulated testing on the condition of procuring a battery storage for the building during the duration of the project, while the ADO stadium will be used for physical testing and, if it proves to be feasible³, hybrid tests before physical testing.

It is important to emphasize that although FCR and FRR both represent a means of ensuring the nominal frequency, they differ in scope and activation time. In terms of scope, FCR refers to operating reserves which ensure continuous containment of frequency fluctuations from the nominal value for the purpose of continuous maintenance of the power balance in the *entire synchronously interconnected system*, while FRR refers to a set of active power reserves which are at TSO's disposal for the purpose of restoration of the system frequency to the nominal frequency and restoration of power balance to the scheduled value *in a single synchronous area* which may consist of one or more Load-Frequency Control (LFC) areas [6][7]. In terms of activation time, the main difference between

³ Hybrid testing at this test site requires creating a complex real-time model and procurement of actual controllers of controlled devices.

FCR and FRR is in the speed required, where the European Union Electricity Market Glossary defines FCR as including “operating reserves with the activation time *up to 30 seconds*“ [6], while FRR is slower, in the sense that it includes “operating reserves with an activation time typically *between 30 seconds up to 15 minutes*” [7]. As far as payments for balancing energy are concerned, FCR and FCC follow the same payment system which distinguish between positive and negative balancing energy and the price which can be either positive, zero and negative. In sum, what this means is that FCR and FCC have the same KPI in terms of their essential function (i.e. maintenance of the nominal frequency) but have different time constants for their activation KPIs.

3.5.1 Frequency containment reserve: validation scenarios

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for frequency containment reserve in general, while relevant subsections provide information on specific validation scenarios at each validation site.

3.5.1.1 General info on the scenario

The detailed description of the Frequency Containment Reserve Case (ID: Frequency_containment) descriptions is provided in D2.3, where its scope is understood to be to achieve optimal frequency regulation by the usage of the available demand response resources, and with the objective to 1) contribute to frequency regulation for the TSO, 2) defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement), and 3) create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DER owners and operators to make FCR, and DR in general, more attractive economically (as specified in D2.3).

3.5.1.1.1 Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario

The table below outlines three KPIs which can be used to assess the validity and functionality of FCR within the DRiVE platform: 01) operating frequency containment reserves and 02) frequency containment reserve activation time. KPI, These KPIs can be said to be simultaneously functional and technical KPIs.

Table 36: KPIs for the general Frequency Containment Reserve validation scenario

Key performance indicators			
ID	Name	Description	Reference to mentioned use case objectives
fcr_kpi_01	Operating frequency containment reserves	The aggregator’s planned operating reserves (<i>opR</i>) for frequency containment reserve should correspond to the frequency containment reserves available during the operate phase. Ideally, this KPI should be 1, where in suboptimal cases it is lower than 1. $kpi_{opR} = \frac{operating\ reserves_{actual}}{operating\ reserves_{planned}}$	The KPI references the following objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> contribute to frequency containment reserve for distribution system defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement) create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DERs to make it more attractive economically
fcr_kpi_02	Frequency containment reserve activation time	The activation time and ramp-up time (<i>acT</i>) for frequency containment reserve should be under 30 seconds. Ideally, this should be as close to 0 as possible, while the scenario can be considered successful as long as the KPI is lower or equal to 1. The scenario should be deemed a fail if the KPI is more than 1.	The KPI references the following objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> contribute to frequency containment reserve for distribution system defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement) create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DERs to make it more attractive economically

		$kpi_{actTFCR} = \frac{activation\ time_{seconds}}{30\ s}$	
--	--	--	--

3.5.1.2 Diagrams of the validation scenario

The diagram given below (taken from D2.3) visually presents the high-level principles by which frequency containment reserve operates.

Figure 22: The diagram of the general Frequency Containment Reserve scenario

3.5.1.3 Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario

The following subsections contain the detailed overview of the Frequency Containment Reserve scenario, starting from the Scenario Conditions, and followed by a human-friendly description of the steps of the scenario.

3.5.1.3.1 Overview of the scenario

This section presents a tabular overview of the scenario conditions and identifies the primary actor which initiates the scenario as well as the triggering event, i.e. the condition necessary for the scenario

to begin. The Frequency Containment Reserve is envisaged as a single scenario in which the TSO is the primary actor.

Table 37: Scenario conditions for the Frequency Containment Reserve validation scenario

<i>Scenario conditions</i>						
<i>No.</i>	<i>Scenario name</i>	<i>Scenario description</i>	<i>Primary actor</i>	<i>Triggering event</i>	<i>Precondition</i>	<i>Postcondition</i>
FCR1	Degree of deviation of reference value	Due to network failure, there is a deviation of the frequency from the nominal value	TSO	Frequency deviates from nominal	Fluctuations in consumption/production create a congestion point	Degree of deviation of reference value

3.5.1.3.2 Steps of the scenario

The steps of the Frequency Containment Reserve scenario are provided in detail in the table below.

Table 38: Step-by-step description of the Frequency Containment Reserve validation scenario FCR1

<i>FCR1</i>			
<i>Scenario name</i>		<i>Frequency Containment Reserve</i>	
<i>No.</i>	<i>Event</i>	<i>Name of process/activity</i>	<i>Description of process/activity</i>
01	Aggregator makes a forecast and reserves capacities for frequency containment reserve	Forecast and capacity reservation	The aggregator has a preliminary forecast, together with the reserved capacity for frequency containment reserve, is sent to the TSO
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_2 req_tec_excommgmt_3
02	The TSO is notified of the forecast and reserved	Forecast and reserved capacity submission to the TSO	The TSO receives the forecast from the aggregators and the reserved capacity. The TSO assesses whether the forecast and capacities are acceptable or not. The TSO receives forecasts from all aggregators and then undertakes network analysis measures.
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_4
03	TSO accepts the forecast and reserves the aggregator's capacity for a possible frequency containment reserve	TSO capacity reservation for frequency containment reserve	The outcome of the network analysis is that there is a high likelihood that the TSO may require a frequency containment reserve action and the TSO accepts the reserved capacity for frequency containment reserve from the aggregator
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_7
04	TSO sends an activation request	Frequency containment reserve activation by the TSO	TSO registers a frequency congestion point during the operation phase and sends a request for activating frequency containment reserve and also sends a reference value for frequency reserve containment to the aggregator
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6

05	The aggregator receives the TSO request for frequency reserve containment	Frequency containment reserve activation request reception by the aggregator	The aggregator receives a frequency containment reserve activation request and the reference value from the TSO	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
06	The aggregator activates the reserved frequency containment reserve capacities	Frequency containment reserve activation by the aggregator	The aggregator activates the reserved capacity and ramps up production in line with the reference value sent by the TSO ($\pm 3\%$)	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6 req_tec_excommgmt_7
07	The aggregator tracks the frequency reserve containment reference value	Frequency containment reserve reference value tracking by the aggregator	The aggregator monitors and modifies the behavior of agents providing frequency containment reserve support in line with the reference value sent by the TSO ($\pm 3\%$)	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
08	The TSO determines that the acceptable frequency profile has been achieved	Required frequency containment reserve achieved	The TSO's monitoring system determines that the acceptable frequency profile has been achieved ($\pm 3\%$)	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
09	TSO sends a deactivation request	Frequency containment reserve deactivation by the TSO	TSO sends a request for deactivation of the frequency containment reserve support by the aggregator	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
10	The aggregator receives the TSO deactivation request for frequency containment reserve	Frequency containment reserve deactivation request reception by the aggregator	The aggregator receives from the TSO a request for deactivating frequency containment reserve support	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
11	The aggregator deactivates the reserved frequency containment reserve capacities	The aggregator deactivates the reserved frequency containment reserve capacities	The aggregator deactivates the reserved capacity and ramps up production to the level before the scenario, or decreases consumption.	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_8

3.5.1.4 Frequency containment reserve: validation scenarios for the ADO stadium

The ADO Stadium site will be used for the validation of the Frequency Containment Reserve service exclusively in the physical testing mode. At the time when the report was being finalized no specific validation scenarios were deemed necessary, i.e. the generic use case FCR1 can be used for this site as specified above.

3.5.1.5 Frequency containment reserve: validation scenarios for the Giessenwind Wind Farm

The Giessenwind Wind Farm site will be used for the validation of the Frequency Containment Reserve service in all three validation modes: emulation, hybrid cyber-physical emulation and physical testing. At the time when the report was being finalized no specific validation scenarios were deemed necessary, i.e. the generic use case FCR1 can be used for this site as specified above.

3.5.1.6 Frequency containment reserve: validation scenarios for the COMSA Head Office

The COMSA Head Office site will be used for the validation of the Frequency Containment Reserve service exclusively in non-physical validation modes: emulation and hybrid cyber-physical emulation. At the time when the report was being finalized no specific validation scenarios were deemed necessary, i.e. the generic use case FCR1 can be used for this site as specified above.

3.5.1.7 Frequency containment reserve: validation scenarios for the Woerden site

The Frequency Containment Reserve at the Woerden site may potentially be tested in three modes: physical testing, emulation and hybrid cyber-physical emulation. Whether this scenario would be tested at the Woerden site depends on two factors: the final agreement permitting the consortium to use the Woerden site for flexibility services for the TSO, and the status and availability of battery storage systems (house-level and district level) at the site. Namely, as it has been mentioned in several previous use cases and scenarios, the batteries at the Woerden site are leased and the lease contract is set to expire early in 2019. Should these batteries be available for the duration of the validation activities, these scenarios may have to be updated to include the Woerden site. Should this be the case, the changes will be elaborated in the reports on the validation platform setting up and the report on validation activities, in the second and third year of the project, respectively.

3.5.2 Frequency restoration reserve: validation scenarios

This section contains standardized validation scenarios for frequency restoration reserve in general, while relevant subsections provide information on specific validation scenarios at each validation site.

3.5.2.1 General info on the scenario

The detailed description of the Frequency Containment Reserve Case (ID: Frequency_restoration) descriptions is provided in D2.3, where its scope is understood to be the dispatch of customer loads/generation/storage based on real-time TSO decisions triggered by frequency deviation measurements and bid prices on an imbalance market, all for the purpose to help maintain generation-demand balance. Frequency Restoration Reserve has two main objectives. The first objective is to be an additional flexibility means for TSOs to maintain the grid balance and stability and one that has the potential to be less expensive than traditional forms of generation. The second objective is to create

new revenue sources and business opportunities for DR resources to make DR and ancillary services more attractive from the economic point of view.

3.5.2.1.1 Key performance indicators (KPIs) for the validation scenario

The table below outlines three KPIs which can be used to assess the validity and functionality of FRR within the DRiVe platform: 01) active power reserves for frequency containment reserves, and 02) frequency restoration reserve activation time. Both KPIs can be classified as being simultaneously functional and technical KPIs.

Table 39: KPIs for the general Frequency Restoration Reserve validation scenario

<i>Key performance indicators</i>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Reference to mentioned use case objectives</i>
frr_kpi_01	Active power reserves for frequency restoration	The aggregator's planned active power reserves (<i>apR</i>) for frequency restoration reserve should correspond to the frequency containment reserves available during the operate phase. Ideally, this KPI should be 1, where in suboptimal cases it is lower than 1. $kpi_{apR} = \frac{operating\ reserves_{actual}}{operating\ reserves_{planned}}$	The KPI references the following objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> contribute to frequency restoration reserve for distribution system defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement) create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DERs to make it more attractive economically
fr_r_kpi_02	Frequency restoration reserve activation time	The activation time and ramp-up time (<i>actFRR</i>) for frequency restoration reserve should be between 30 seconds and 15 minutes. Ideally, this should be as close to 0 as possible, while the scenario can be considered successful as long as the KPI is lower or equal to 1. The scenario should be deemed a fail if the KPI is more than 1. $kpi_{actFRR} = \frac{activation\ time_{seconds}}{900\ s}$	The KPI references the following objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> contribute to frequency restoration reserve for distribution system defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement) create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DERs to make it more attractive economically

3.5.2.2 Diagrams of the validation scenario

The diagram given below (taken from D2.3) visually presents the high-level principles by which frequency restoration reserve operates.

Figure 23: The diagram of the general Frequency Restoration Reserve scenario

3.5.2.3 Step-by-step analysis of the validation scenario

The following subsections contain the detailed overview of the Frequency Restoration Reserve scenario, starting from the Scenario Conditions, and followed by a human-friendly description of the steps of the scenario.

3.5.2.3.1 Overview of the scenario

This section presents a tabular overview of the scenario conditions and identifies the primary actor which initiates the scenario as well as the triggering event, i.e. the condition necessary for the scenario to begin. Just like the previous scenario (FCR), Frequency Restoration Reserve (FCR) is envisaged as a single scenario in which the TSO is the primary actor.

Table 40: Scenario conditions for the Frequency Restoration Reserve validation scenario

Scenario conditions						
No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Precondition	Postcondition
FRR1	Degree of deviation of reference value	Due to network failure, there is a deviation of the frequency from nominal value	TSO	Frequency deviates from nominal	Fluctuations in consumption production create a congestion point	Degree of reference value

3.5.2.3.2 Steps of the scenario

The steps of the Frequency Restoration Reserve scenario are provided in detail in the table below.

**Table 41: Step-by-step description of the Frequency Restoration Reserve validation scenario
FRR1**

FRR1			
Scenario name		Frequency Restoration Reserve	
No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity
01	Aggregator makes a forecast and reserves capacities for frequency restoration reserve	Forecast and capacity reservation	The aggregator has a preliminary forecast, together with the reserved capacity for frequency restoration reserve, is sent to the TSO
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_2 req_tec_excommgmt_3
02	The TSO is notified of the forecast and reserved	Forecast and reserved capacity submission to the TSO	The TSO receives the forecast from the aggregators and the reserved capacity. The TSO assesses whether the forecast and capacities are acceptable or not. The TSO receives forecasts from all aggregators and then undertakes network analysis measures.
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_4
03	TSO accepts the forecast and reserves the aggregator's capacity for a possible frequency restoration reserve	TSO capacity reservation for frequency restoration reserve	The outcome of the network analysis is that there is a high likelihood that the TSO may require a frequency restoration reserve action and the TSO accepts the reserved capacity for frequency restoration reserve from the aggregator
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_7
04	TSO sends an activation request	Frequency restoration reserve activation by the TSO	TSO registers a frequency congestion point during the operation phase and sends a request for activating frequency restoration reserve and also sends a reference value for frequency restoration reserve to the aggregator
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
05	The aggregator receives request	Frequency restoration reserve activation request reception by the aggregator	The aggregator receives a frequency restoration reserve activation request and the reference value from the TSO
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
06	The aggregator activates the reserved frequency restoration reserve capacities	Frequency restoration reserve activation by the aggregator	The aggregator receives a frequency containment reserve activation request and the reference value from the TSO , reaching the reference value within 15 minutes
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
07	The aggregator tracks the frequency restoration reserve reference value	Required frequency restoration reserve achieved	The aggregator monitors and modifies the behavior of agents providing frequency restoration reserve support in line with the reference value sent by the TSO ($\pm 3\%$)
			Requirement ID: req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
08	The TSO determines that	Frequency Containment Report	The TSO's monitoring system determines that the acceptable frequency profile has been achieved ($\pm 3\%$)

	the acceptable frequency profile has been achieved		Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
09	TSO sends a deactivation request	Frequency containment reserve deactivation by the TSO	TSO sends a request for deactivation of the frequency containment reserve support by the aggregator	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
10	The aggregator receives the TSO deactivation request for frequency restoration reserve	Frequency restoration reserve deactivation request reception by the aggregator	The aggregator receives from the TSO a request for deactivating frequency containment reserve support	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_5 req_tec_excommgmt_6
11	The aggregator deactivates the reserved frequency restoration reserve capacities	The aggregator deactivates the reserved frequency restoration reserve capacities	The aggregator deactivates the reserved capacity and ramps up production to the level before the scenario, or decreases consumption.	
			Requirement ID:	req_tec_excommgmt_8

3.5.2.4 Frequency restoration reserve: validation scenarios for the DEVO Residential District

The DEVO Residential District pilot most probably will not be used for Frequency Restoration Reserve, because, at the time when the document was being finalized and the foreseeable future, there are no controllable elements in the residential pilot which could be used for the FRR1 scenario. The reason why this site was originally included in this scenario stemmed from possible upgrades to the site, including a battery storage. Be that as it may, the site was originally planned to be validated for Frequency Restoration Reserve only in the non-physical mode of validation: emulation and hybrid, cyber-physical emulation.

3.5.2.5 Frequency restoration reserve: validation scenarios for the ADO stadium

The ADO Stadium site will be used for the validation of the Frequency Restoration Reserve service exclusively in the physical testing mode. At the time when the report was being finalized no specific validation scenarios were deemed necessary, i.e. the generic use case FRR1 can be used for this site as specified above.

3.5.2.6 Frequency restoration reserve: validation scenarios for the Giessenwind wind farm

The Giessenwind Wind Farm site will be used for the validation of the Frequency Restoration Reserve service in all three validation modes: emulation, hybrid cyber-physical emulation and physical testing. At the time when the report was being finalized no specific validation scenarios were deemed necessary, i.e. the generic use case FRR1 can be used for this site as specified above.

3.5.2.7 Frequency restoration reserve: validation scenarios for the COMSA Head Office

The COMSA Head Office site will be used for the validation of the Frequency Restoration Reserve service exclusively in non-physical validation modes: emulation and hybrid cyber-physical emulation. At the time when the report was being finalized no specific validation scenarios were deemed necessary, i.e. the generic use case FRR1 can be used for this site as specified above.

3.5.2.8 Frequency restoration reserve: validation scenarios for the Woerden site

The Frequency Restoration Reserve at the Woerden site may potentially be tested in three modes: physical testing, emulation and hybrid cyber-physical emulation. Whether this scenario would be tested at the Woerden site depends on two factors: the final agreement permitting the consortium to use the Woerden site for flexibility services for the TSO, and the status and availability of battery storage systems (house-level and district level) at the site. Namely, as it has been mentioned in several previous use cases and scenarios (including Frequency Containment Reserve), the batteries at the Woerden site are leased and the lease contract is set to expire early in 2019. Should these batteries be available for the duration of the validation activities, these scenarios may have to be updated to include the Woerden site. Should this be the case, the changes will be elaborated in the reports on the validation platform setting up and the report on validation activities, in the second and third year of the project, respectively.

3.6 CYBER SECURITY: VALIDATION SCENARIOS

This section contains validation scenarios related to cyber security. The following list does not attempt to be exhaustive but presents the list of the different components that could be involved in other scenarios that could be developed in the frame of the DRiVE project, pending the actual DRiVE system being developed and deployed.

Indeed, additional scenarios could be developed depending on the level of information we have (through log collection) from the other components, the features developed on these components and their relevance regarding the cyber security issues in the DRiVE project.

Having in mind that cyber security is not a separate use case, but a protective layer which will be developed to provide cyber security to all services described in use cases, the following sections use a high-level description of validation scenarios, as well as KPIs for their assessment. A more detailed overview of cyber security provisions and the manner in which they were implemented and validated will be provided in subsequent deliverables from the validation work package, system integration work package and cyber security work package.

3.6.1 Forecast correlation: validation scenario

In this scenario, we try to identify a problem between the cloud forecast solution and the local one. Indeed, a difference between the cloud and the local forecast could be the result of a cyber-attack and need to be supervised.

Therefore, the result of the locale and the cloud forecast will be continuously compared by the detection capacity and any problem will trigger an alarm that will be used for further analysis or in a more complex scenario.

It would be tempting to revoke automatically the gateway on which the local forecast is embedded because any problem between local and cloud forecast should be the result of a gateway modification. As there is no physical access, the cloud platform offers a smaller attack surface which makes an attack more difficult and so less probable. But less probable doesn't mean impossible and in case of illegal cloud platform modification, this measure would lead to the automatic revocation of all gateway connected to the system, leading to a Deny of Service (DoS) attack. That's why an alarm is triggered instead of an automatic gateway revocation.

1. Identify inconsistency between cloud and embedded forecast.
2. Trigger an alarm to the investigation capacity.

KPI: Considering this scenario, a KPI could be defined as the reaction time of the system. In that case, the system should trigger an alarm less than 1 minute after the problem of forecast is detected.

3.6.2 Intrusion on AMQP message queue: validation scenario

In this scenario, any intrusion on AMQP message queue between the gateway and the Enernalis backend will be detected. In that case, the gateway needs to be revoked immediately as the communication channel is compromised.

1. Identify intrusion on AMQP message queue.
2. Revocation of the gateway.

KPI: The gateway is revoked within one minute.

3.6.3 Malicious firmware upload: validation scenario

In this scenario, we will detect an attempt to modify a gateway firmware. This scenario starts from the gateway enrolment and goes until its revocation after having detected the modification. Here are the different steps of the scenario:

1. Registration of a new gateway in the central asset management.
2. Automatically add the gateway under supervision rules as soon as the gateway is registered.
3. Detect a divergence between an update order from the cloud and the version on the gateway.
4. Revocation of the gateway.

KPI: The gateway is revoked within one minute.

3.6.4 Unauthorized access to HMI: validation scenario

This scenario shows how to detect and handle a suspicious connection on the Enernalis cloud backend human-machine interface (HMI).

1. Admin connection attempt on the HMI out of working days and/or out of the country.
2. Ask for a second factor for authentication.
3. Trigger an alarm to the investigation capacity.

KPI: alarm triggered within one minute. Even if the second factor is correctly provided, the alarm must be triggered because this event can be taken into account in the frame of a more complex scenario.

3.6.5 Summary of cyber security KPIs

The table below provides a tabular overview of the KPIs described in the previous subsection.

Table 42: KPIs for Cyber Security

<i>Key performance indicators</i>			
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Reference to mentioned use case objectives</i>
cys_kpi_01	Forecast correlation	This KPIs assess the system capability to first identify inconsistencies between the cloud backend and embedded forecast and then to trigger an alarm to the investigation capacity. Cys_kpi_01 is defined as the reaction time. time to trigger an alarm < 1 minute (after the problem in forecast is detected)	N/A (cyber security is not a separate use case, but a protective layer which will be developed to provide cyber security to all services described in other use cases)
cys_kpi_02	AMQP message queue intrusion	This KPIs assess the system capability to detect any intrusion into the AMQP message queue between the local energy gateway and the Enervalis backend and to revoke the local energy gateway. Cys_kpi_02 is defined as the reaction time. time to revoke the LEG < 1 minute (after the AMQP message queue intrusion is detected)	N/A (cyber security is not a separate use case, but a protective layer which will be developed to provide cyber security to all services described in other use cases)
cys_kpi_03	Malicious firmware upload attempt	This KPIs assess the system capability to first detect an attempt to overwrite or modify the firmware of the local energy gateway and then to revoke the local energy gateway. Cys_kpi_03 is defined as the reaction time. time to revoke the LEG < 1 minute (after the firmware upload/modification is detected)	N/A (cyber security is not a separate use case, but a protective layer which will be developed to provide cyber security to all services described in other use cases)
cys_kpi_04	Unauthorized access to HMI	This KPIs assess the system capability to first detect an unauthorized access to HMI provided by the Enervalis cloud-based backend and then to trigger an alarm. Cys_kpi_04 is defined as the reaction time. time to trigger an alarm < 1 minute (after the unauthorize HMI access is detected)	N/A (cyber security is not a separate use case, but a protective layer which will be developed to provide cyber security to all services described in other use cases)

4 VALIDATION TIMELINE

This chapter provides the optimal timeline for conducting validation activities specified in the previous chapter. It contains two sets of figures, i.e. Gantt charts, for start and end month of validation activities:

- a) a timeline for validation activities of each service, and
- b) a timeline for validation activities for each individual test sites.

These two forms of timeline presentation provide the optimal starting point for tracking validation activities in subsequent tasks within WP7.

The general timeline of all validation activities is given in the table below, which identifies individual test site, functionalities tested and validated at each site, as well as modes of validation used for each functionality.

Table 43: General validation timeline for all DRIVe functionalities at all test sites (orange = physical testing, green = emulation and/or hybrid cyber-physical testing, grey =offline simulation)

Unless stated otherwise, the validation timeline does not include specific milestones.

As can be deduced from the table above, given the complexity of the DRiVE platform and the ultimate goal of proving its benefits in real time operation, it was decided that the safest and the most logical way to do validation is by employing the incremental approach: instead of implementing all functionalities at the same time at all test sites, the validation activities will be conducted incrementally by implementing individual functionalities at an individual test site and then bringing other sites online as the previous ones become mostly operational. The principle of non-simultaneous testing refers primarily to physical testing. Hybrid-physical testing can be conducted independently from physical, preferably before the physical testing, while the number of simultaneous sites may vary from one to two, depending on the complexity of the fidelity and complexity of the real-time model of the test site and the required time step of the emulation. The exact number of concurrent sites in the hybrid-physical testing will be determined in the final stages of the validation platform setting up, which is the focus of a separate task that builds on the foundations of this one.

The timelines given in the sections below reflect the aforementioned incremental approach to organizing validation activities that combine non-physical and physical testing.

It is of the utmost importance to emphasize that the timelines given in this section represent the desired timelines, while the actual implementation of each given timelines shall depend on the as-of-yet-unknown peculiarities and specificities of setting up the DRiVE solution at each test site. In short, it is possible that the actual validation activities will be conducted on the basis of timelines that, to a smaller or greater degree, diverge from the ones shown in this section, due to technical, organization, legal or other difficulties which may arise during the implementation stage.

4.1 VALIDATION TIMELINE FOR IN-BUILDING SERVICES FOR THE PROSUMER

This section contains the timeline for conducting validation activities of the following services: ToU optimisation, kWmax control, and consumer portal. These services are to be tested in offline simulation, hybrid cyber-physical emulation mode and physical mode at the following test sites: Bleanau Gwent, DEVO District, ADO Stadium, Giessenwind Wind Farm, COMSA Head Office and the Woerden Site. It should be noted that the Blaenau Gwent will only be tested in the offline simulation mode within the REEFS platform.

Table 44: Validation timeline for in-building services for the prosumer

	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	
	(2019-03)	(2019-04)	(2019-05)	(2019-06)	(2019-07)	(2019-08)	(2019-09)	(2019-10)	(2019-11)	(2019-12)	(2020-01)	(2020-02)	(2020-03)	(2020-04)	(2020-05)	
ToU Optimization	BGCBC															
ToU Optimization			COMSA HQ: Single floor physical testing				COMSA HQ: Whole building physical testing									
kWmax Control	BGCBC															
kWmax Control		ADO Stadium														
kWmax Control			COMSA HQ: Single floor physical testing				COMSA HQ: Single floor physical testing									
kWmax Control	COMSA HQ															
kWmx Control	Woerden															
Consumer Portal	DEVO District															
Consumer Portal	ADO Stadium															
Consumer Portal	Giessenwind Wind Farm (WF)															
Consumer Portal	COMSA HQ															
Consumer Portal	Woerden															

As is the case in all timelines, orange colour indicates physical testing, the green colour indicates emulation and/or cyber-physical testing, while the grey colour indicates the offline simulation in REEFS.

4.2 VALIDATION TIMELINE FOR COMMUNITY SERVICES

This section contains the timeline for conducting validation activities of the following service: community optimization, i.e. smart community based on NRGcoin market principles. This service is to be tested in hybrid cyber-physical mode and physical mode at the following test sites: DEVO District and the Woerden Site.

Table 45: Validation timeline for community services

	M16 (2019-03)	M17 (2019-04)	M18 (2019-05)	M19 (2019-06)	M20 (2019-07)	M21 (2019-08)	M22 (2019-09)	M23 (2019-10)	M24 (2019-11)	M25 (2019-12)	M26 (2020-01)	M27 (2020-02)	M28 (2020-03)	M29 (2020-04)	M30 (2020-05)
Community Optimization		DEVO District													
Community Optimization	Woerden			DEVO District											

As is the case in all timelines, orange colour indicates physical testing, the green colour indicates emulation and/or cyber-physical testing, while the grey colour indicates the offline simulation in REEFS.

4.3 VALIDATION TIMELINE FOR FLEXIBILITY SERVICES FOR THE BRP

This section contains the timeline for conducting validation activities of the following service: portfolio management. This service is to be tested in hybrid cyber-physical mode and physical mode at the following test sites: DEVO District, ADO Stadium, Giessenwind Wind Farm, and the Woerden Site. It should be noted that the DEVO District, most likely, will not be used to validate these services due to a lack of controllable assets.

Table 46: Validation timeline for flexibility services for the BRP

	M16 (2019-03)	M17 (2019-04)	M18 (2019-05)	M19 (2019-06)	M20 (2019-07)	M21 (2019-08)	M22 (2019-09)	M23 (2019-10)	M24 (2019-11)	M25 (2019-12)	M26 (2020-01)	M27 (2020-02)	M28 (2020-03)	M29 (2020-04)	M30 (2020-05)
Portfolio Management		DEVO District													
Portfolio Management				DEVO District											
Portfolio Management		ADO Stadium													
Portfolio Management	Giessenwind Wind Farm (WF)														
Portfolio Management	Woerden														

As is the case in all timelines, orange colour indicates physical testing, the green colour indicates emulation and/or cyber-physical testing, while the grey colour indicates the offline simulation in REEFS.

4.4 VALIDATION TIMELINE FOR FLEXIBILITY SERVICES FOR THE DSO

This section contains the timeline for conducting validation activities of the following services: congestion management, voltage control, and power quality support. These services are to be tested in hybrid cyber-physical mode and physical mode at the following test sites: DEVO District, ADO Stadium, Giessenwind Wind Farm, COMSA Head Office and the Woerden Site. It should be noted that the DEVO District, most likely, will not be used to validate these services due to a lack of controllable assets.

Table 47: Validation timeline for flexibility services for the DSO

As is the case in all timelines, orange colour indicates physical testing, the green colour indicates emulation and/or cyber-physical testing, while the grey colour indicates the offline simulation in REEFS.

4.5 VALIDATION TIMELINE FOR FLEXIBILITY SERVICES FOR THE TSO

This section contains the timeline for conducting validation activities of the following services: frequency containment reserve, and frequency restoration reserve. These services are to be tested in hybrid cyber-physical mode and physical mode at the following test sites: ADO Stadium, Giessenwind Wind Farm, COMSA Head Office and DEVO District. It should be noted that the DEVO District, most likely, will not be used to validate these services due to a lack of controllable assets. Additionally, the use of Woerden site depends on the availability of the battery or batteries (currently leases, but the lease expires before the beginning of validation activities).

As is the case in all timelines, orange colour indicates physical testing, the green colour indicates emulation and/or cyber-physical testing, while the grey colour indicates the offline simulation in REEFS.

Table 48: Validation timeline for flexibility services for the TSO

5 STRATEGIES TO ENSURE RELIABILITY OF RESULTS

Although the definitive architecture of the validation platform is not devised at the time when this report was being finalized, the general strategies for ensuring the reliability of the results have been identified and will be implemented during the subsequent activities of Task 7.3 (setting up the validation platform and best practices). Having in mind that the validation activities will be conducted in two modes - 1) physical testing and 2) non-physical (virtualized) testing – this section of the document explains the considerations necessary to ensure the reliability of results in each of these validation modes.

5.1 STRATEGIES FOR ENSURING THE RELIABILITY OF THE RESULTS OF PHYSICAL TESTING

In accordance with the principles of physical testing as a validation mode (as explained in 2.2.1), it is assumed that the reliability of validation results represents a non-issue. Namely, as physical testing of the DRiVE solution will involve control of physical grid-tied assets with real-time interactions among DRiVE and the BRP, DSO, TSO and individual consumers at pilot sites, the results will be inherently reliable thanks to the smart metering capabilities, protection devices and monitoring assets already installed at pilot sites and in SCADA systems of the BRP, DSO and TSO. In other words, the KPIs are calculated on the basis of data coming from a production system with independently certified smart metering and monitoring infrastructure (ABB-produced local energy gateways, smart meters, as well as the monitoring and measurement systems of BRPs, DSOs and TSOs which provide reference values and measure relevant parameters of the aggregated assets/devices).

5.2 STRATEGIES FOR ENSURING THE RELIABILITY OF THE RESULTS OF NON-PHYSICAL (VIRTUALIZED) TESTING

Unlike physical testing, which, as explained above, is deemed inherently reliable due to its physical nature where multiple parties can immediately detect erroneous data and/or faults, non-physical (virtualized) testing requires a proper strategy for ensuring the reliability of the results. As explained in 2.2.2, non-physical testing/validation of the DRiVE solution will involve three different modes: 1) offline simulation, 2) emulation and 3) hybrid, cyber-physical emulation (with virtualized devices, but real local energy gateways). Despite differences among these modes (please see 2.2.2), the strategies for ensuring the reliability of results are identical for all of them, which stems from their common denominator: their non-physical (virtualized) nature.

The strategy for ensuring the reliability of results implies a pre-validation of the validation platform and is visually represented in the figure below. The four main elements in the figure are: 1) “physical before” (the data collected from test sites without the DRiVE solution operating, i.e. historic data), 2) “physical after” (the data collected from test sites with the DRiVE solution operating), 3) “virtual before” (the validation platform simulation/emulating test sites without the DRiVE solution operating, based on historical data) and 4) “virtual after” (the validation platform simulating/emulating test sites with the DRiVE solution operating).

The main strategy in ensuring the reliability of the validation platform is what may be termed “self-validation”, i.e. the validation of the validation platform itself (depicted in the figure as Step 1). In this step, the validation platform is, traditionally speaking, “the device under test” and the reliability is achieved when the simulation/emulation data fully matches the historic data from test sites. It should be noted that “full matching” does not imply an absolute match between the simulation/emulation data and historic data, but a match where differences between the “physical before” and “virtual before”

datasets are not statistically significant at a confidence level of 95% or more (ideally, 99%). This “self-validation” ensures that the addition of the DRIVe to the validation platform does not jeopardize the fidelity and reliability of the simulation/emulation. In the simplest terms, this implies that any differences in the results, when the DRIVe solution is performing optimizations, do indeed represent the result of the actual DRIVe logic and communication layer.

Towards the end of the project, the “self-validation” can be extended with “benchmarking”. This is shown in the figure below as Step 2. This step implies the comparison of the data obtained in physical testing of the DRIVe solution (“physical after”) and the data obtained in the validation platform when it was fed the control messages, forecasting data and other relevant data recorded during the corresponding physical test (“virtual after” but based on the data from “physical after”, not on historical data). Step 2 should, by the end of the project, provide datasets where differences are not statistically significant at a confidence level of 95% or more. This way, the validation platform can be used to develop further test scenarios using the models of test sites beyond the duration of the project, and can be also used to demonstrate the DRIVe system, both in the dissemination events and in the post-project phase, to decisionmakers and stakeholders in an interactive way (e.g. instead of waiting for a congestion point to appear in a physical system, it is possible to insert a congestion point scenario into the real-time model and show how the DRIVe multi-agent system provides congestion management, while guaranteeing that the behaviour of the simulated/emulated system matches the behaviour of the physical system).

Figure 24: High-level strategies for validating models and ensuring the reliability of the results

6 CONCLUSION

In order to start implementing testing and validation activities of the DRIVe solution during the second year of the project, it is necessary to define the validation scenarios which will be used to validate that the DRIVe solution is operating as designed, as well as to measure its benefits and to assess its upgrades of the state of the art. This document serves this purpose by 1) identifying and describing use cases and validation scenarios for each type of the service, and 2) defining key performance indicators for each validation scenario. Additionally, the document also outlines the general, tentative timeline of the validation activities, as well as the general architecture of the validation platform which will be fully specified and subsequent reports, i.e. deliverables, from WP7.

This document presents the specific KPIs which were devised for the validation of the DRIVe solution and which are applicable during both the testing and operational phase. As such, the contents of this document is intended to represent a specification from which WP7 can first develop a validation platform and, afterwards, conduct validation activities.

A total of 47 different KPIs have been identified as essential for validating the DRIVe solution. Of the 47, the majority of KPIs (43) are devised for the 10 scenarios (e.g. ToU, kWmax, etc.) within the 5 main services provided by the DRIVe solution (in-building optimization, community services, flexibility services for the BRP, flexibility services for the DSO and flexibility services for the TSO). The remaining 4 KPIs were devised to address the cyber security provisions of the DRIVe solution: these KPIs are not scenario-specific, but apply to all scenarios and all services provided by the DRIVe platform. All KPIs have been designed in a way which makes it possible to implement them in the cloud, for the overarching aim of them being accessible by means of the web-based interface.

Additionally, the tentative validation timeline for conducting validation activities was also defined. The validation timeline identifies the modes and duration of validation which will be used to validate each service at each test site. This part of the document also contains a concise, general overview of the strategies which will be used for ensuring the reliability of the results. Lastly, the summaries of data capabilities of pilot site, KPIs, use case actors and use case requirements are provided in the Annexes, which, taken together, should provide the specification for devising a suitable validation platform.

While it is expected that much of the KPIs and validation scenarios devised and identified in this deliverable will be used without any modifications in the actual validation and operation stage, it is possible that, through development of the DRIVe project and development of the validation platform itself, additional KPIs and validation scenarios will be identified, or that the existing KPIs and validation scenarios will have to be modified. Should this be the case, all additional needs and/or modification identified will be properly addressed in future reports, i.e. deliverables.

7 REFERENCES

- [1] “ISO/IEC/IEEE International Standard - Systems and software engineering – Vocabulary,” ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765:2010(E), pp. 1–418, Dec. 2010.
- [2] Wattalyst FP7 Consortium, “Wattalyst,” *WATTALYST*, 19-Sep-2013. [Online]. Available: <https://web.archive.org/web/20130919105038/http://www.wattalyst.org:80/WattalystWebsite/index.html>. [Accessed: 19-Mar-2018].
- [3] G. Thanos *et al.*, “Evaluating demand response programs by means of key performance indicators,” in *Communication Systems and Networks (COMSNETS), 2013 Fifth International Conference on*, 2013, pp. 1–6.
- [4] S3C Consortium, “GUIDELINE: KPIS FOR ENERGY CONSUMPTION EFFECTS.” [Online]. Available: http://www.smartgrid-engagement-toolkit.eu/fileadmin/s3ctoolkit/user/guidelines/guideline_kpis_for_energy_consumption_effects.pdf. [Accessed: 19-Mar-2018].
- [5] EDSO for Smart Grids, “Flexibility: The role of DSOs in tomorrow’s electricity market” [Online]. Available: [Accessed: 21-Mar-2018].
- [6] M. Glowacki, “Frequency Containment Reserve (FCR) : European Union Electricity Market Glossary.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.emissions-euets.com/internal-electricity-market-glossary/793-frequency-containment-reserve>. [Accessed: 25-Mar-2018].
- [7] M. Glowacki, “Frequency Restoration Reserve (FRR) : European Union Electricity Market Glossary.” [Online]. Available: <https://www.emissions-euets.com/internal-electricity-market-glossary/794-frequency-restoration-reserve-frr>. [Accessed: 25-Mar-2018].
- [8] H. Gerard, E. Rivero and D. Six, “Basic schemes for TSO-DSO coordination and ancillary services provision” [Online]. Available: http://smartnet-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/12/D1.3_20161202_V1.0.pdf. [Accessed: 11-July-2018].
- [9] USEF—Universal Smart Energy Framework.”USEF: the framework explained,” *USEF*, 18-Nov-2015. [Online]. Available: http://www.globalsmartgridfederation.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/USEF_TheFrameworkExplained-18nov15.pdf. [Accessed: 28-Oct-2018].

Annex B KPIs devised for validation of DRivE services

The table below summarizes all key performance indicators (KPIs) devised to assess and validate the performance of DRivE services. The KPIs are sorted according to the type of services which they pertain to:

- ToU – Time of Use Optimization,
- kWmax – Kilowatt Max Control, Consumer Portal,
- NRGCoin - Smart Community Based on NRGcoin Market Principles,
- PM – Portfolio Management,
- CM – Congestion management,
- VC – Voltage Control,
- PQS – Power Quality Support,
- FCR – Frequency Containment Reserve,
- FRR – Frequency Restoration Reserve, and
- CY5 – Cyber Security Provisions (CY5 is not a use case, but is relevant to all use cases)

<i>Key performance indicators</i>				
<i>ID</i>	<i>Name</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Reference to mentioned use case objectives</i>	<i>Use Case</i>
tou_kpi_01	Energy Bill Savings	The total energy bill savings (in euros) will be calculated using the actual billing method used at the considered sites. Therefore, the equation for this KPI is entirely dependent on the site's contract with their energy supplier. In cases where kWmax is also considered (such as COMSA), this KPI can be summed with the kwmax_kpi_01 in order to optimise the energy bill as a whole.	Objective: Minimize energy consumption costs (D2.3 Table 3)	ToU
tou_kpi_02	Occupant Comfort	Temperature must remain within an acceptable range as defined by the building manager (also considering the occupancy schedule). This can be quantified by measuring the % of time that the temperature is outside of the acceptable range, with 0% representing optimum performance. $\% \text{ Time Outside Range} = \frac{(Hou + Huu)}{8760h}$ where Hou is the total number of hours during the time the building is occupied annually where temperature inside the building is outside the threshold set by the building manager, and Huu is the total number of hours during the unoccupied period where temperature inside the building is outside the building manager threshold. Temperature can represent the real temperature or a "heat index" temperature (temperature adjusted to account for relative humidity), depending on the definition agreed by the building manager.	Objective: Maintain indoor comfort (D2.3 Table 3)	ToU
kwmax_kpi_01	Energy Bill Savings	The total energy bill savings (in euros) will be calculated using the actual billing method used at the considered sites. Therefore, the equation for this KPI is entirely dependent on the site's contract with their energy supplier. In cases where ToU is also considered (such as COMSA), this KPI can be summed with the tou_kpi_01 in order to optimise the energy bill as a whole.	Objective: Minimize power demand costs (D2.3 Table 3)	kWmax

kwmax_kpi_02	Occupant Comfort	<p>Temperature must remain within an acceptable range as defined by the building manager (also considering the occupancy schedule). This can be quantified by measuring the % of time that the temperature is outside of the acceptable range, with 0% representing optimum performance.</p> $\% \text{ Time Outside Range} = \frac{(Hou + Huu)}{8760h}$ <p>where Hou is the total number of hours during the time the building is occupied annually where temperature inside the building is outside the threshold set by the building manager, and Huu is the total number of hours during the unoccupied period where temperature inside the building is outside the building manager threshold. Temperature can represent the real temperature or a “heat index” temperature (temperature adjusted to account for relative humidity), depending on the definition agreed by the building manager.</p>	Objective: Maintain indoor comfort (D2.3 Table 3)	kWmax
kw_kpi_03	Max kW demand in considered period	<p>While in many cases this value will be a necessary input to the calculation of kwmax_kpi_01, it is important to track this value separately. The exact definition of the considered period depends on the site’s contract with their energy supplier. Examples of possible considerations include, but are not limited to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Billing periods dependant on the time of day - Billing periods dependant on the time of year <p>The time period or schedule over which kW demanded should be averaged to determine the max kW demand.</p>	Objective: Minimize power demand costs (D2.3 Table 3)	kWmax
cp_kpi_01	Consumer Portal implementation	Number of test sites for which a consumer portal is implemented vs where it is planned.	<p>Objective 1</p> <p>The target is 1-5 (of the objectives identified in the text preceding the table)</p>	Consumer Portal
cp_kpi_02	Documented Access rule settings	For each pilot the relevant actors are defined, and it is documented to which data they should have access. The access rule settings should be GDPR compliant and reviewed by the relevant stakeholders.	<p>Objective 2</p> <p>The target is 1-5 (of the objectives identified in the text preceding the table)</p>	Consumer Portal
cp_kpi_03	Individual portal for the residents	For each resident in a residential pilot, an individual portal exists for representation of user relevant performance data and interactive setting of user configurations	<p>Objective 3</p> <p>Target = 95%</p>	Consumer Portal
cp_kpi_04	Local terminal implementation	A local terminal “smart thermostat” is implemented, specifically designed to allow interactive communication with the residents in the DRiVE context (DEVO pilot for NRGcoin , Woerden for automatic optimisation)	<p>Objective 3</p> <p>Target = 90 % of the planned local terminals are operational</p>	Consumer Portal
cp_kpi_05	Individual portal usage	The usage of the individual portals either local or web based is tracked	Objective 3	Consumer Portal
cp_kpi_05w		# of interactions per user and per month.	Target:	

Web cp_kpi_051 Local			cp_kpi_051 > 2* cp_kpi_05w	
cp_kpi_06	Portal user satisfaction	For all the stakeholder portals user satisfaction data is collected Remarks are used to steer the roadmap	Objective 3 Target cp_kpi_06a = 80% of stakeholders is reached Target cp_kpi_06b = 70% of the stakeholders is either satisfied or neutral in their judgement	Consumer Portal
cp_kpi_07	GDPR compliant user interactivity	For all residents of the DRIVE residential pilots GDPR compliant user interactivity is implemented and available either via website or via a local terminal	Objective 4 Target cp_kpi_07 = available for 100% of the relevant residents.	Consumer Portal
cp_kpi_08	Customer portal for external systems	For all the external systems requiring automatic access a website is foreseen for the operator of such a system giving insight in the performance of the relevant services and the operational status of remote data access	Objective 5 cp_kpi_08a Target = 100% external systems have a website cp_kpi_08b Target = 99% availability of the interfaces toward the external services	Consumer Portal
cp_kpi_09	Energy savings nudging	For each pilot having a local objective to save energy an individual webpage or a local terminal should give insight in the energy usage and give advice (nudging) to the end users in order to save energy or energy cost	cp_kpi_09. Target 100% of relevant residential users reached	Consumer Portal
cp_kpi_10	Energy savings nudging effectivity	For each relevant user the effectivity of the “nudging” should be monitored by comparing the actual savings of the “nudged” users with a control group.	cp_kpi_09 Target = X% of energy (cost) savings increase due to nudging	Consumer Portal
cs_kpi_01	Consumer cost savings via manual optimisation	Difference of the annual bill under NRG coin and that of a baseline mechanism in % The optimisation of cost savings is done via manual control of the end user	Objective 1	NRGcoin
cs_kpi_02	Consumer cost savings via automatic optimisation	Difference of the annual bill under NRG coin and that of a baseline mechanism in % The optimisation of cost savings is done via automatic control of	Objective 1	NRGcoin

		the end user loads and energy production.		
cs_kpi_03	Community RES self-consumption Baseline	Locally produced renewable energy that is instantly consumed by the local community in % and in absolute value for a baseline scenario	Objective 2	NRGcoin
cs_kpi_04	Community RES self-consumption Manual optimisation	Locally produced renewable, energy that is instantly consumed by the local community in % and in absolute value when the users have manual control of the deferrable loads	Objective 2	NRGcoin
cs_kpi_05	Community RES self-consumption Automatic optimisation	Locally produced renewable energy that is instantly consumed by the local community in % and in absolute value when the aggregator controls deferrable and other controllable load	Objective 2	NRGcoin
cs_kpi_06	Flexibility provision accuracy In %	We will measure the ratio in % between the offered flexibility and the delivered flexibility	Avoid congestion	NRGcoin
pm_kpi_01	Portfolio management spot market performance	When flexibility is being used to optimize the load profile of an asset on the SPOT market, it combines the normal forecast of the load with a forecast of the SPOT prices. $\sum_{n=1 \dots 96} Forecast_{original} Price_{SPOT} - Forecast_{adjusted} Price_{SPOT}$ $S.T. \sum Forecast_{original} = Forecast_{adjusted}$	This KPI references the following objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reduce sourcing costs 	PM
pm_kpi_02	Portfolio management imbalance market performance	When flexibility is being used to optimize the load profile of an asset on the imbalance market, the asset reacts directly to the imbalance price signal. $\sum_{n=1 \dots 96} (Allocation_{original} - Forecast) Price_{Imbalance}$ $- \sum_{n=1 \dots 96} (Allocation_{adjusted} - Forecast) Price_{Imbalance}$	This KPI references the following objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • lower risk to high imbalance costs • lower imbalance costs or increase imbalance revenue 	PM
cm_kpi_01	Solar production Forecast accuracy day ahead	In the USEF day ahead cycle for DSO's a forecast needs to be made of the electrical energy production and consumption at the site. For this KPI we will measure the solar forecast accuracy comparing the one sent in for the last flex offer, with the real data at operation time. We will compare and benchmark this figure with free online tools as offered by weather services. To be repeated for each relevant pilot	Avoid congestion	CM
cm_kpi_02	Load Forecast accuracy day ahead	In the USEF day ahead cycle for DSO's a forecast needs to be made of the electrical energy production and consumption at the site. For this KPI we will measure the electrical consumption forecast accuracy comparing the one sent in for the last flex offer, with the real data at operation time. We will compare and benchmark this figure with free online tools as offered by weather services. To be repeated for each relevant pilot	Avoid congestion	CM
cm_kpi_03	Solar production Forecast intraday	In the USEF day ahead cycle for DSO's a forecast needs to be made of the electrical energy production and consumption at the site. For this KPI we will measure the solar forecast accuracy comparing the one sent in for the last flex offer, with the real data at operation time.	Avoid congestion	CM

		<p>We will compare and benchmark this figure with free online tools as offered by weather services.</p> <p>To be repeated for each relevant pilot</p>		
cm_kpi_04	Load Forecast accuracy intraday	<p>In the USEF day ahead cycle for DSO's a forecast needs to be made of the electrical energy production and consumption at the site. For this KPI we will measure the electrical consumption forecast accuracy comparing the one sent in for the last flex offer, with the real data at operation time.</p> <p>We will compare and benchmark this figure with free online tools as offered by weather services.</p> <p>To be repeated for each relevant pilot</p> <p>Accuracy to be measured for a set of 52 PTU's</p>	Avoid congestion	CM
cm_kpi_05	Time for plan A	We will measure the time it takes for the USEF end -to-end chain to provide an initial D-prog after the receipt of the request for D-prog from the aggregator	Avoid congestion	CM
cm_kpi_06	Time from Flex request to flex offer	We will measure the time it takes for the USEF end -to-end chain to provide a flex offer after the receipt of the flex request as issued by the DSO	Avoid congestion	CM
cm_kpi_07	Flexibility provision accuracy In %	We will measure the ratio in % between the offered flexibility and the delivered flexibility	Avoid congestion	CM
cm_kpi_08	Number of outages/ months	<p>We will count the number of outages which would occur if the virtual boundary as set by the DSO would be breached</p> <p>Target = 0</p>	Avoid congestion	CM
cm_kpi_09	Prosumer comfort	<p>Depending on the kind of flexible elements in the demonstrator we will define comfort parameters for the end user/prosumer. We will measure or count comfort breaches as occurring due to the optimisation</p> <p>The minimum set is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of cases where significant cold water at the outflow was detected <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ cold=< 45°c ○ Very cold=<40° • % volume of cold water <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ cold =<45°c ○ Very cold=<40°C • Differences with control group to be assessed 	Prosumer comfort	CM
cm_kpi_10	Volume of offered flexibility	<p>Over a period of at least 2 summer months and 2 winter months (preferably a whole year) , the validator will test how much flexibility was delivered to the DSO in kWh/day,</p> <p>this KPI will be split up over the flexible elements in the congestion points</p>	Avoid congestion	CM
vc_kpi_01	Voltage variation	This KPI measures the difference between the actual voltage that aggregated devices are supplying to either the LV or MV network and the aggregator's reference value set for the activation of voltage control service. This KPI is measured in percent and it should be as close to 0 as possible.	This KPI references the following objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contribute on voltage regulation for distribution systems • defer investments in 	VC

		$kpi_{voltageVariation} = \frac{V_{measured} - V_{ref}}{V_{ref}}$	<p>infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DERs to make it more attractive economically 	
vc_kpi_02	Voltage control activation and ramp-up time	<p>The activation time and ramp-up (<i>actRampTVC</i>) time for voltage control should be under 5 seconds. Ideally, this should be as close to 0 as possible, while the scenario can be considered successful as long as the KPI is lower or equal to 1. The scenario should be deemed a fail if the KPI is more than 1. It should be noted that only battery storage systems can provide ramp-up times that would satisfy this KPI: for combined power and heating plants (and spinning reserves), the time constant should be longer than 5s.</p> $kpi_{actRampTVC} = \frac{activation\ time_{seconds}}{5\ s}$	<p>This KPI references the following objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contribute on voltage regulation for distribution systems • defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement) • create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DERs to make it more attractive economically 	VC
pqs_kpi_01	THD correction	<p>Voltage total harmonic distortion at the measuring point within the scope of the aggregator's control should be $\leq 8\%$ at all times. This KPI is the ratio of time when THD was over the limit and the time when THD was within the permissible limits: ideally it should be close to 0.</p> $kpi_{thdratio} = \frac{t\ (THD_{over})}{t\ (THD_{within})}$	<p>This KPI references the following objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contribute to power quality support in the distribution systems • defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement) 	PQS
pqs_kpi_02	Power factor correction	<p>Power factor within the scope of the aggregator's control should be ≥ 0.95 at all times. This KPI is the ratio of time when power factor was over the limit and the time when power factor was within the permissible limits: ideally it should be close to 0.</p> $kpi_{PFratio} = \frac{t\ (PF_{under95})}{t\ (PF_{over95})}$	<p>This KPI references the following objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contribute to power quality support in the distribution systems • defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement) 	PQS
fcr_kpi_01	Operating frequency containment reserves	<p>The aggregator's planned operating reserves (<i>opR</i>) for frequency containment reserve should correspond to the frequency containment reserves available during the operate phase. Ideally, this KPI should be 1, where in suboptimal cases it is lower than 1.</p> $kpi_{opR} = \frac{operating\ reserves_{actual}}{operating\ reserves_{planned}}$	<p>The KPI references the following objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contribute to frequency containment reserve for distribution system • defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement) 	FCR

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DERs to make it more attractive economically 	
fcr_kpi_02	Frequency containment reserve activation time	<p>The activation time and ramp-up time (acT) for frequency containment reserve should be under 30 seconds. Ideally, this should be as close to 0 as possible, while the scenario can be considered successful as long as the KPI is lower or equal to 1. The scenario should be deemed a fail if the KPI is more than 1.</p> $kpi_{actTFCR} = \frac{activation\ time_{seconds}}{30\ s}$	<p>The KPI references the following objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contribute to frequency containment reserve for distribution system • defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement) • create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DERs to make it more attractive economically 	FCR
frr_kpi_01	Active power reserves for frequency restoration	<p>The aggregator's planned active power reserves (apR) for frequency restoration reserve should correspond to the frequency containment reserves available during the operate phase. Ideally, this KPI should be 1, where in suboptimal cases it is lower than 1.</p> $kpi_{apR} = \frac{operating\ reserves_{actual}}{operating\ reserves_{planned}}$	<p>The KPI references the following objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contribute to frequency restoration reserve for distribution system • defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement) • create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DERs to make it more attractive economically 	FRR
frr_kpi_02	Frequency restoration reserve activation time	<p>The activation time and ramp-up time ($actFRR$) for frequency restoration reserve should be between for frequency restoration reserve should be under between 30 seconds and 15 minutes. Ideally, this should be as close to 0 as possible, while the scenario can be considered successful as long as the KPI is lower or equal to 1. The scenario should be deemed a fail if the KPI is more than 1.</p> $kpi_{actTFRR} = \frac{activation\ time_{seconds}}{900\ s}$	<p>The KPI references the following objective:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • contribute to frequency restoration reserve for distribution system • defer investments in infrastructure (grid control equipment, grid reinforcement) • create new revenue sources and business opportunities for DERs to make it 	FRR

			more attractive economically	
cys_kpi_01	Forecast correlation	This KPIs assess the system capability to first identify inconsistencies between the cloud backend and embedded forecast and then to trigger an alarm to the investigation capacity. Cys_kpi_01 is defined as the reaction time. time to trigger an alarm < 1 minute (after the problem in forecast is detected)	N/A (cyber security is not a separate use case, but a protective layer which will be developed to provide cyber security to all services described in other use cases)	CYS
cys_kpi_02	AMQP message queue intrusion	This KPIs assess the system capability to detect any intrusion into the AMQP message queue between the local energy gateway and the Enervalis backend and to revoke the local energy gateway. Cys_kpi_02 is defined as the reaction time. time to revoke the LEG < 1 minute (after the AMQP message queue intrusion is detected)	N/A (cyber security is not a separate use case, but a protective layer which will be developed to provide cyber security to all services described in other use cases)	CYS
cys_kpi_03	Malicious firmware upload attempt	This KPIs assess the system capability to first detect an attempt to overwrite or modify the firmware of the local energy gateway and then to revoke the local energy gateway. Cys_kpi_03 is defined as the reaction time. time to revoke the LEG < 1 minute (after the firmware upload/modification is detected)	N/A (cyber security is not a separate use case, but a protective layer which will be developed to provide cyber security to all services described in other use cases)	CYS
cys_kpi_04	Unauthorized access to HMI	This KPIs assess the system capability to first detect an unauthorized access to HMI provided by the Enervalis cloud-based backend and then to trigger an alarm. Cys_kpi_04 is defined as the reaction time. time to trigger an alarm < 1 minute (after the unauthorize HMI access is detected)	N/A (cyber security is not a separate use case, but a protective layer which will be developed to provide cyber security to all services described in other use cases)	CYS

Annex C A Unified List of Use Case Actors

This appendix contains the unified list of actors which will be involved in the six main use cases/validation scenarios of the DRiVE system, as well as in twelve subtypes of use cases/validation scenarios contained in them.

The table uses the following acronyms to identify the use cases/validation scenarios:

- ToU = Time-of-Use Optimization,
- kWmax = kWmax optimization,
- CustPort = Consumer Portal,
- CustPortalEnSave = Consumer Portal Energy Saving,
- CommunMngmt = Community Management,
- PortfolioMngmnt = Portfolio Management,
- CongMngmnt = Congestion Management,
- VoltCont = Voltage Control,
- PQS = Power Quality Support,
- FCR = Frequency Containment Reserve,
- FRR = Frequency Restoration Reserve

Table 49: A unified list of 22 actors that play a role in Use Case scenarios

1	Actor Name:	DRiVE		
	Actor Type	System	Actor Group	DRiVE platform
	Actor Description:	Collecting relevant unit operation/consumption information, environmental data, and tariff information, solve the optimization and/or control problem, and send the optimal schedules/signals to the building via LEG		
	Further Information:	Relevant communication interface		
	Use Cases:	ToU, kWmax, VoltCont		
	Actor ID:	act_drive		
2	Actor Name:	Mitsubishi HVAC system		
	Actor Type	Device	Actor Group	HVAC Units
	Actor Description:	77 HVAC indoor units. Each one of them is controllable independently. Control parameters are: (1) Temp. set-point and (2) on-off status. Also 10 outdoor units exist, but they automatically meet indoor units needs, so they need no consideration in this use case.		
	Further Information:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Although control granularity is on a unit-by-unit basis, consumption measurement granularity is on a floor-by-floor basis. • Consumption measurement should be available through Modbus TCP and HVAC units through Modbus RS-485. 		
	Use Cases:	ToU, kWmax		
	Actor ID:	act_comsa_hvac		
3	Actor Name:	Battery		
	Actor Type	Device	Actor Group	Storage Battery
	Actor Description:	Additional information to be defined if final contract regarding battery is signed. In any case the charge or discharge rate of the current will probably be the only control parameter.		
	Further Information:	Should be available via Modbus RS-485.		
	Use Cases:	ToU, kWmax		
	Actor ID:	act_comsa_batt		

4	Actor Name:	Building energy management systems (BEMS)		
	Actor Type	Device	Actor Group	In-building Control Components
	Actor Description:	Monitors energy consumption, weather conditions and state of charge of battery units within the building and sends signals to controllable assets.		
	Further Information:	Monitors energy consumption, weather conditions and state of charge of battery units within the building and sends signals to controllable assets.		
	Use Cases:	ToU, kWmax		
	Actor ID:	act_comsa_bems		
5	Actor Name:	Energy controller		
	Actor Type	Device	Actor Group	In-building Control Components
	Actor Description:	Local energy control systems, such as room level HVAC control (i.e. thermostats)		
	Further Information:	none		
	Use Cases:	ToU, kWmax		
	Actor ID:	act_comsa_encon		
6	Actor Name:	Local Energy Gateway		
	Actor Type	Device	Actor Group	In-building Control Components
	Actor Description:	Act as bridge between the building EMS and the DRiVE solution, to send and receive information/control signals between DRiVE solution and building controller/EMS.		
	Further Information:	Relevant communication interface.		
	Use Cases:	ToU, kWmax		
	Actor ID:	act_comsa_leg		
7	Actor Name:	BRP		
	Actor Type	Market Party	Actor Group	Market parties
	Actor Description:	Balance responsible party		
	Further Information:	Overview of grouped data (consumptions, productions and logging)		
	Use Cases:	CustPortal, PortfolioMngmnt		
	Actor ID:	act_brp		
8	Actor Name:	TSO		
	Actor Type	System Operator	Actor Group	Market parties
	Actor Description:	Responsible for the grid transmission (for FCR): Request frequency containment reserve services from demand response resource or aggregator.		
	Further Information:	Overview of specific data		
	Use Cases:	CustPortal, PortfolioMngmnt, FCR, FRR		
	Actor ID:	act_tso		
9	Actor Name:	Resident		
	Actor Type	Market Party	Actor Group	Market parties
	Actor Description:	The resident is the consumer/prosumer of an individual house/asset.		
	Further Information:	Overview of local house consumption/production		
	Use Cases:	CustPortal, CustPortalEnSave		
	Actor ID:	act_resident		
10	Actor Name:	Group Manager		
	Actor Type	Market Party	Actor Group	Market parties
	Actor Description:	Responsible for an individual asset group which can produce and or consume. Example a building manager responsible, site manager		
	Further Information:	Overview and interaction with the local data		
	Use Cases:	CustPortal		
	Actor ID:	act_grpmngr		
11	Actor Name:	Smart Power Suite		

	Actor Type	Device	Actor Group	M2M Interfaces
	Actor Description:	Decentralized communication hub capable of communicating with local deployed devices (as a gateway application for PortfolioMngmnt): Communicates with management system of the asset and gathers inputs for composing steering signal		
	Further Information:	Sends and receives all local information needed.		
	Use Cases:	CustPortal, CustPortalEnSave, PortfolioMngmnt		
	Actor ID:	act_sps		
12	Actor Name:	External System		
	Actor Type	Interface	Actor Group	M2M Interfaces
	Actor Description:	Responsible for actively interacting with the consumer portal		
	Further Information:	Uses external standards to communicate or the REST API		
	Use Cases:	CustPortal		
	Actor ID:	act_extsys		
13	Actor Name:	(Local) AGR		
	Actor Type	System	Actor Group	Market parties
	Actor Description:	Local aggregator		
	Further Information:	Unlike traditional AGR who is a standardised figure operating at market level, this use case deals with a local aggregator, an actor that performs the aggregation at district/community level and for which a clear legislation still not exists.		
	Use Cases:	CommunMngmnt		
	Actor ID:	act_localagr		
14	Actor Name:	Prosumer		
	Actor Type	Device	Actor Group	Market parties
	Actor Description:	This use case will be residential so the prosumer will make reference to a residential end user.		
	Further Information:	This use case will be residential so the prosumer will make reference to a residential end user.		
	Use Cases:	CommunMngmnt, CongMngmnt		
	Actor ID:	act_prosumer		
15	Actor Name:	Active Demand & Supply		
	Actor Type	Component	Actor Group	Process/Field/Station actors
	Actor Description:	Represents all types of systems that either demand energy or supply energy and which can be actively controlled.		
	Further Information:	none		
	Use Cases:	CommunMngmnt		
	Actor ID:	act_ads		
16	Actor Name:	Asset Management System		
	Actor Type	Device	Actor Group	Gateways
	Actor Description:	Each asset needs its own asset management system that converts the steering signal to a control action in the asset. (for VoltCont): Implement power changes (controlling the underlying assets) upon requests. (for FCR and FRR): Implements the accorded power-frequency relation for the Frequency Containment Reserve, acting on the energy resources available to fulfil the service to the TSO.		
	Further Information:	none		
	Use Cases:	PortfolioMngmnt, VoltCont, FCR, FRR		
	Actor ID:	act_ams		
17	Actor Name:	DSO		

	Actor Type	Market Party	Actor Group	Market parties
	Actor Description:	The DSO is responsible for the active management of the distribution grid and introduces the system operation services defined in the USEF flexibility value chain. The DSO is responsible for the cost-effective distribution of energy while maintaining grid stability in a given region. (for VoltCont): Responsible for the distribution grid		
	Further Information:	The DSO can temporarily overrule the market to prevent a complete power outage. In doing so, it differentiates between clients who critically depend on energy and those where a service interruption has a lesser impact.		
	Use Cases:	CongMngmnt, VoltCont		
	Actor ID:	act_dso		
18	Actor Name:	Aggregator		
	Actor Type	Organisation	Actor Group	Market parties
	Actor Description:	The DSO is responsible for the active management of the distribution grid and introduces the system operation services defined in the USEF flexibility value chain. The DSO is responsible for the cost-effective distribution of energy while maintaining grid stability in a given region. (for VoltCont): Responsible for the aggregation of the available DR resources (for FCR and FRR): Presents itself as a single service provider for the TSO, virtually owning the operation of all underlying assets.		
	Further Information:	The DSO can temporarily overrule the market to prevent a complete power outage. In doing so, it differentiates between clients who critically depend on energy and those where a service interruption has a lesser impact. (for VoltCont): Uses DRiVE aggregator platform to operate on the flexibility market and to provide fast demand response to DSO		
	Use Cases:	CongMngmnt, VoltCont, FCR, FRR		
	Actor ID:	act_agr		
19	Actor Name:	DMS		
	Actor Type	Device	Actor Group	Gateways
	Actor Description:	System for monitoring distribution grid condition and acting on field equipment, possibly optimizing control actions.		
	Further Information:	Interacts with DRiVE platform by receiving measurements, forecasts and flexibility available on the defined congestion points.		
	Use Cases:	VoltCont		
	Actor ID:	act_dms		
20	Actor Name:	Asset Owner		
	Actor Type	Asset Owner	Actor Group	Market parties
	Actor Description:	Agrees with participation on power change requests (for FCR and FRR): Agrees with participation on frequency reserve services.		
	Further Information:	none		
	Use Cases:	VoltCont, FCR, FRR		
	Actor ID:	act_asstownr		
21	Actor Name:	Smart Inverter		
	Actor Type	Device	Actor Group	Device
	Actor Description:	Equipment that could contain specific power quality functions		
	Further Information:	none		
	Use Cases:	PQS		
	Actor ID:	act_smartinv		
22	Actor Name:	Smart Energy Device		
	Actor Type	Device	Actor Group	Device
	Actor Description:	Smart energy devices that include power-frequency functions could autonomously implement the frequency reserve services.		
	Further Information:	none		

	Use Cases:	FCR, FRR
	Actor ID:	act_smarted

Annex D A Unified List of Use Case Requirements

This appendix contains the unified list of requirements which were identified for each use case in D2.3. These requirements will be used in subsequent reports on validation activities in line with scenarios described in this document. The requirements are groups into 1) general, technical requirements relevant for the DRiVE solution, and 2) requirements specific to each site.

Table 50: A unified list of technical requirements for Use Case scenarios

Forecasting engine	
ID	Description
req_tec_forecast_1	Computational power where the minimum of computational power needed for the prediction algorithms is 0.05 GFLOPS (GFLOPS - a billion floating point operations per second)
req_tec_forecast_2	Execution time where the minimum of Execution time needed for the prediction algorithms is 1 sec
req_tec_forecast_3	Renewable energy and energy demand shall be accurately forecasted as inputs to the optimization model.
req_tec_forecast_4	The demand forecast should take into account the historical demand profiles
req_tec_forecast_5	The renewable energy forecast should take into account the historical weather conditions
req_tec_forecast_6	Forecasts for both demand and renewables should take into account weekly/ seasonal effects.
Building model predictive control	
ID	Description
req_tec_bmpc_1	Money shall be saved by using the MPC
req_tec_bmpc_2	Optimization shall take into account building thermal inertia to maximize energy flexibility
req_tec_bmpc_3	Optimization shall take into account the indoor and outdoor environmental conditions
req_tec_bmpc_4	Optimization shall take into account the energy production and consumption forecast
req_tec_bmpc_5	Optimization shall take into account occupancy patterns
req_tec_bmpc_6	Optimization shall respect thermal comfort constraints
req_tec_bmpc_7	Optimization shall respect devices' operational constraints
Advanced building DR optimisation	
ID	Description
req_tec_bdr_1	There should be controllable devices providing source of flexibility
req_tec_bdr_2	Requested consumption profiles for appliances should provide the source of flexibility.
req_tec_bdr_3	Supplier tariffs should provide incentives for the prosumer to change its consumption behaviour.
req_tec_bdr_4	The forecasted values of the energy produced by renewable sources should provide accurate estimates.
req_tec_bdr_5	The power consumption profiles resulting from optimization should meet the specification of appliances.

req_tec_bdr_6	The consumption profiles resulting from optimization should meet the prosumer's preferences.
req_tec_bdr_7	The energy bill resulting from optimization should bring benefits for the prosumer.
Implicit DR protocols for community energy management	
ID	Description
req_tec_imcommgmt_1	The DR system should include controllable devices providing the source of flexibility.
req_tec_imcommgmt_2	Requested power consumption profiles for appliances within the DR system should provide the source of flexibility.
req_tec_imcommgmt_3	The supplier tariffs should provide incentives for the prosumers.
req_tec_imcommgmt_4	The forecasted values of the energy produced by renewable sources should provide accurate estimates.
req_tec_imcommgmt_5	The power consumption profiles resulting from optimization should meet the specification of appliances.
req_tec_imcommgmt_6	The consumption profiles resulting from optimization should meet the prosumer's preferences.
req_tec_imcommgmt_7	The energy bills resulting from optimization should bring benefits for the prosumers involved in the DR program.
req_tec_imcommgmt_8	The aggregator should acquire the flexibility of the prosumers involved in the DR program.
Explicit DR protocols for community energy management	
ID	Description
req_tec_excommgmt_1	The DR system should include controllable devices providing the source of flexibility.
req_tec_excommgmt_2	Requested power consumption profiles for appliances within the DR system should provide the source of flexibility.
req_tec_excommgmt_3	The supplier tariffs should provide incentives for the prosumers.
req_tec_excommgmt_4	The forecasted values of the energy produced by renewable sources should provide accurate estimates.
req_tec_excommgmt_5	The power consumption profiles resulting from optimization should meet the specification of appliances.
req_tec_excommgmt_6	The consumption profiles resulting from optimization should meet the prosumer's preferences.
req_tec_excommgmt_7	The prosumers should benefit from participating in the explicit DR program.
req_tec_excommgmt_8	The explicit demand response request should be satisfied.
Real-time explicit DR protocols for community energy management	
ID	Description
req_tec_rtcommgmt_1	The DR system should include controllable assets capable of real-time explicit demand response
req_tec_rtcommgmt_2	Requested power consumption profiles for appliances within the DR system should provide the source of flexibility.

Table 51: A unified list of pilot-site requirements for Use Case scenarios

Blaneau Gwent district	
ID	Description

req_ps_bgcbc_01	The DRiVE platform (REEFS to be more specific) should be able to get access to historical data of consumption/generation/environment/social-economic of each building for forecasting needs. It should be noted that an offline simulation-based method will be adopted for BGCBC site due to the time scales of simulation runtimes.
req_ps_bgcbc_02	The DRiVE platform should be able to get access to detailed information of some key building assets such as the combined heat and power (CHP).
req_ps_bgcbc_03	The DRiVE platform should be able to get access to the maximum load penalty tariff from DSO.
req_ps_bgcbc_04	The DRiVE platform should be able to get the ToU tariff information from local energy supplier.
DEVO district	
ID	Description
req_ps_devo_1	DRiVE shall directly control the heat network production assets via a Smartpower Suite Energy gateway, which in turn is connected to the « Heat Network Building Management System » (HN-BMS) which currently controls and extracts data from the heat network.
req_ps_devo_2	DRiVE shall directly control possible future flexible assets in residential buildings extensions (battery storage, EV as controllable loads, controllable solar inverters).
req_ps_devo_3	The above-mentioned appliances shall participate to the flexibility which will be exposed on the day-ahead/imbalance/local energy markets.
req_ps_devo_4	It is not sure that in the course of the DRiVE project these other flexibility sources will be available but when the opportunity presents itself, they should be integrated.
req_ps_devo_5	Other appliances not yet listed may be added during the project.
req_ps_devo_6	DRiVE shall gather local household energy patterns via a Smartpower Suite Energy gateway which is connected to a smart meter per house.
req_ps_devo_7	DRiVE shall gather solar production measurements via the Smartpower Suite Energy gateway which is connected to a smart meter per relevant house.
req_ps_devo_8	The target is to also get access to the heat consumption (spatial heat and domestic hot water) per household via the central HN-BMS.
req_ps_devo_9	DRiVE shall gather all needed data-points to be able to forecast consumption/production/flexibility.
req_ps_devo_10	All above mentioned devices, data-points will need to adhere to GDPR security/privacy requirements which will be guaranteed via the Enervalis Smartpower Suite platform and related procedures and End User Licence Agreements (EULA).
ADO Stadium	
ID	Description
req_ps_ado_1	DRiVE shall directly control the energy storage system and provide smart charging possibilities
req_ps_ado_2	The DRiVE platform will communicate directly to the DSO via the USEF framework
req_ps_ado_3	The DRiVE platform will be able to provide frequency containment reserve services by reading the frequency of the grid and controlling the assets to respond to deviations of the normal frequency
req_ps_ado_4	The DRiVE platform will be able to send measurement data to the TSO
req_ps_ado_5	DRiVE will be used to forecast the assets of the site and the corresponding

	flexibility
req_ps_ado_6	The DRiVE platform will be able to gather allocation data for the different assets on the site
req_ps_ado_7	The DRiVE platform will be able to communicate with the BRP's system for sending forecasts and allocation data and receiving control signals
req_ps_ado_8	Optional: The DRiVE platform will be able to communicate directly to the TSO for delivering frequency restoration services
Giessen wind	
ID	Description
req_ps_gwind_1	The power quality and voltage control will be tested via a microgrid testbed from Typhoon HIL.
req_ps_gwind_2	Live testing and measuring for different scenarios is optional.
req_ps_gwind_3	DRiVE platform will be able to control the ESS via the SmartPowerSuite.
req_ps_gwind_4	DRiVE platform will be able to control the wind turbines via the SmartPowerSuite.
req_ps_gwind_5	Optional: The DRiVE platform will communicate directly to the DSO via the USEF framework.
req_ps_gwind_6	Optional: The DRiVE platform will be able to provide frequency containment reserve services by reading the frequency of the grid and controlling the assets to respond to deviations of the normal frequency.
req_ps_gwind_7	Optional: The DRiVE platform will be able to send measurement data to the TSO.
req_ps_gwind_8	Optional: DRiVE will be used to forecast the assets of the site and the corresponding flexibility.
req_ps_gwind_9	Optional: The DRiVE platform will be able to gather allocation data for the different assets on the site.
req_ps_gwind_10	Optional: The DRiVE platform will be able to communicate with the BRP's system for sending forecasts and allocation data and receiving control signals.
req_ps_gwind_11	Optional: The DRiVE platform will be able to communicate directly to the TSO for delivering frequency restoration services.
COMSA Head Office	
ID	Description
req_ps_comsa_1	LEG specific for tertiary buildings shall act as bridge between the building EMS and the DRiVE solution.
req_ps_comsa_2	The facility manager / building operator should have at any moment the possibility to suspend the 'cloud-driven' mode in the building if he considers that operation of the building is being jeopardised. This entails that: -The LEG would stop overwriting variables on the existing building EMS or any other building asset. -The facility manager would take over responsibility for driving the building assets from then on. -DRiVE solution would take care of maintaining consistency within the DRiVE platform while respecting facility manager's decision about this particular building

req_ps_comsa_3	<p>The facility manager / building operator would have the above-mentioned possibility by means of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The consumer portal. Here the decision on the suspension of the ‘cloud-driven’ mode could have some granularity. For example, HVAC considered on a floor-by-floor basis and storage battery considered independently. The LEG cabinet (2-position switch). Here suspension would have a more reliable effect (not dependent on the consumer portal and directly executed by the LEG) but would have no granularity: the suspension would apply to all assets in the building when the switch is toggled.
req_ps_comsa_4	<p>The in-building optimization shall minimise the cost of the energy consumption (implicit DR), given constrains such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -ToU tariff specific to the building (time slots and prices). -Demand penalties specific to the building (contracted demand). -Comfort (temperature) range established by facility management service. -Building occupation schedule established by facility management service. <p>For this purpose, HVAC units and storage battery shall be available as controllable assets.</p>
req_ps_comsa_5	<p>HVAC units and storage battery shall contribute to flexibility (explicit DR) by being available as controllable assets.</p>